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EDITORIAL

Dear ISHA members, dear readers

The reaction on the open call for papers for this Carnival, already volume XXI by now, shows the continued interest and need for publishing a journal in the ISHA framework. Not only provides it an accessible platform for students and early stage researchers in reworking and communicating their research following the scientific standards, but it also allows the editors to hone their skills in editing and working with the authors to improve their articles throughout the different stages of the publication process. The results of this are to be found in this publication, with a variety of topics, time periods and subdisciplines represented in this volume. I sincerely hope you will enjoy reading the articles in the present volume, and even consider submitting your contribution for the next call for papers.

Kind regards and viva ISHA!

Charlotte Rottiers

Ghent, 25.1.2021

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Enslaved nobles, ennobled slaves: The inversion of Roman society in Tacitus' description of the reign of Tiberius

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Abstract

The following paper approaches Tacitus' criticism of the Roman Principate in his Annals by analyzing several key episodes from the reign of Tiberius as described by the Roman historiographer, and looking in particular at Tacitus' implied inversion of the roles of master and slave under the emperor's reign.

By taking Tiberius as an example, the paper aims to invite further research into slavery and enslavement tropes in Tacitus' later works, as well as their usage as means of denouncing the Principate as unjust. Besides Tacitus, Sallust and Suetonius serve as important sources, the first as an influence on the Annales, the second as an author who has drawn from them.

Introduction

The Roman historiographer and senator Cornelius Tacitus (~58-117 CE) witnessed an age in which the Principate had already established itself as an accepted and stable institution of the Roman *res publica*.¹ The transitions between specific principes were no longer characterized by the potential return to Republican rule, but much rather by the question which Roman noble would be the next one to lay claim to the role of autocrat. Despite the Principate having become seemingly inexorable, Tacitus is anything but flattering towards it in his writings. During the first passages of his *Annales*, he explores the origins of the Principate and identifies the

¹ Anthony R. Birley, "The Life and Death of Cornelius Tacitus," *Historia: Zeitschrift für Alte Geschichte* 49 (2000); 246-247.

increasing accumulation of important privileges and positions of power by a single person, Augustus Caesar, as the process which lays the foundation of the autocratic authority for all principes following him. It is from this point going forward that Tacitus associates the decline of Republican values with the moral decline of its formerly dominant upper class:

[...] nullo adversante, cum ferocissimi per acies aut proscriptione cecidissent, ceteri nobilium, quanto quis servitio promptior, opibus et honoribus extollerentur ac novis ex rebus aucti tuta et praesentia quam vetera et periculosa mallent. neque provinciae illum rerum statum abnuebant, suspecto senatus populique imperio ob certamina potentium et avaritiam magistratum, invalido legum auxilio quae vi ambitu postremo pecunia turbabantur.

He was wholly unopposed, for the boldest spirits had fallen in battle, or in the proscription, while the remaining nobles, the readier they were to be slaves, were raised the higher by wealth and promotion, so that, aggrandised by revolution, they preferred the safety of the present to the dangerous past. Nor did the provinces dislike that condition of affairs, for they distrusted the government of the Senate and the people, because of the rivalries between the leading men and the capacity of the officials, while the protection of the laws was unavailing, as they were continually deranged by violence, intrigue, and finally by corruption.²

It is thus already at the very beginning of his *Annales* that Tacitus characterizes the relationship between Rome's aristocracy and the *princeps* as equivalent to the relationship between slaves and their master. He provides a lens through which all following interactions between these two factions of Roman rule are to be observed in the coming chapters of his work.

William Turpin ascribes to Tacitus the intent of teaching his readership through moralizing *exempla*.³ It can be assumed then that tropes associated with slavery play a central role in these exemplary narratives, in particular with regards to the Principate.

² Tac. Ann. 1.2.1.

³ William Turpin, "Stoic exempla, and the praecipuum munus annalium," *Classical Antiquity* 27 (2008); 360.

In the following essay, the tropes and symbols of slavery from Tacitus' *Annales* with regards to the interaction between the principes and the other members of Roman society are to be analyzed on an exemplary level. With regards to the usage of similar tropes among Tacitus' influences, namely Sallust (86-34/5 BCE), the role of slavery topics in Tacitus' establishment of moral *exempla* is to be investigated. The focus of the observation is to lie on the reign of Tiberius, covered in the first six volumes of Tacitus' *Annales*, as this is the first complete reign the historiographer describes in the *Annales*, which is why many of the tropes that will be utilised in his descriptions of later *principes* make their first appearance here. A more extended analysis of the topic could cover a larger part of the *Annales*, but would go beyond the scope of this essay.

The topic of the *princeps* Tiberius as tyrant in Tacitus' works has been approached in other articles, namely by A.J. Woodman in "Tiberius and the Taste of Power" (2006), which explores the depiction of the princeps as the literal devourer of the Republic.⁴ Rebecca Edwards has discussed Tiberius' retreat to Capri, a passage of Tacitus in which many exhibitions of tyrannical or enslaving behaviour, including the fragmentary *coprea*-episode mentioned below,⁵ are shown, pointing out how the island's superficial charm and deep-lying corruption mirrors its most prominent inhabitant.⁶ The topic of Tiberius specifically as enslaver has been approached by Mehran A. Nickbakht in "Fighting for Liberty, Embracing Slavery" (2006); that article approaches the pivotal passage of Tac. Ann. 1.7.1 with far more attention to detail than this essay could provide, and is thus an important basis for my argumentation.

⁴ A.J. Woodman, "Tiberius and the Taste of Power: The Year 33 in Tacitus," *The Classical Quarterly* 56 (2006), 188-189.

⁵ Suet. Tib. 61.6.

⁶ Rebecca Edwards, "Tacitus, Tiberius and Capri," *Latomus* 70 (2011), 1057.

The *princeps* as enslaver

The enslavement of free citizens and the treatment of free citizens as slaves have been associated with ‘oriental despotism’ since at least the works of Herodotus and Aischylos. A ruler who is shown humiliating or murdering his own citizens, such as Herodotus’ Cambyses,⁷ is thus to a Greek or Roman reader evocative of the tradition of Eastern tyrants. These would often be called *reges* in Roman literary canon,⁸ which further connected them to Rome’s own mythical despot-kings. Loyal writers in the early Principate were thus very careful to differentiate the concepts of *rex* and *princeps* from one another (see for example Curtius Rufus)⁹, whereas critics of single *principes*, or in the case of Tacitus the entire institution of the Principate, would draw conscious connections between the two forms of autocracy.

From the position of the Roman reader, familiar with Herodotus, the basic responsibility for the enslavement of free citizens lay not only with the despotic slaver. When Cyrus II is shown considering expanding his kingdom into a particularly rich and bounteous region, he at first declines, citing that the overflowing wealth of that region would make him and his citizens decadent and complacent, fit only to be eventually enslaved by stronger, less luxurious peoples.¹⁰ From this the idea that continuous decadence and moral decay inevitably leads to enslavement of the formerly powerful could be derived. Whosoever let his traditional mores languish would eventually descend to the level of a barbarian, whose enslavement was seen as justified from the Roman perspective.¹¹ Sallust, describing the moral development of the Republic in his *Bellum Catilinae*, follows a similar argumentative arc.¹²

⁷ Hdt. 3.34.

⁸ Tac. Ann. 2.1.

⁹ Curt. 10.9.3.

¹⁰ Hdt. 9.122.

¹¹ Wilfried Nippel, "The Construction of the ‘Other’," *Greeks and Barbarians*, ed. Thomas Harrison, (Edinburgh: University Press 2002), 291.

¹² Sall. Cat. 12.1-5.

A first indicator for this form of perceived willing enslavement in the *Annales* can be found in Tac. Ann. 1.2. The enslavement of the free citizens of Rome is accompanied by a description of the general decline of Roman morals, culminating in the loss of all societal coherence.¹³

The first true *princeps*, Augustus, is not thoroughly covered in Tacitus, but the biographer Suetonius, familiar with Tacitus, distances Augustus from the conscious enslavement of the entire *populum*. Nonetheless, he does describe at least one case in which the *princeps* treats a high-ranking citizen as a slave:

[...] et Quintum Gallium praetorem, in officio salutationis tabellas duplices veste tectas tenentem, suspicatus gladium oculere, nec quicquam statim, ne aliud inveniretur, ausus inquirere, paulo post per centuriones et milites raptum e tribunali servilem in modum torsit ac fatentem nihil iussit occidi, prius oculis eius sua manu effossis [...]

[...] when Quintus Gallius, a praetor, held some folded tablets under his robe as he was paying his respects, Augustus, suspecting that he had a sword concealed there, did not dare to make a search on the spot for fear it should turn out to be something else; but a little later he had Gallius hustled from the tribunal by some centurions and soldiers, tortured him as if he were a slave, and though he made no confession, ordered his execution, first tearing out the man's eyes with his own hand.¹⁴

This section is followed by a description of Augustus' claiming of the *tribunitia potestas*.¹⁵

Thus, the degradation of powerful citizens to slaves is directly associated with Augustus' acquisition of power.

¹³ Tac. Ann. 1.4.

¹⁴ Suet. Aug. 27.4.

¹⁵ Suet. Aug. 27.5.

The portrayal of the willing servile subordination of the aristocracy eventually begins in earnest with the ascent to power of Tiberius. This is the first transition between one *princeps* and the next within the *Annales*, and can thus be seen as exemplary for similar processes in later books. As Nickbakht mentions,¹⁶ the attention of the reader within Tac. Ann. 1.7. is suddenly drawn from the personal consequences of the death of Augustus for Tiberius towards Rome:

At Romae ruere in servitium consules, patres, eques. quanto quis inlustrior, tanto magis falsi ac festinantes, vultuque composito ne laeti excessu principis ne tristiores primordio, lacrimas gaudium, questus adulationem miscebant. Sex. Pompeius et Sex. Appuleius consules primi in verba Tiberii Caesaris iuravere [...]

Meanwhile at Rome people plunged into slavery—consuls, senators, knights. The higher a man's rank, the more eager his hypocrisy, and his looks the more carefully studied, so as neither to betray joy at the decease of one emperor nor sorrow at the rise of another, while he mingled delight and lamentations with his flattery. Sextus Pompeius and Sextus Apuleius, the consuls, were the first to swear allegiance to Tiberius Caesar [...]¹⁷

According to Matthews¹⁸, the transition from Augustus to Tiberius wasn't an unforeseeable change of paradigm. Rather, the *princeps* had spent the last years of his life ensuring that Tiberius would be able to take over his position. Tacitus uses the imagery of the “plunge into slavery” as a contrast to the previously described murder of Agrippa Postumus by Tiberius and his mother, Livia.¹⁹ Even though an autocratic tyrant has committed an unjust crime against an (admittedly flawed, but innocent) member of their own family,²⁰ he is not held accountable by a heroic defender of Republican virtue. This narrative of unpunished crime can be seen as a foil

¹⁶ Mehran A. Nickbakht, "Fighting for Liberty, Embracing Slavery: Tacitus, 'Annals' 1.7.1", *Museum Helveticum* 63 (2006); 39.

¹⁷ Tac. Ann. 1.7.

¹⁸ John Matthews, "Tacitus, Acta Senatus, and the inauguration of Tiberius," *Roman Perspectives: Studies in Political and Cultural History, from the First to the Fifth Century*, ed. John Matthews (Swansea: Classical Press of Wales 2010); 58-59.

¹⁹ Tac. Ann. 1.6.

²⁰ Tac. Ann. 1.3.

to the mythical origins of Republican values in Rome, the rape of Lucretia and the consequent dissolution of the Roman monarchy through its subjects.²¹ The latter uprising was in fact led by the ancestor of the same Marcus Iunius Brutus whose failure to defend the Republic Tacitus laments at the very beginning of the *Annales* („*Postquam Bruto et Cassio caesis nulla iam publica arma [...]*“ Tac. Ann. 1.2). Instead of a new Brutus arising to purge Tiberius’ reign, originated in violence, it is the consuls, those whose office represents the pinnacle of the *res publica*, who are the first to swear an oath on Tiberius, leading Tacitus’ *ruere in servitium*. Nickbahkt extends the verbal and thematic connections of this scene to Virgil’s depiction of Aeneas.²² In the Aeneid, Aeneas is being portrayed as a defender of *libertas*.²³ Instead of *libertas*, however, the descendants of the founders of the *res publica* are shown by Tacitus to intentionally prefer *servitium*. Seneca, according to William Turpin²⁴ an influence on Tacitus’ formulation of *exempla*, harshly condemns willing slaves who refuse to interfere with tyranny as worse than the tyrant himself, as they contribute to tyranny without even benefitting from it.²⁵

An important aspect of slavery is the “social death”, the uprooting of the slave from their previous life by taking away their previous name as well as other markers of identity, a practice common in Rome, as Bodel writes, and usually paired with maintaining fragments of the slave’s previous identity as part of a form of institutionalized liminality.²⁶ Tacitus’ Tiberius doesn’t have the members of the aristocracy die a literal social death, but he neglects mentioning their names when new consuls are being introduced to him:

²¹ Liv. 1.58-60.

²² Mehran A. Nickbakht, "Fighting for Liberty, Embracing Slavery: Tacitus, ‘Annals’ 1.7.1" (2006), 40.

²³ Verg. Aen. 8.648.

²⁴ William Turpin, "Stoic exempla, and the praecipuum munus annalium," *Classical Antiquity* 27 (2008), 368.

²⁵ Sen. Ira 3.14-15.

²⁶ John Bodel, "Death and Social Death in Ancient Rome," *On Human Bondage: After Slavery and Social Death*, eds. John Bodel & Walter Scheidel, (Chichester: Wiley Blackwell 2017), 96-97.

Modo subtractis candidatorum nominibus originem cuiusque et vitam et stipendia descripsit ut qui forent intellegeretur; aliquando ea quoque significatione subtracta candidatos hortatus ne ambitu comitia turbarent, suam ad id curam pollicitus est. Plerumque eos tantum apud se professos disseruit, quorum nomina consulibus edidisset; posse et alios profiteri, si gratiae aut meritis confiderent: speciosa verbis, re inania aut subdola, quantoque maiore libertatis imagine tegebantur, tanto eruptura ad infensius servitium.

Sometimes he kept back the names of the candidates, describing their origin, their life and military career, so that it might be understood who they were. Occasionally even these hints were withheld, and, after urging them not to disturb the elections by canvassing, he would promise his own help towards the result. Generally he declared that only those had offered themselves to him as candidates whose names he had given to the consuls, and that others might offer themselves if they had confidence in their influence or merit. A plausible profession this in words, but really unmeaning and delusive, and the greater the disguise of freedom which marked it, the more cruel the enslavement into which it was soon to plunge us.²⁷

To the strongly familial Roman aristocrats, the connection between their family name and personal accomplishments was of immense importance.²⁸ Having this connection ignored while accessing the nominally highest rank of the *res publica* was thus a severe humiliation. The utterances made by Tacitus' Tiberius about the new consuls (their place of origin and skill set) are additionally reminiscent of the information that slave merchants would provide at the market in the form of *tituli*. Tiberius is portrayed not as introducing new consuls to the Senate, but as selling them slaves, a feasible step after the “plunge into slavery” from Tac. Ann. 1.7, which also, as already mentioned, features the consuls foremost.

²⁷ Tac. Ann. 1.81.

²⁸ Helmut Rix, "Gentile," *Der Neue Pauly*, eds. Hubert Cancik, Helmuth Schneider & Manfred Landfester. Accessed December 9, 2021.

The *slave as dominus*

The inversion of the enslaved aristocrat can be found in the enslaving slave, who meddles with the realm of politics that should be exclusive to the upper classes. Suetonius mentions, referring to Tacitus,²⁹ a case in which Tiberius is advised by a *coprea* (buffoon) on the manner of punishment for a treasonous aristocrat:

Annalibus suis vir consularis inseruit, frequenti quodam convivio, cui et ipse affuerit, interrogatum eum subito et clare a quodam nano astante mensae inter copreas, cur Paconius maiestatis reus tam diu viveret, statim quidem petulantiam linguae obiurgasse, ceterum post paucos dies scripsisse senatui, ut de poena Paconi quam primum statueret.

A man of consular rank writes in his annals, that at table, where he himself was present with a large company, he was suddenly asked aloud by a dwarf who stood by amongst the buffoons, why Paconius, who was under prosecution for treason, lived so long. Tiberius immediately reprimanded him for his pertness; but wrote to the senate a few days after, to proceed without delay to the punishment of Paconius.³⁰

This episode can be seen as pointing towards two grievances: on the one hand, it shows how easily manipulated Tiberius, at this time withdrawn to his pleasure island of Capri, has become. On the other hand, it inverts the order of Roman society. Instead of Senate being called into session to decide on the proper punishment for a member of Roman high society (Paconius portrays Tacitus as one of the accusers in the Silanus case),³¹ it is a slave from the bottom rungs of Roman society who gives the (potentially purely humorous, as he is a jester) advice to dispose of Paconius.

²⁹ Suetonius refers to a *vir consularis* writing about the incident in his *Annali*, which implies a Tacitean episode, likely belonging to the fifth book of the *Annales*, which has only been preserved in fragments.

³⁰ Suet. Tib. 61.6.

³¹ Tac. Ann. 3.67.

This is not the only case in which the slaves of the narratives of Suetonius or Tacitus lead to the capture or execution of influential Romans. The *Annales* repeatedly mention slaves being interrogated by Tiberius to gain incriminating evidence on their masters.³² The inflationary acquisition of slaves, seen as a sign of decadence,³³ becomes the bane of their *domini*. But not all cases of slaves turning on their masters within Tacitus' narrative are coerced; the historiographer also describes cases of slaves willingly and intentionally putting pressure on their masters by referring to Tiberius:

Exim promptum quod multorum intimis questibus tegebatur. Incedebat enim deterrimo cuique licentia impune probra et invidiam in bonos excitandi arrepta imagine Caesaris; libertique etiam ac servi, patrono vel domino cum voces, cum manus intentarent, ultro metuebantur.

Next was exposed an abuse, hitherto the subject of many a whispered complaint. The vilest wretches used a growing freedom in exciting insult and obloquy against respectable citizens, and escaped punishment by clasping some statue of the emperor. The very freedman or slave was often an actual terror to his patron or master whom he would menace by word and gesture.³⁴

The very image of the *princeps* has thus become a means of social upheaval that enables slaves and freedmen to openly question Roman societal norms. Social unrest as a consequence of misrule is a trope which is also employed by Sallust, an acknowledged influence of Tacitus.³⁵ In Sallust's works, it is the *plebs* which intends to rebel against the aristocracy in the follow-up to the Catiline Conspiracy.³⁶ Neither the slaves of Tacitus nor the plebeians of Sallust are portrayed as being justified in their rebellions. In both cases, however, their unrest is shown to be the symptom of the moral decay of the upper classes.³⁷

³² Tac. Ann. 2.30; 3.14; 3.23; 3.67.

³³ Tac. Ann. 3.53.

³⁴ Tac. Ann. 3.36.

³⁵ Tac. Ann. 3.30.

³⁶ Sall. Cat. 37.1.

³⁷ Sall.Cat. 10.1-3.

Another section which clarifies the inversion of the social order under Tiberius is the episode of the False Agrippa. In this, a slave of the previously killed Agrippa Postumus assumes the identity of his master³⁸ and prepares to march onto Rome:

Vulgabatur interim per Italiam servatum munere deum Agrippam, credebatur Romae; iamque Ostiam invectum multitudo ingens, iam in urbe clandestini coetus celebrabant, cum Tiberium anceps cura distrahere, vine militum servum suum coerceret an inanem credulitatem tempore ipso vanescere sineret: modo nihil spernendum, modo non omnia metuenda ambiguus pudoris ac metus reputabat.

It was rumoured meanwhile throughout Italy, and was believed at Rome, that Agrippa had been saved by the blessing of Heaven. Already at Ostia, where he had arrived, he was the centre of interest to a vast concourse as well as to secret gatherings in the capital, while Tiberius was distracted by the doubt whether he should crush this slave of his by military force or allow time to dissipate a silly credulity. Sometimes he thought that he must overlook nothing, sometimes that he need not be afraid of everything, his mind fluctuating between shame and terror.³⁹

The former slave of the imperial family is, even though he dies shortly thereafter, a serious threat to Tiberius. Not only is he being widely accepted as truthful and attracts followers by his reputation alone, he also appears to genuinely possess the potential to endanger Tiberius' position. Clemens' march on Rome appears as a parody of the classic hero story, archetypical for which is Herodot's portrayal of Cyrus II:⁴⁰ The scion of the royal family, banished or condemned to death by a paranoid relative rife with tyrannical traits, returns to the capital to make claim to his rightful throne. Thus Tacitus expands on his image of Tiberius as tyrant, which as Edwards writes he also employs otherwise,⁴¹ while placing the Principate into the tradition of "oriental" Herodotean ruling dynasties.⁴² On the other hand, he also points out the weakness of the Principate, as a slave without means is capable of threatening its legitimacy

³⁸ Tac. Ann. 2.39.

³⁹ Tac. Ann. 2.40.

⁴⁰ Hdt. 1.110-112.

⁴¹ Rebecca Edwards, "Tacitus, Tiberius and Capri," *Latomus* 70 (2011), 1052-1053. Edwards refers to Tac. Ann. 6.6. specifically to explain Tacitus' depiction of Tiberius as a Platonic tragic tyrant.

⁴² R. Schmitt, "Astyages", *Encyclopaedia Iranica*, ed. Ahmad Ashraf; Accessed December 9, 2021.

through simple deception. Instead of the Senate, which under Tiberius only consists of willing slaves, it is a single actual slave who becomes the first person to attempt to topple Tiberius' power, albeit not motivated by the Republican *virtus*.

Conclusion

In his *Annales*, Tacitus adapts Sallust's means of displaying his personal grievances with the decline of the Republic by applying slavery-adjacent tropes to both the members of the Roman aristocracy and the plebs. By exchanging the roles of *dominus* and *servus* in portraying the early Principate, he guides the process already sketched out by Sallust towards its logical extreme. The social hierarchy of the Roman Republic has now been turned on its head, and the sole person to maintain their power within these upheavals is the *princeps* himself. The main responsibility for this lies not with the *princeps*, however, who is portrayed as himself being disgusted with the subordination of the enslaved senators,⁴³ but with those who are shown to not only tolerate their enslavement, but to actively plunge into it, as described in Tac. Ann. 1.7. Tacitus, having himself witnessed the turbulent Year of the Four Emperors, thus treads a path common for Flavian and post-Flavian authors of the late first and early second century AD, criticising the Principate while also coming to begrudging terms with its prolonged existence by excising himself from the senatorial class held responsible for its establishment.

A larger-scale investigation of this topic might approach Tacitus' depiction of the other *principes* of the Julio-Claudian era, as well as differences between imperial power as depicted in the *Annales* and the earlier *Histories*.

⁴³ Tac. Ann. 3.65.

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‘Base by Birth, Mean by Estate, and Calling’: Fashion and the Social Order in Early Modern England

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Abstract

Recent historiographical trends have begun to reemphasise the integral role played by dress in early modern society and its unique role in fostering both individual and group identities. However, little attention has been paid to placing these new discoveries within the broader narrative of social history. In doing so, it becomes apparent that dress is integral to the formation and conception of the early modern social order and the complex interactions between communities. This paper seeks to synthesise historiographical developments in the field of English social history as well as textile studies. This way, this study aims to demonstrate that dress in early modern England provided a unique opportunity for members of the aspirational middling sort to self-fashion in an increasingly mobile society, challenging traditional roles and leading to anxiety amongst the gentry and aristocracy. In addition, this research draws upon a diverse array of primary sources, including sermons, conduct books, and English sumptuary legislation to reveal the contemporary importance of costume and appearance. Ultimately, in consolidating these disparate sources, one can observe the crucial role fashion played in the arbitration and enforcement of the social order in early modern England, and thus, its usefulness as an analytical tool for social historians.

Introduction

It seems incongruous that clothing, an object as old and ever-changing as society itself, has seldom been incorporated into the examination of early modern lives. Scholars frequently disregard costume studies as ‘hemline histories’ practical solely for dating artwork, or at best, an economic analysis of consumption patterns.¹ Finally, historians are beginning to explore the profound impact of textiles on the complex relationships of early modern society.² As recent scholarship has noted, clothing was a means to construct and maintain individual identities and to emphasise and delineate between socio-economic hierarchies.³ Social order and the complex, interlocking relationships that governed society remains a prominent topic of discussion amongst social historians of the early modern period. Their interest reveals how the ‘middling sort’, a dynamic group existing between the landed gentry and the labouring poor, comprised of individuals ranging from yeomen farmers to urban artisans, routinely challenged this traditional order within an increasingly mobile society.⁴ The study of dress, though often ignored, provides compelling evidence to support the dramatic and radical changes observed by historians, particularly contemporary attitudes towards clothing, differences between urban and rural regions, and the institution of sumptuary legislation. Through an analysis of these historiographical strands, supplemented by an array of primary material, it is evident that while elite society attempted to use clothing as a way to enforce social stratification, ultimately these same resources set a standard of ‘fashionability’ that allowed the middling sort to more effectively emulate the gentry and demonstrate their social mobility.

¹ Christopher Breward, *The Culture of Fashion* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1995), 1-3 and S. Vincent, ‘When I am in Good Habit’: Clothes in English Culture c. 1550 - c. 1670’ (PhD diss., University of York, 2002), 12-16.

² Susan Vincent, *Dressing the Elite: Clothes in Early Modern England* (Oxford: Berg, 2003), 2.

³ Diana Crane, *Fashion and its Social Agendas: Class, Gender and Identity in Clothing* (London: University of Chicago Press, 2000), 4.

⁴ Jonathan Barry, ‘Introduction’, in *The Middling Sort of People: Culture, Society, and Politics in England, 1550-1800*, ed. John Barry et. all (London: Palgrave, 1994), 2.

This article seeks to assess the degree to which dress can be used as an analytical tool for social historians investigating the middling sort in early modern England. It will investigate how scholars have utilised dress in their studies and the conception of clothing by contemporaries through the employment of historiography on early modern clothing, trade, sumptuary legislation, and moral conduct, alongside contemporary sermons, conduct books, and acts or proclamations of apparel from the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. By marrying historiographical trends with primary source analysis, it becomes apparent that early modern society was preoccupied with clothing. It is evident that both the gentry and the middling sort conceived dress as crucial to understanding their social identity and position in the ‘great chain of being’. More specially, garments held both a moral and political importance, and it was increasingly important for members of the gentry and aristocracy to safeguard their apparel through various means. Aspirational members of the middling sort could simultaneously use dress within their socially mobile societies to emulate the gentry and blur social hierarchies. Therefore, this essay presents a guide to scholars seeking to understand the impact of fashion on the social, political, and moral makeup of early modern English society, ultimately establishing that the study of clothing and textiles has a place within the historiography of social history alongside more traditional studies.

Historiographical Roots of Fashion and the Social Order

To understand the complexity of early modern social relations and the influence of clothing on the establishment of social order, one must connect their seemingly disparate theoretical and historiographical foundations. Of note is Thorstein Veblen’s *The Theory of the Leisure Class*. Even though its focus was on late nineteenth-century American fashion, Veblen’s thesis, specifically his theories on emulation and conspicuous consumption can be directly applied to

the study of early modern communities. Clothing was carefully guarded and consumed by elite members of the male society as a display of their reputability and status as gentlemen.⁵ The fact that those with financial means, identified as the bourgeoisie or middle class by Veblen, deliberately emulated these styles through their personal consumption, prompted the need for a constant redevelopment of fashionable apparel in order to maintain distinct socio-economic group identities.⁶ Veblen's work has fundamentally influenced the way scholars have studied fashion and its influence on social order. Its distinct Marxist elements provide an inextricable connection to the study of social history and the labours of historians such as Daniel Roche, whose analysis of early modern French fashion reaches a similar conclusion, asserting that 'clothes became weapons in the battle of appearances'.⁷ Veblen's theory is reinforced through Norbert Elias's *The Civilising Process*, which outlines the nobility's attempts to create a unique culture, and a subsequent 'trickle-down' effect in which civilised behaviours travelled down the social ladder from the elite to their 'social inferiors'.⁸ In tandem, these two influential works support this essay's claim that the processes of emulation and conspicuous consumption were affecting social relations and disturbing social order in early modern England.

Furthermore, the study and contextual importance of social history are integral to understanding the complex dynamic between clothing and social relations. E.M.W Tillyard notably provides a careful analysis of Elizabethan social structures by outlining the ideas of the Great Chain of Being and the Body Politic in Elizabethan thought and writing.⁹ Analogous works also demonstrate how these imagined orders manifested, looking specifically at gestural codes and

⁵ Thorstein Veblen, *The Theory of the Leisure Class* (London, 1899), 24, 53.

⁶ Veblen, *The Theory of the Leisure Class*, 22.

⁷ D.E Allen, 'Fashion as a Social Process', *Textile History* 22 (1991): 350 and Daniel Roche, *The Culture of Clothing: Dress and Fashion in the Ancien Regime* (trans. by Jean Birrell) (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 1996), 6.

⁸ Norbert Elias, *The Civilising Process* (London: Wiley-Blackwell, 2000), 64, 116.

⁹ E.M.W Tillyard, *The Elizabethan World Picture* (London, 1943).

books of conduct in the enforcement of elite identity and the maintenance of the social order, drawing heavily from the anthropological observations of Norbert Elias.¹⁰ Governed by Marxist ideology, early social historians, such as E.P. Thompson and J.H. Hexter, failed to acknowledge the importance of the middling sort in this order, in favour of ‘history from below’.¹¹ This was challenged by the social historians of the 1980s, especially by Keith Wrightson, whose work is invaluable in understanding the nature of social relations in England in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, and particularly, the role played by the middling sort in this complicated community. Wrightson highlights the ability to transition between the lower gentry and the middling sort as well as contemporary ideas of social order that demonstrate ‘society as it ought to be’ in contrast to reality.¹² Wrightson’s work led to a growing interest in studying the middling sort, encapsulated most comprehensively in the collected essays *The Middling Sort of People* edited by Jonathan Barry and Christopher Brooks.¹³ These studies parallelly describe the principal strains of social history that come together to illuminate scholars on the complex web of social relationships in early modern England and provide a frame of reference for this essay. More specifically, these sources provide a conceptual framework as to who, exactly, constituted the middling sort in early modern England and how they could interact with members of the gentry within their local communities. It also illuminates the blurring social boundaries within early modern society, which allowed the middling sort to utilise dress as a form of social currency and provide insight into the role of morality and religion in contemporary society.

¹⁰ See, for example, J. Walter, ‘Gesturing at Authority: Deciphering the Gestural Code of Early Modern England’, in, *The Politics of Gesture: Historical Perspectives*, ed. M Braddick (Past and Present, Supplement, 4, 2009) and Keith Thomas, *In Pursuit of Civility: Manners and Civilisation in Early Modern England*, (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2018).

¹¹ Barry, ‘Introduction’, 9-10.

¹² Keith Wrightson, *English Society 1580-1680* (London: Routledge 1982), 2-8.

¹³ Barry et. al, *The Middling Sort of People*.

Most importantly, the diverse study of textiles and clothing works in conjunction with related efforts to study the social order. Economic histories such as those by Lorna Weatherill, Keith Wrightson, and Joan Thirsk have had limited scopes as they investigate clothing and textiles to demonstrate changing patterns of consumption and the emergence of a consumer society within early modern England in the late seventeenth century.¹⁴ Few attempts have been made to understand the social role of clothing in early modern England and those that have, prioritised elite clothing culture.¹⁵ A significant body of work has also emerged in recent years concerning sartorial politics, exploring the role of early modern clothing in the enforcement of royal and courtly identities.¹⁶ Nonetheless, while much of this research is solely applicable to the upper gentry and the aristocracy, certain findings, particularly the notion of clothing being used as a tool of social distinction, can be translated to a study of the social historian's middling sort. Danae Tankard has completed a comprehensive study on seventeenth-century clothing in provincial England. Using a series of case studies from Sussex, she succinctly summarises what was worn in the countryside, how they accessed these goods locally and through commerce with London, as well as the multitude of ways in which clothing was conceived as governing social, gender, and age identities.¹⁷ However, while her work addresses, in part, the middling sort, her primary examples concentrate on members of the rural gentry who possessed the financial resources to travel to London or shop via proxy for current fashions.¹⁸ Regardless, this

¹⁴ Joan Thirsk, *Economic Policy and Projects: The Development of a Consumer Society in Early Modern England* (Oxford: Oxford University Press 1978), Lorna Weatherill, *Consumer Behaviour & Material Culture in Britain 1660-1760*, Second Edition (London: Routledge 1996), and Keith Wrightson, *Earthly Necessities: Economic Lives in Early Modern Britain, 1470-1750* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000).

¹⁵ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite* and Vincent, "When I am in Good Habit".

¹⁶ See for example, Maria Hayward, *Stuart Style: Monarchy, Dress and the Scottish Male Elite* (London; New Haven: Yale University Press, 2020) and Erin Griffey, *Sartorial Politics in Early Modern Europe: Fashioning Women* (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2019).

¹⁷ Danae Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England* (London: Bloomsbury Visual Arts 2020), 1-17.

¹⁸ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 65, 74-83

literature presents compelling evidence that suggests the advantages of exploring the social and cultural role of clothing in early modern England beyond an elite level.

A growing number of publications explore the lowest orders of society and the proliferation of fashion to the labouring poor.¹⁹ Of note in this scholarship are the works of Margaret Spufford and Susan Mee, both of whom have published extensively on the subject- they mainly specialise on the diverse impecunious population of rural England.²⁰ Unfortunately, few of these monographs consider the middling sort, with wide-ranging incomes and varying access to material goods. Nevertheless, by combining these distinct trends of historiography with pioneering work on sumptuary legislation such as that of Francis Baldwin and Wilfrid Hooper and their successors, N.B Harte and Alan Hunt, one can piece together the complex puzzle of early modern clothing. They can then ascertain its undeniable importance in governing social relations and creating and challenging unique communal identities.²¹ Ultimately, it is evident that the study of clothing can effectively contribute to the broader study of history.

¹⁹ Steven King and Christina Payne, 'The Dress of the Poor', *Textile History* 22 (2002), 1-8.

²⁰ Margaret Spufford, *The Great Reclothing of Rural England* (London: Hambledon Press, 1994), Margaret Spufford and Susan Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort: 1570-1700* (New York: OUP Oxford, 2017).

²¹ Frances Baldwin, *Sumptuary Legislation and Personal Regulation in England* (Baltimore 1923), Wilfrid Hooper, 'The Tudor Sumptuary Laws', *The English Historical Review* 30 (1915), Alan Hunt, *Governance of the Consuming Passions, A History of Sumptuary Law* (London: Palgrave 1996), and N.B. Harte, 'State Control of Dress and Social Change in Pre-Industrial England', in, *Trade, Government and Economy in Pre-Industrial England*,(eds.) D.C. Coleman & A.H. John (London, 1976), 132-65.

Order and Obedience in Early Modern English Society

Contemporary attitudes towards the social order should be considered. Sermons such as the 1547 *Homily on Obedience* stressed that God had structured the world in ‘a most excellent and perfect order’, and failure to adhere to one’s preordained social position could only result in discord and the breakdown of society.²² This ‘Great Chain of Being’ drew from medieval precedents of cosmic order and Christian morality to create a ladder or chain beginning with inanimate objects, through plants, animals, man, and ultimately angels.²³ In an effort to maintain order during periods of increased social mobility, elites sought to create a unique culture that would distance them from the middling sort.²⁴ They accomplished this in part through the publication of conduct books and treatises, such as Sir Thomas Elyot’s *Boke Named the Governour*, which outlined the education and pedigree required for any productive member of society or member of state, and emphasised that ‘without order may be nothing stable or permanent’.²⁵

Similarly, polite manners became a sign of deference, forcing people to behave according to their respective position within society.²⁶ Gestural codes were equally important as physical signs of courtesy, many of which involved articles of clothing such as docking one’s hat to a social superior.²⁷ This confirms that dress was an unmistakable symbol of status and respect, that could be used as a tool in enforcing order. However, equally important to the contextualisation of social relations in early modern England is the growing mobility of the

²² Thomas Cranmer, ‘The Homily on Obedience’, *First Book of Homilies* (1547), 105.

²³ Tillyard, *The Elizabethan World Picture*, 7, 35-6 and Wrightson, *Earthly Necessities*, 27.

²⁴ Barry, ‘Introduction’, 24.

²⁵ Sir Thomas Elyot, *The Boke named the Governour* (1531) 4-5.

²⁶ Thomas, *In Pursuit of Civility*, 19, 68.

²⁷ Walter, ‘Gesturing at Authority’, 120.

middling sort and the ‘permeable membrane’ that granted those with means access into the ranks of the lower gentry.²⁸ While contemporaries sought to segregate society into categories or estates, in reality, this was significantly complicated by the lofty aspirations of many yeomen and professionals, along with an accumulation of wealth in the sixteenth century that made their ascent possible.²⁹ Therefore, in addition to their behaviours, the gentry turned to clothing as a means of separating themselves from their social inferiors.

Early modern textiles and material culture also require contextualisation to draw a distinct parallel to the changing social relations described above. Clothing was closely linked to decorum and appropriate behaviour as well as a civilised identity.³⁰ While theorists and historians often attribute the emergence of conspicuous consumption to the nineteenth-century bourgeoisie, its origins can be traced back to the beginnings of a consumer culture in the early modern period.³¹ Although some cite the years following the Civil War (1642-1651) as the initial roots of fashionable imitation, evidence suggests that emulation predated the expansion of the consumer market and was indicative of a shift in social morality.³² The growing prosperity of yeomen farmers in the sixteenth century contributed to the ‘erosion’ of the old economic order seen through a growing pattern of social mobility and increased spending as well as social emulation.³³ For most households, besides food, clothing constituted the most substantial annual expenditure, signifying its innate importance.³⁴ Greater accessibility to material goods, both domestic and imported, led to an increasing number of popular styles, and

²⁸ Wrightson, *English Society*, 8.

²⁹ Wrightson, *English Society*, 4-6.

³⁰ Thomas, *In Pursuit of Civility*, 19.

³¹ Sara Pennell, ‘Consumption and Consumerism in Early Modern England’, *The Historical Journal* 42 (1999), 558.

³² Barry, ‘Introduction’, 19.

³³ Wrightson, *Earthly Necessities*, 3-7.

³⁴ Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, 4 and Weatherill, *Consumer Behavior*, 119.

the rapid evolution of fashion.³⁵ This culminated in the increased importance of clothing to ‘reveal or conceal social position’.³⁶

The Proliferation of Fashionable Ideals Across England and its Consequences

The nationwide increase in consumption significantly impacted the clothing worn by the wealthy, the poor, and the middling sort across urban environments and the countryside, in both similar and disparate ways. London was the capital of fashion, and residents relied on apparel for public social display, where it could be recognised, acknowledged and replicated.³⁷ Due to its centre for international trade and fabric importation, urban fashion tended to be more colourful and varied, and members of the middling sort had better access to domestic and imported goods than their rural counterparts.³⁸ In contrast, practicality often dictated the styles in the rural areas, despite the desire of many country inhabitants. For many members of the country gentry, they could shop in London for fashionable styles either in person, or through the use of a proxy.³⁹ However, this did not prevent the middling sort, located outside the cities, from dressing fashionably as probate inventories reported an increase in the quantity and quality of clothing owned by yeomen in comparison to their less affluent neighbours.⁴⁰ Regardless of the region, clothing symbolised social status and connections, intended for a public demonstration of wealth and identity.⁴¹ Rural residents also benefited from the diffusion of urban goods to the countryside, often in the hands of petty chapmen or travelling merchants,

³⁵ N.B. Harte, ‘The Economics of Clothing in the Late Seventeenth Century’, *Textile History* 22 (1991), 278 and Thirsk, *Economic Policy and Projects*, 14-15.

³⁶ Weatherill, *Consumer Behavior*, 9 and Roche, *The Culture of Clothing*, 4.

³⁷ Breward *The Culture of Fashion*, 50-52.

³⁸ Maria Anne Hayward, *Rich apparel: clothing and the law in Henry VII's England* (London: Ashgate, 2009), 332.

³⁹ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 82-83.

⁴⁰ Anne Buck, ‘Clothing and Textiles in Bedfordshire Inventories, 1617-1620’, *Costume* 34 (2000), 29.

⁴¹ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 332.

who carried cloth, trims, and haberdashery material to small villages.⁴² Local mercers are also possessed a considerable amount of material and ready-made goods, particularly by the latter portion of the seventeenth century.⁴³ Margaret Spufford conducted extensive research on the importance of petty chapmen in the distribution of textiles across the country. They were especially known for the sale of decoration and embellishment used to reflect status and wealth as well as accessible ready-made clothing and accessories.⁴⁴ With their suppliers located in London, chapmen, many of whom later established market stalls or storefronts, provided an essential connection between urban fashion and the countryside- thus, they minimised some of the fundamental disparities in wealth and style.⁴⁵ It is evident that members of the urban and rural middling sort, including yeomen farmers, shop-keepers, and professionals, all experienced a degree of economic prosperity that enabled them to invest in the growing number of fashionable styles and to cultivate their image in a manner that those socially beneath them could not.⁴⁶

⁴² Weatherill, *Consumer Behaviour*, 90 and Spufford, *The Great Reclathing*, 51-52.

⁴³ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 58-69.

⁴⁴ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 119 and Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, xvi.

⁴⁵ Spufford, *The Great Reclathing*, 58, 78.

⁴⁶ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 327-328.

Identity, Morality, and Clothing in a Contemporary Context

Due to the proliferation of fashion across the country, distinct perceptions towards apparel became deeply entrenched in the enforcement of the social order, driving scholars to assess the impact of clothing and dress on contemporary attitudes.⁴⁷ In addition to describing the appropriate manners for behaving at court and at home, conduct books were instrumental in enforcing the importance of clothing as a social tool linked to decorum and status.⁴⁸ They dictated the origins of modern conceptions of the self and the importance of appearance as a display of inner character.⁴⁹ One of the most influential conduct books in England and abroad was Baldassare Castiglione's *The Courtier*. Hoby's English 1561 translation proved to be a seminal work in connecting apparel to the broader formation of an elite cultural identity. Castiglione argued that a man 'ought to determine with himselfe what he will appeere to be, and in suche sorte as he desireth to bee esteamed so to appaile himselfe, and make his garmentes helpe him to be counted suche a one.'⁵⁰ Over a century later, Sir Francis Osborne stressed a similar sentiment in his 1656 *Advice to a Son*, arguing that one should 'wear your clothes neat, exceeding rather than coming short of others of like fortune.'⁵¹ Increasing rates of literacy meant that the advice incorporated in these conduct books could also be appropriated by aspirational members of the middling sort. Conduct books encouraged individuals to 'appear what he was, but also what he aspired to be', and as such, by propagating fashionable styles through these publications, the middling sort were able to more effectively emulate and blend in with the gentry and the classes above.⁵² Both sources highlight the importance of apparel for

⁴⁷ Elias, *The Civilizing Process*, 61-63.

⁴⁸ Thomas, *In Pursuit of Civility*, 66.

⁴⁹ Finkelstein, *The Fashioned Self*, 155-157

⁵⁰ Baldissare Castiglione, *The Book of the Courtier trans. by Sir Thomas Hoby*, (ed.) Sir Walter Raleigh (London: Davis Nutt Publisher, 1900), accessed December 7, 2021, <http://www.luminarium.org/renascence-editions/courtier/courtier2.html>.

⁵¹ Francis Osborne, *Advice to a Son* (London 1656), 12.

⁵² Osborne, *Advice to a Son*, 55.

elite members of society to distinguish themselves as socially superior linkable to Elias's Civilizing Process, as well as Veblen's hypothesis on the importance of conspicuous consumption by further associating good manners and an influence on dress selection.⁵³

Morality similarly played a fundamental role in defining attitudes towards clothing in the early modern period.⁵⁴ Excesses in dress were considered both a personal and a public vice.⁵⁵ Sermons and prescriptive literature of the era relayed the dangers of dressing above one's station, despite acknowledging the impact of clothing on the delineation of social order.⁵⁶ Superficial and impractical decorations, such as ruffs, were indicative of one's status, but were often a source of ridicule by moralists, particularly Puritans.⁵⁷ Bishop John Jewel's 1571 *Homily Against Excesses of Apparel* was widely circulated and read aloud in churches throughout the country. Jewel reiterated the God-given place of each man within society and condemned those who dressed in apparel unbecoming for their social level.⁵⁸ A similar sentiment was expressed by Samuel Annesley in 1671 when he plead 'That yet there are some modes of Apparel... so inconsistent with the Rule of Decency, so apparently transgressing the bounds of Modesty, that no pretence of an honest intention, no uprightness of heart can atone, or excuse the evil of wearing them.'⁵⁹ In addition to sermons, contemporary publications, often authored by members of the gentry, also signalled concern for the excesses of apparel, such as Richard Allestree's *The Whole Duty of Man*, which states that the 'end of apparel is the distinguishing

⁵³ Roche, *The Culture of Clothing*, 54-55.

⁵⁴ Breward, *The Culture of Fashion*, 50.

⁵⁵ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 46.

⁵⁶ Catherine Richardson, 'Introduction' in, *Clothing Culture, 1350-1650*, ed. Catherine Richardson (Aldershot: Routledge, 2004), 1.

⁵⁷ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 32-33, 86.

⁵⁸ Bishop John Jewel, 'Homily Against Excess of Apparel', *Second Book of Homilies* (1571), accessed December 7, 2021, <http://www.anglicanlibrary.org/homilies/bk2hom06.htm>.

⁵⁹ Samuel Annesley, *A Continuation of morning-exercise questions and cases of conscience practicaly resolved by sundry ministers in October, 1682* (London 1683), 608.

and differencing of persons'.⁶⁰ Essentially, these publications were not only critiquing the extravagance of contemporary attire, but confirming that clothing distinguished various ranks, and those who dressed above their status were disrupting the divine Great Chain of Being.

In addition to conducting books and sermons, other forms of prescriptive literature articulated contemporary anxieties regarding excesses in apparel. Philip Stubbes' 1583 *An Anatomie of Abuses* can be regarded as a pivotal work in moralising literature that fuses secular and religious discourse, to target apparel specifically.⁶¹ Stubbes provided an exceptionally thorough evaluation of contemporary clothing, and comments how individuals of all social ranks 'go daily in silks, velvets, satins, damasks, taffetas, and such like, notwithstanding that they be both base by birth, mean by estate, and calling.'⁶² He further describes the clothing worn by members of society, decrying the ornate fabrics and colours used in the everyday clothing of the common sort, and lambasting their frivolous styles such as overly decorated hats.⁶³ Although Stubbes and many of his fellow writers could be characterised as overtly biased, even extremist due to his puritanical views, his writings are indicative of the mindset wherein apparel was identified as a potent social tool.⁶⁴ This moral argument against current fashionability may have been used to disguise their ulterior motive- to prevent people from emulating gentlemanly styles and enforce social stratification. In addition to unveiling the undeniable connection between apparel and the enforcement of social order, the frequency of these publications reflects the regularity of such offences, and an increasing concern amongst the elite regarding these overt displays.

⁶⁰ Richard Allestree, *The Whole Duty of Man* (1659), 238-239.

⁶¹ Roze Hentschell, 'Moralizing Apparel in Early Modern London: Popular Literature, Sermons, and Sartorial Display', *Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies* 39 (2009): 575.

⁶² Phillip Stubbes, *An Anatomie of Abuses* (1583), accessed December 7, 2021, <https://ezp.lib.cam.ac.uk/login?url=https://www-proquest-com.ezp.lib.cam.ac.uk/books/front-matter-stage-plays-enterluds-etc/docview/2138578574/se-2?accountid=9851>.

⁶³ Stubbes, *An Anatomie of Abuses* (1583).

⁶⁴ Vincent, "When I am in Good Habit", 118.

Beyond Morality: Sumptuary Legislation and the Enforcement of the Social Order

It is equally noteworthy that the government focused on the enforcement of the Great Chain of Being through the implementation of sumptuary legislation that enshrined into law the relationship between clothing and the social order. The Henrician Acts of Apparel, passed in 1533, along with a subsequent Act passed by Queen Elizabeth I in 1553, proved to be the most comprehensive and enduring.⁶⁵ Elizabeth seemed particularly preoccupied with the enforcement of sumptuary law. She issued nineteen additional proclamations on the subject of dress between 1562 and 1597, to deal with wide-ranging topics from the ‘the outrageous double ruffs which now of late are crept in’ to prescriptive legislation encouraging yeomen farmers and husbandmen to wear felt caps as part of their daily apparel.⁶⁶ Francis Baldwin and Wilfrid Hooper, the preeminent scholars on England sumptuary law, derived three basic principles from this legislation- to preserve the domestic economy and limit the importation of foreign goods, to condemn and prevent excessive luxury, and most importantly, to preserve class structures.⁶⁷ Sumptuary legislation ensured that one’s social position could easily be ascertained, and its success or failure demonstrated the inherent value being placed on clothing.⁶⁸ It also served to control the spending of the lower orders to avoid and prevent them from slipping into poverty or crime to support their extravagant taste. This was evidenced by Elizabeth’s dramatic 1574 proclamation in which she decried ‘the ruin of a multitude of serviceable young men and gentlemen and of many good families’ through their excesses in apparel.⁶⁹ Generally, sumptuary legislation targeted young men, and it was enforced particularly strenuously amongst

⁶⁵ Baldwin, *Sumptuary Legislation and Personal Regulation*, 267 and Harte, ‘State Control of Dress’, 135.

⁶⁶ Harte, ‘State Control of Dress’, 135, Proclamation 7 May 1562, 4 Eliz. I (495).

⁶⁷ Baldwin, *Sumptuary Legislation and Personal Regulation*, 2 and Hooper, ‘The Tudor Sumptuary Laws’, 436.

⁶⁸ Joanne Finkelstein, *The Fashioned Self* (Philadelphia: Polity Press, 1991), 137-139.

⁶⁹ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 18 and Proclamation 15 June 1574, 16 Eliz. I (601).

those attending university, many of whom grazed the social divide between the gentry and middling sort.⁷⁰ This exemplifies how elite anxieties regarding apparel were codified into law to restrict socially mobile young men and to reaffirm traditional ideas of the social order.

The very structure and wording of sumptuary legislation and subsequent proclamations validates the crown's primary motivation of maintaining and enforcing patterns of social order. The preamble to Henry VIII's 1533 Act of Apparel explicitly details how excesses in apparel led to the 'undoing of many in expert and light persons inclined to pride mother of all vices and 'the subversion of good and politic order in knowledge and distinction of people according to their estates, pre-eminences dignities and degrees'.⁷¹ This perfectly illustrates a dual motivation for implementing control over the apparel of the lower orders- it serves to preserve their morality, but more importantly to establish boundaries ensuring that individuals can be easily distinguished based on their appearance. Queen Elizabeth expresses a similar sentiment in her proclamations against Excesses of Apparel, stating that over time there had been 'the disorder and confusion of the degrees of all estates (wherein always diversity of apparel hath taken place)' as well as condemning 'the wasting and undoing of a great number of young gentlemen... seeking by show of apparel to be esteemed as gentlemen'.⁷² These statements provide vital support for early modern applications of Veblen by explicitly describing how young men leveraged conspicuous consumption to emulate their social superiors.⁷³ Though emulative consumption was regarded as an urban fear, it clearly served as a means of marking societal division.⁷⁴ The concerns expressed by religious moralists echo the Queen's messaging to demonstrate throughout the sixteenth century- there were shared anxieties regarding the

⁷⁰ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 131-132.

⁷¹ 24 Hen. VIII, 13 (1533).

⁷² Proclamation 12 February 1566, 8 Eliz. I (542) and Proclamation 15 June 1574, 16 Eliz. I (601).

⁷³ Finkelstein, *The Fashioned Self*, 140.

⁷⁴ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 34-35.

enhanced access to apparel that led both civic and moral-minded officials to take a firmer stand to preserve order within the nation.

Additionally, the details of the legislation itself are critical of the argument of its use to enforce social order within English society. In general, it was not the styles of clothing that differed between members of the middling sort and the elites, but rather the colour, fabric, and level of ornamentation that were regulated. For example, metallic fabric, velvet and silk embroidery were all restricted to those in the gentry and above as well as a number of restrictions on fur trimmings.⁷⁵ These guidelines were outlined in sumptuary legislation throughout social levels or conditions and grew increasingly detailed as new legislation was passed. Typically, a monarch and his or her family were granted the most significant liberties, followed closely by members of the court and the landed gentry, then freeholding yeomen farmers, and finally husbandmen and labourers.⁷⁶ Within these categories, there were more granular distinctions, often based upon titles, landholdings, and accumulated wealth. Amongst the gentry, the common gentleman had the fewest options in apparel, thus encouraging ‘unscrupulous’ individuals to pass themselves off as members of the gentry.⁷⁷ At times, there was little difference in the restrictions placed upon members of the lesser gentry and wealthy members of the middling sort, making it even more essential for the gentry to distinguish themselves from their social inferiors.⁷⁸ Evidently, though sumptuary legislation served a multitude of purposes, it was above all an invaluable weapon of the crown to dictate the degrees of society.

⁷⁵ Proclamation 15 June 1574, 16 Eliz. I (601).

⁷⁶ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 204-210.

⁷⁷ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 210.

⁷⁸ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 221.

By 1604, sumptuary legislation had been repealed, and subsequent attempts by James I and Charles I to reinstate it failed to pass through the House of Commons.⁷⁹ The early disappearance of sumptuary legislation in England, as compared to continental Europe, puzzles historians such as N.B Harte, who has confessed his inability to provide a sufficient explanation.⁸⁰ Alan Hunt has proposed a number of alternative explanations in his nuanced approach to the study of sumptuary legislation, but has reiterated the general uncertainty within the scholarship.⁸¹ He theorised that the absence of seventeenth-century legislation to control apparel might reflect the rapidly changing styles of the early modern period. After the passing of the Henrician sumptuary legislation in 1533, men's style transitioned from long gowns to the doublet and hose, and eventually to the suit by the end of the seventeenth century.⁸² Additionally, the commercial regulation made it impossible for legislation to keep up with increasingly diverse styles.⁸³ Similarly, while sumptuary legislation mandated what was desirable, it did little to prevent people from purchasing forbidden fabrics and was virtually impossible to be enforced, therefore implying what was desirable, but doing little to prevent its acquisition.⁸⁴ Despite placing guards at the entrance to London during Queen Elizabeth's reign, it became increasingly apparent that in order for sumptuary legislation to be effectively upheld, the people needed to report and self-regulate excesses within their community- this proved to be unpopular.⁸⁵ In her final proclamation on the subject of apparel, Elizabeth lamented how 'no reformation at all hath followed' her previous declarations, indicating that sumptuary legislation was clearly being

⁷⁹ Harte, 'State Control of Dress', 134 and Maria Hayward, "'Outlandish Superfluities': Luxury and Clothing in Scottish and English Sumptuary Law from the Fourteenth to the Seventeenth Century', *The Right to Dress: Sumptuary Laws in a Global Perspective, c.1200–1800*, eds. Giorgio Riello and Ulinka Rublack (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019), 97.

⁸⁰ Harte, 'State Control of Dress', 153-154.

⁸¹ Hunt, *Governance of the Consuming Passions*, 357-361.

⁸² Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 115.

⁸³ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 336.

⁸⁴ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 84, 108.

⁸⁵ Hooper, 'The Tudor Sumptuary Laws', 439-443.

ignored.⁸⁶ Ultimately, despite Elizabeth's 'Herculean' efforts to enforce these laws, their existence failed to stem the tide of change, nor to blur the boundaries between the gentry and the middling sort.⁸⁷

Fashioning the Middling Sort

The desire of the elite within English society to restrict apparel across all social levels was aided by the financial constraints of the middling sort. However, despite most attempts from the church, state, and community to regulate the clothing worn by this group, these efforts failed. In instances where the middling sort were unable to afford to dress in the apparel of their social superiors, they found inexpensive alternatives such as *mockado*, a fake velvet that is commonly found among upper-middling sort inventories. These substitutions generally left them with the necessary resources to invest in higher quality textiles and ornamentation, as opposed to basic russet or linen worn by husbandmen or more impoverished artisans.⁸⁸ The great care the middling sort afforded to their clothing also serves as an indication of the inherent value it held.⁸⁹ Therefore, it can be argued that despite the apparent differences in the overall quality of the apparel of the gentry and middling sort, clothing was essential for grooming people for the role they sought to inhabit as well as the role they were expected to inhabit.⁹⁰ Similarly, as traditional community values eroded and cities increased in size, urban anonymity made it increasingly possible for the middling sort to masquerade above their social position without recognition, and for members to invest in clothing specifically designed to attract the

⁸⁶ Proclamation 6 July 1597, 39 Eliz. I (786).

⁸⁷ Harte, 'State control of Dress', 148.

⁸⁸ Spufford and Mee, *Clothing of the Common Sort*, 132, 217.

⁸⁹ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 133.

⁹⁰ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 177.

community's attention.⁹¹ Again, this emphasises a profound early modern anxiety regarding the disguise and manipulation of appearance which directly challenged the Great Chain of Being.⁹² It is equally evident that by establishing parameters and guidance, the conduct books, sermons, and sumptuary legislation were setting precedents for what could be worn. In fact, this determined what was in style and accordingly increased the demand for such prohibitive fashions.⁹³ Therefore, rather than suppressing attire, the conduct books, sermons, and sumptuary legislation encouraged styles to spread further and promoted the desire to own such prohibited goods.⁹⁴ In other instances, like the case of caps, this notoriety would cause items to fall out of fashion quickly, as they became the prescriptive headwear or garments for yeomen, husbandmen, and below.⁹⁵ Therefore, the very actions taken to create distinct social boundaries ultimately contributed to the crossover between the gentry and the literate, as aspirational members of the middling sort made fashion the 'joint expression of status aspiration and status assertion'.⁹⁶

The inability of the gentry to successfully define their 'class' identity through clothing correlates to the distinction of societal expectations versus fundamental reality. This principle has its foundation in the work of James C. Scott, who describes a 'hidden transcript' that contrasts acceptable public belief, and argues that in truth there is a distinct difference between expected behaviour and what is actually practised.⁹⁷ Although the gentry assumed an elevated level of social ranking, it is increasingly evident that such roles were flexible within society. As

⁹¹ Pennell, 'Consumption and Consumerism', 550 and Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, 164.

⁹² Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 10.

⁹³ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 127.

⁹⁴ Breward, *The Culture of Fashion*, 55.

⁹⁵ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 25.

⁹⁶ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 127.

⁹⁷ James C. Scott, *Domination and the Arts of Resistance, Hidden Transcripts*, (London: Yale University Press, 1990, 1-15.

noted above, the transformation within both urban and rural communities led to a reevaluation of how the middling sort regarded themselves and articulated their status. Specifically, their acquisition of clothing signified the increasing wealth and social aspirations of the middling sort, contradicting traditional orders dictating that people must stay within their respective estates.⁹⁸ Nevertheless, even those beneath the middling sort were able to engage in the culture of fashion from the middle of the sixteenth century onwards. A rapidly expanding market in second-hand and stolen clothing as well as inexpensive, ready-made accessories and apparel confirm that clothing was an important tool of social elevation and emulation.⁹⁹ Chapmen also offered goods at a variety of prices so that everyone could find fashionable clothing at an appropriate level.¹⁰⁰ However, this reality was not expressed in the sumptuary legislation, conduct books, and prescriptive literature that placed a significant emphasis on the separation of society into different groups and the necessity of a separation between the lower gentry and aspirational middling sort. While these sources promoted an idealised version of society, or a public transcript, they ignored the hidden reality wherein social mobility was a contemporary phenomenon, and these documents were appropriated by those seeking to emulate elite customs and fashion and to break down the traditional social order. Therefore, it is apparent that even if the gentry sought to use fashion to create a unique identity for themselves, their failure to consider the larger machinations of early modern society largely contributed to the undoing of their own sartorial uniformity. Instead, it allowed the middling sort to fashion a cultural identity of their own.

Conclusion

⁹⁸ Vincent, ‘When I am in Good Habit’, 20.

⁹⁹ Beverly Lemire, ‘The Theft of Clothes and Popular Consumerism in Early Modern England’, *Journal of Social History* 24 (1990): 255, 269 and Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, 40-41.

¹⁰⁰ Thirsk, *Economic Policy and Projects*, 116.

Although it was initially intended to be another mechanism for enforcing the social order, apparel ultimately delivered the opposite effect as it created a sense of ambiguity between social classes. Beginning in the sixteenth century, fashion became 'a means for publicising social status', with increased mobility and purchasing power fostering such dramatic change.¹⁰¹ Despite the fact that the incomes of the middling sort varied dramatically, much of their finances were devoted to fashionable textiles and apparel, portraying their growing influence in society and infringement on the positions of the landed gentry.¹⁰² While there has been limited historiographical research dedicated to assessing the impact of clothing on social relations in early modern England, this survey has demonstrated that by expanding the analysis to increasingly diverse historiography, there is compelling evidence to support the fundamental theory of emulation proposed by Veblen at the turn of the twentieth century. This challenges criticism of emulation theory which postulates that the middling sort created a distinctive identity through fashion separate from the gentry, and perhaps even influenced courtly attire.¹⁰³

As noted at the beginning of this article, despite a general increase in scholarship on the subject of dress, a survey of relevant literature revealed that the study of clothing within the broader field of social history was lacking. This provided a historiographical foundation and methodological framework for the arguments presented while acknowledging the gaps in the literature. Secondly, contemporary ideals regarding the social order, deference, and the 'great chain of being' were summarised, followed by a brief investigation of how fashion and cultural trends could circulate throughout early modern England. These studies support the argument that the study of dress and textiles fits into contemporary understanding of social order and that

¹⁰¹ Finkelstein, *The Fashioned Self*, 155-157, 165.

¹⁰² Weatherill, *Consumer Behavior*, 98-103.

¹⁰³ Wrightson, *Earthly Necessities*, 299-300.

members of the middling sort had access to clothing which effectively allowed them to emulate the gentry, even outside of urban centres. Contemporary sermons and conduct books were studied in great detail. This exposed the moral impetus to restrict dress to preserve social order and prevent excessive consumption while simultaneously advancing the view that apparel was a crucial tool in defining their own identity as gentlemen. Likewise, an exploration into the role of sumptuary legislation and contemporary ‘acts of apparel’ revealed that restricting the dress of the middling sort was not solely the preoccupation of the gentry and religious moralists but was also the subject of national governance, proving that dress was perceived as a critical tool of social identification. However, the failure of these sumptuary laws was equally telling, indicating that despite the best efforts of elite society, there was little they could do to control dress and its use by the middling sort. Finally, the ‘hidden transcript’ of the middling sort was uncovered, demonstrating that despite the best efforts of elite society, individuals were able to ingeniously replicate the fashions of their social betters, despite financial constraints. This ultimately demonstrates that rather than restricting dress, sumptuary legislation, conduct books, and sermons on apparel effectively provided insight into what was fashionable, encouraging emulation by the middling sort, rather than curtailing it. By connecting these arguments, it becomes apparent that clothing was perceived as a potent tool across contemporary society in constructing social and cultural identities. By exploring the variety of ways in which these ideas could be articulated across early modern English society, one can observe how despite the best efforts of the gentry, the middling sort were able to wield clothing as a weapon for social advancement.

Contemporary evidence suggests that while the middling sort were frequently the arbiters of fashion, they often considered this role in response to the economic, legal, and moral limitations placed upon them by the gentry. Perhaps, while seeking to emulate the culture of the elite, the

middling sort ultimately devised a culture of their own.¹⁰⁴ Alternatively, as Danae Tankard argues, emulative consumption was not vertical, but instead based around the desire of both the rural gentry and middling sort to mimic fashionable apparel from the urban centre of London.¹⁰⁵ Regardless, to early modern observers, fashion enabled social recognition, and thus, was an integral tool in the construction of social groups and the maintenance of order.¹⁰⁶ In subverting the existing boundaries of fashion and appearance, the middling sort established a fundamental role in restructuring English society that continues to impact the evolving field of social history today.

¹⁰⁴ Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, 220-221.

¹⁰⁵ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 185

¹⁰⁶ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 92.

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The development of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania, 1555-1588¹

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Abstract

This paper maps the history of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania between 1558 and 1588 by outlining the origins and tenets of Christians rejecting the doctrine of the Trinity as well as analysing the denomination's spread and radicalisation in the East Central European region. It argues that Antitrinitarians in the second half of the sixteenth century achieved a prominent status at the Transylvanian court due to their personal good relations with the rulers and the relative religious tolerance of the principality. Thus, this paper sheds light on the exceptional influence of a Protestant community in the age of fierce religious persecutions across Europe.

Images 1 and 2 (next page): Unitarian church (Homoródszentpéter/Petreni in modern-day Romania)²

¹ I would like to thank Dr. Lionel Laborie (Institute for History, Leiden University) for his valuable advice in the spring of 2020 in the course of writing the paper which served as the basis of this article.

² Wikimedia Commons, 2015, accessed May 15, 2020.

Introduction

In 1517, Martin Luther's theses criticised the pursuits and activities of the papacy and challenged several Roman Catholic principles. The escalating theological debates induced the appearance of numerous reform movements that formed parts of a comprehensive European phenomenon. Theological disagreements within the Protestant Reformation led to the birth of several different creeds and denominations. One radical branch, Antitrinitarianism, rejected the Holy Trinity and Christ's divinity, and East Central Europe proved to be the only place in the continent where it could develop successfully. Antitrinitarianism was introduced in Transylvania by Italian individuals in the 1550s and 1560s. It started to spread at the court and among the wider population, under the reign of its religiously tolerant prince, John Sigismund (1559-1571). By the late 1570s, theological disputes between Giorgio Biandrata (1515-1588) and Ferenc Dávid (1520-1579), the leaders of Transylvanian Antitrinitarians, resulted in an unprecedented religious conflict in the community. Nonetheless, the Antitrinitarian denomination has survived and is present in Transylvania even today.

This paper addresses the question: What role did the Antitrinitarian movement play in the religious plurality and in the process of confessionalisation in Transylvania between 1555 and 1588? The aim of this paper is to analyse how Antitrinitarianism was accepted in Transylvania, and how Antitrinitarians contributed to the religious and intellectual life of the principality in the sixteenth century.

Antitrinitarianism has attracted the curiosity of various scholars in the past centuries due to the role of Transylvania as a ‘religious melting pot’. First, Antitrinitarian history interested Unitarian³ intellectuals who approached the topic from a specifically religious perspective, for instance Earl Morse Wilbur.⁴ In the 1960s, an increased attention was paid to Antitrinitarianism in a transnational context, due to the publication of a series on the Italian Reformation, the *Biblioteca del Corpus Reformatorum Italicorum*. One of its volumes, authored by Delio Cantimori, dealt with the activities of sixteenth-century Italian ‘heretics’ in the Swiss cantons, the Holy Roman Empire, and Eastern Europe.⁵ His research was improved by Domenico Caccamo’s analysis of the ‘heretical’ thinking of Italians specifically in Transylvania, Poland-Lithuania,⁶ and Moravia. Caccamo has argued that the progress of these radical trends was dependent on the gradually changing political environment of the area.⁷ These scholars found the origin of Antitrinitarianism in the theology of Michael Servetus (1511-1553), but this concept was challenged by Andrew M. Hill. He has stated that its chief source was Calvinism since Antitrinitarian communities both in Poland-Lithuania and Transylvania were established after their breaks with the local Calvinist congregations.⁸ Howard Hotson has regarded Antitrinitarian thinkers as the philosophical forerunners of the Enlightenment by attributing the most progressive ideas of the context of the Reformation and the Renaissance, reason, freedom, tolerance, to them.⁹ Gábor Almási has highlighted that Antitrinitarians emphasised the Old

³ The Unitarian Church of Transylvania is the institutionalised form of Antitrinitarianism. Since this name became widely used from the seventeenth century, I refer to the community by using the term ‘Antitrinitarian’ in this paper.

⁴ Earl Morse Wilbur, *A history of Unitarianism*, 1 (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1945).

⁵ Delio Cantimori, *Eretici italiani del Cinquecento. Ricerche storiche* (Florence: Sansoni, 1967), 320–330.

⁶ The Kingdom of Poland and the Grand Duchy of Lithuania was a dual state (1569-1575), officially unified in 1569 by Sigismund II Augustus (1548-1572). Nonetheless, Sigismund I the Old (1506-1548) had already ruled both states. Therefore, I use the term ‘Poland-Lithuania’ in this paper.

⁷ Domenico Caccamo, *Eretici italiani in Moravia, Polonia, Transilvania* (Florence: Sansoni, 1970), 22–31, 109–151.

⁸ Andrew M. Hill, “Why Unitarian-Universalists owe more to John Calvin than they do to Michael Servetus,” *Keresztény Magvető* 109 (2003): 143–152.

⁹ Howard Hotson, “Arianism and Millenarianism: The Link Between the Two Heresies from Servetus to Socinus,” in *Continental Millenarians: Protestants, Catholics, Heretics*, ed. by John Christian Laursen and Richard H. Popkin (Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2001), 9–35.

Testament and the importance of Hebrew and Syrian studies in theological education.¹⁰

Similarly, Nicholas Terpstra has asserted that from the 1580s, Antitrinitarian intellectuals had followed the humanistic ideal of reading the Bible in original languages in order to get more trustworthy interpretations.¹¹

The concept most central to this paper is religious radicalism. The term ‘radical’, both in political and religious senses, has been defined in various ways, such as a fundamental political or social reform, a distinctive behaviour and a renewing activity. Ariel Hessayon and David Finnegan have argued that the borders between ‘radical’ and ‘mainstream’ phenomena are often not solid, and therefore, each case study should be contextualised.¹² I agree with the interpretation of ‘radicalism’ as a relative and anachronistic label which started to be used in modern times. Consequently, I use the term religious radicalism in the framework of the theological disagreements and doctrinal differences that distinguished Antitrinitarians from Catholics and Calvinists.

The approach of this research is political. It aims to carry out a qualitative investigation of primary sources to map the turning points of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania. It focuses on information with historical rather than theological value, and on references to political events to delineate the circumstances of theological radicalisation and the relations of Antitrinitarian leaders with a Protestant as well as a Catholic ruler. Antitrinitarians’ writings will be used to explicate why they were seen as ‘heresy’, while resolutions of the Transylvanian Diet will be

¹⁰ Gábor Almási, “Andreas Dudith (1533-1589): Conflicts and strategies of a religious individualist in confessionalising Europe,” in *Between Scylla and Charybdis: Learned Letter Writers Navigating the Reefs of Religious and Political Controversy in Early Modern Europe*, ed. by Jeanine de Landtsheer and Henk Nellen (Leiden: Brill, 2011), 161–184.

¹¹ Nicholas Terpstra, *Religious Refugees in the Early Modern World* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 155–156.

¹² Ariel Hessayon and David Finnegan, eds., *Varieties of Seventeenth- and Eighteenth-Century English Radicalism in Context* (Farnham: Ashgate, 2011), 10–15.

examined to trace down the stages of the political acceptance of Antitrinitarians.¹³ The accounts of oral theological polemics and written disputations will be examined to outline the statements and refutations between Antitrinitarian and Calvinist thinkers. The main obstacle when analysing these are their length so this paper will focus on parts that had the most significant political implications.

Thus, this paper offers a contribution to the scholarship on a radical branch of the Protestant Reformation, which flourished in Transylvania in the era of common religious persecutions throughout Europe. The paper aims to demonstrate that Antitrinitarianism succeeded and survived in Transylvania due to the social and religious diversity of the territory, and to the continental political situation that made toleration necessary for stability to be preserved. The first part of the paper is dedicated to the introduction of Antitrinitarianism's appearance in Europe in the 1550s, the second covers its Transylvanian history until 1571, and the third section concentrates on the process of radicalisation up to the late 1580s.

¹³ Transylvania was a semi-independent *elective monarchy* where the *estates* (Hungarian nobles, Saxon patricians, Szekler soldiers) had a considerable say in governmental issues at diet assemblies. See Teréz Oborni, "State and governance in the Principality of Transylvania," *Hungarian Studies* 27 (2013), 313–324.

The origins, doctrines, and early spread of Antitrinitarianism in the 1550s

Image 3: Christian Fritsch, Michael Servetus (c.1740)

¹⁴ Antitrinitarianism was born out of the theories of several individuals in the course of the sixteenth century. The first Antitrinitarians were Spanish and Italian Protestant intellectuals who revived the ancient principles of Arianism – the denial of Christ’s divinity and the dogma of the Holy Trinity. In the first part of this paper, it is worth looking at why Antitrinitarianism can be defined as a ‘radical’ religious belief, and how it was dealt with by the Catholic Church and by other Protestants in the 1550s.

The first important figure of Antitrinitarianism was Michael Servetus. The Spanish humanist was a physician and a theologian, and his writings testify to the great extent to which his two professions were intertwined. During his anatomical training in Paris in the 1530s, Servetus elaborated a theory according to which the Holy Spirit deifies human beings through their breathing.¹⁵ His arguments largely contributed to the study of pulmonary circulation, the exchange of deoxygenated and oxygenated blood between the heart and the lungs.¹⁶ In 1531, Servetus summarised his arguments for the ‘errors’ of the Trinity in *De Trinitatis erroribus* which became the Christological basis of a new belief system:

¹⁴ Wikimedia Commons, 2017, accessed May 15, 2020.

¹⁵ Michael Servetus, *Christianismi Restitutio* (Vienne, 1553), 171 – Digital Imaging Unit, Edinburgh University Library, accessed May 11, 2020, <https://images.is.ed.ac.uk/luna/servlet/view/search;JSESSIONID=3ec3dc7c-41a1-4481-9dea-04e82a75fede?q=Df.8.90&os=0&pgs=250&res=0>.

¹⁶ Elizabeth Martin and Robert Hine, *A dictionary of biology*, 6th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008), 540.

Christ, being one with Yahweh his Father, equal in power, came down from heaven and assumed flesh as a man. In short, all the Scriptures speak of Christ as a man.¹⁷

Servetus described his medical observations in a 1553 theological book titled *Christianismi Restitutio*, and denied the concepts of the Trinity, the original sin, and the predestination.¹⁸ Thus, Servetus challenged basic Catholic teachings along with the tenets of the French reformer John Calvin (1509-1564) which were noted in ‘Chapter XIII. One Divine Essence, Containing Three Persons; Taught In The Scriptures From The Beginning’ in the first book of Calvin’s *Institutes of the Christian Religion* (1536).¹⁹ Eventually, Servetus was burnt at the stake in the Calvinist Republic of Geneva for his ‘heretical’ views in October 1553.

Servetus’s thoughts spread quickly in the religiously relatively tolerant Republic of Venice, particularly in the academic circles of the University of Padua, which had not been confined by a severe religious supervision.²⁰ Matteo Gribaldi Moffa (1505-1564) was a Piedmontese law professor at Padua and a leading figure of local Protestants and religious refugees from German territories. Gribaldi had been in contact with the Italian community in Geneva, supported the ideas of Servetus, and was even present at his trial in 1553. Gribaldi moved to Geneva in 1555, but soon found himself in the opposition of Calvin for rejecting the theory of predestination and sympathising with Servetian thoughts. As expressed in his brochure *De vera Dei et filius eius cognitione*. Gribaldi believed that the divine Trinity was an invention of men in the first centuries of Christianity that had no foundation in the Scriptures.²¹ Gribaldi left for Tübingen

¹⁷ Michael Servetus, *De Trinitatis erroribus* (Hagenau, 1531) quoted in English in Earl Morse Wilbur, ed., *The two treatises of Servetus on the Trinity* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1932), 3.

¹⁸ Published in Vienne, France.

¹⁹ John Allen, ed., *Institutes of the Christian Religion by John Calvin* (Philadelphia: Presbyterian Board of Publication, 1813), 140–186.

²⁰ On the history of the University of Padua, see Lucia Rossetti, *The University of Padua. An Outline of Its History* (Trieste: Edizioni Lint, 1983); and Piero Del Negro, *L’Università di Padova: otto secoli di storia* (Padova: Signum, 2001).

²¹ Delio Cantimori and Elizabeth Feist, eds., *Per la storia degli eretici italiani del secolo XVI in Europa. Studi e documenti*, 11 (Rome: Reale Accademia d’Italia, 1937), 81.

where he published a pamphlet titled *Apologia pro Michaele Serveto* in which he defended the executed reformer.²² Gribaldi became persecuted by the university council, so he fled to Farges in the Kingdom of France. In 1559, the professor started to teach at the University of Grenoble, but due to an investigation ordered against him, he returned to Farges, where he died in 1564.²³

Gribaldi's Antitrinitarian ideas influenced many other intellectuals, notably Polish theologian Petrus Gonesius (1525-1573) who studied philosophy and then taught logic at Padua. Antitrinitarian works were taken into Poland-Lithuania by Gonesius in 1555. He objected to the dogma of the Trinity at the Synod of the Polish Reformed Church in January 1556.²⁴ Gonesius was excommunicated but managed to gain some supporters. In 1565, the theological disagreements within the Polish Reformed Church led to a split between the Calvinists and the Antitrinitarian faction. In 1565, the latter group reorganised themselves with the leadership of Gonesius as the Polish Brethren or *Ecclesia minor*, that is to say the Minor Reformed Church of Poland.²⁵

Gribaldi's other colleague, with whom he collaborated to develop his Antitrinitarian ideas in Padua, was Lelio Sozzini (1525-1562), a humanist reformer from Siena.²⁶ He started his education as a lawyer in Bologna and Padua but soon moved to Vicenza in the Republic of Venice. Here he became involved in the gatherings of a Protestant group, the *Collegia Vicentina*

²² Piet Visser, ed., *Bibliographia Sociniana: A Bibliographical Reference Tool for the Study of Dutch Socinianism and Antitrinitarianism* (Amsterdam: Hilversum, 2004), 13.

²³ Frederic C. Church, *I riformatori italiani*, 2 (Milan: Il Saggiatore, 1967), 179–182.

²⁴ The Polish Reformed Church was founded in 1551 and followed the Calvinist trend in theological and organisational aspects.

²⁵ Ralf Bröer, “Blutkreislauf und Dreieinigkeit Medizinischer Antitrinitarismus von Michael Servet (1511–1553) bis Giorgio Biandrata (1515–1588),” *Berichte zur Wissenschaftsgeschichte* 29: (2006), 21–37.

²⁶ Earl Morse Wilbur, *A history of Unitarianism*, 1 (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1945), 81.

or Fratres vicentini who professed Anabaptist²⁷ and Antitrinitarian doctrines. Lelio frequently traveled abroad to preach his thoughts, and conducted vivid correspondence with John Calvin, raising his doubts concerning the Trinity, the predestination, and the resurrection of the body.²⁸ Suspected of following Servetian principles, Lelio was persecuted by the Roman Inquisition. After 1555, he could not return to Italy and died in Zürich in 1562.

Lelio's nephew, Fausto Sozzini (1539-1604) continued his uncle's exploration of biblical texts, European travels, and participation in theological debates. In 1579, he settled down in Poland-Lithuania and became the leader of the Polish Brethren. He believed that Christ could be addressed in prayers only indirectly as a mediator between people and the Father. In addition, he strived for simplifying Christian dogmas exclusively on the basis of the Bible. In 1578, Fausto completed his chief work, the *De Jesu Christo Servatore*, in which he argued that Christ's death had not made a full satisfaction for sins since only the Father could decide which sins would be forgiven – otherwise the 'delinquent would not have a true repentance but a fear of punishment'.²⁹ Fausto Sozzini's theological statements were highly influential in the later development of Antitrinitarianism in Poland-Lithuania. The term Socinianism stands for the system of tenets evolved in the Polish Brethren along the ideas of Lelio and Fausto Sozzini, and is derived from the Latinising version of their surname, Socinus.

²⁷ Anabaptists, members of another branch of the Radical Reformation, proclaimed that baptism should be preceded by a confession of faith, and therefore, rejected the baptism of infants.

²⁸ Luisa Simonutti, "Locke's Biblical Hermeneutics on Bodily Resurrection," in Luisa Simonutti, ed., *Locke and Biblical Hermeneutics. Conscience and Scripture* (New York: Springer International Publishing, 2019), 55–74.

²⁹ '... delinquentis non veram poenitentiam, sed poenae formidinem...' in Fausto Sozzini, *De Jesu Christo Servatore* (Krakow: Alexi Rodeci, 1594), 234, accessed May 10, 2020, <https://books.google.hu/books?id=vy9bAAAAcAAJ&printsec=frontcover&dq=De+Iesu+Christo+Servatore&hl=hu&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwjQ2sn40sDpAhWOpokHWZwAJgQ6AEIKDAA#v=onepage&q=De%20Iesu%20Christo%20Servatore&f=false>.

All in all, the diversity of Antitrinitarian theology originated in the international network of persecuted radicals and their religious activities. Most of them were educated physicians or lawyers who produced radical religious ideas and innovative scientific theories as well.³⁰

Transylvanian Antitrinitarianism, 1559-1571

Transylvania became the most flourishing centre of Antitrinitarianism in the 1560s. It is essential to discuss the political and religious circumstances that attracted Antitrinitarians to Transylvania, and the role that Antitrinitarians played at John Sigismund's court.

The name *Transylvania* refers to a historical and geographical area in the East Central European region that was a relatively short-lived semi-independent political territory in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. Until 1526, it had been part of the Kingdom of Hungary, which was divided after the victorious campaign of Suleiman I, sultan of the Ottoman Empire (1520-1566). A lengthy power struggle for total influence over the former royal territories started between the House of Habsburg and the Szapolyai family. The eastern areas were ruled by John I Szapolyai until 1540, by his widow Isabella Jagiellon until 1559, and then by their son John Sigismund (1540-1571). John Sigismund's legitimacy, as it remained the case with later rulers too, was dependent on Ottoman support against the Habsburg rivals who continued contesting the title of Transylvanian rulers in order to unite Hungary under their crown.³¹ In addition to the political challenge of being located between the Habsburg and Ottoman interests of expansion, John Sigismund inherited a land inhabited by Calvinist Hungarians, Lutheran Saxons, Roman Catholic Szeklers, and Eastern Orthodox Christian Romanians.

³⁰ On medicine and the Reformation in Italy, see Alessandra Celati, "*Contra medicos*: Physicians Facing the Inquisition in Sixteenth-Century Venice," in *Medicine and the Inquisition in the Early Modern World*, ed. by Maria Pia Donato (Leiden: Brill, 2019), 72–91.

³¹ László Makkai and András Mócsy, eds., *Erdély története, 1: A kezdetektől 1606-ig* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1986), 409–446.

Image 4: Giorgio Biandrata

³² The protagonist of the Transylvanian expansion was Giorgio Biandrata (1515-1588), a physician from Saluzzo (Piedmont) and alumnus of the University of Montpellier – which was a hotspot of the radical heterodoxy at that time.³³ Biandrata specialised in obstetrics and gynaecology, and issued a pioneering textbook in this field in 1539, in which he summarised Aristotelian gynaecological theories on fertilisation, weight, birth, and childbed.³⁴

Biandrata dedicated this book to Bona Sforza (1494-1557), the wife of Sigismund I the Old of Poland-Lithuania (1467-1548), and a member of the Milanese princely Sforza family, for whom he worked as a personal physician from 1540 until 1544; and to her daughter, the wife of John I Szapolyai of Hungary (1487-1540), Isabella Jagiellon (1519-1559), whom he served as a gynaecologist during the following eight years. In 1551, Biandrata returned to Italy and practiced medicine in Mestre but clashed with the Inquisition for his Antitrinitarian proclamations. Therefore, he fled to Geneva where the ‘Italian exile’ was gradually increasing in the course of the 1550s.³⁵ In 1558, a few theologians of this community frequently expressed their disagreements with Calvin, namely Giovanni Valentino Gentile (c.1520-1566), Gian Paolo Alciati (1515-1573), and Biandrata. They argued for the ‘detachment’ of the persons of the Trinity and the subordination of Christ and the Holy Spirit to the Father. Calvin responded

³² Wikimedia Commons, 2012, accessed May 15, 2020.

³³ Antonio Rotondò, “Giorgio Biandrata,” in *Dizionario Biografico degli Italiani*, 10 (1968), accessed May 20, 2020, http://www.treccani.it/enciclopedia/giovanni-giorgio-biandrata_%28Dizionario-Biografico%29/

³⁴ Giorgio Biandrata, *Gynaeceorum ex Aristotele et Bonaciolo a Georgio Blandrata medico Subalpino noviter excerpta de fecundatione, gravitate, partu et puerperio* (Argentinae, 1539).

³⁵ Elek Jakab, “Néhány adat Blandrata György élete és jelleme ismeréséhez,” *Keresztény Magvető* 12: (1877), 1–32, 3-4.

to these theological issues in a letter titled *Responsum ad quaestiones Georgii Blandratae*.³⁶

After being forced to sign a declaration of faith in the Holy Trinity, the ‘rebels’ escaped to Pińczów, Poland-Lithuania, and joined the Polish Reformed Church. Calvin fervently warned his Polish ‘colleagues’ about the danger inherent in the presence of the Antitrinitarians:

Their comments decreased Christ to only a mediator, and thus, interfered with the Trinity... There are filthy loafers with you, Giorgio Biandrata, Valentino Gentile, Gian Paolo Alciati, and others, whose frantic lust leads to innovation and headlong turbulence...³⁷

As Calvin constantly urged the Polish Reformed Church to excommunicate the ‘heretics’, their situation was deteriorating. Biandrata soon found an opportunity to move to Transylvania, while his fellows were expelled from Poland-Lithuania when the 1564 Edict of Parczów forced all foreign Protestants to leave.

In the early modern period, confessionalisation consisted of the evolution of religious beliefs and trends into set denominations along with the consolidation of their doctrines. In Transylvania, the institutionalisation of the different Protestant communities was a relatively slow process. This phenomenon was closely related to a so-called ‘universal Protestantism’ which had characterised the religious atmosphere of Transylvania until the 1560s.³⁸ This condition was the reason for the failure of Francesco Stancaro (1501-1574) when preaching his Antitrinitarian views in Transylvania in the 1550s. Stancaro had been a physician and professor of theology and Hebrew at Padua until he left Italy after a clash with the Inquisition. He

³⁶ Jean-François Gilmont and Peter Rodolphe, eds., *Bibliotheca Calviniana: les oeuvres de Jean Calvin publiées au XVIe siècle III, Écrits théologiques, littéraires et juridiques: 1565-1600*, 3 (Genève: Librairie Droz, 2000), 121-125.

³⁷ ‘Sunt enim apud vos impuri nebulones Georgius Blandrata, Valentinus Gentilis, Ioannes Paulus Alciatus, et similes, quos furiosa libido novandi et turbandi praecipites agit.’ in Edouard Cunitz et al., eds., *Ioannis Calvinii opera quae supersunt omnia*, 9 (Brunsvigae: Schwetschke, 1870), col. 646.

³⁸ Mihály Balázs, “Megjegyzések János Zsigmond valláspolitikához,” in Béla Varjas, ed., *Irodalom és ideológia a 16-17. században* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1987), 67–93, 76-77.

followed Servetian beliefs – denied Christ’s divinity and insisted on using the Bible as the exclusive theological source. In 1554, Stancaro was employed as the physician of Péter Petrovics (c.1486-1557), a Hungarian nobleman and supporter of the Reformation in Transylvania, so he had a chance to preach his views there. In 1555, a synod was held in Szék in order to discuss Antitrinitarian and Lutheran disagreements where Stancaro’s ideas were not accepted.³⁹

In 1563, John Sigismund invited Giorgio Biandrata, known as a loyal member of his mother’s entourage, to become his personal physician and counsellor at the court in Alba Iulia (in Hungarian: Gyulafehérvár), the capital of Transylvania. Thus, the heterogeneous palette of the Transylvanian society received a new colour with Biandrata’s arrival since he got engaged in religious polemics beside his medical commitments.⁴⁰ His main colleague in building the Antitrinitarian community was Ferenc Dávid (1520-1579), a Hungarian superintendent of the Calvinist Reformed Church in Transylvania. Dávid was raised Catholic, then became Lutheran, later Calvinist, and finally Antitrinitarian – his eagerness for theological research drew him from one denomination to another. In 1555, he had rejected Stancaro’s ideas against the Trinity in his writing titled *Dialysis Scripti Stancari Contra Primum Articulum Synodi Szekiensis...* He became John Sigismund’s court pastor still as a Calvinist but his theological versatility and interest in the works of Servetus and the Dutch humanist philosopher Erasmus of Rotterdam (1466-1536) provided fertile soil for Biandrata’s preachings. In 1567, Dávid dedicated his first Antitrinitarian work, the *Refutatio scripti Petri Melii* to ‘Joannes secundus D[ei] g[ratia] elect[us] rex Hungariae Dalmatiae Croatiae’ – this way, he referred to John Sigismund as the king of all the historical (former) territories of Hungary. In this piece, Dávid stated that the ruler

³⁹ Francesco Ruffini, *Studi sui riformatori italiani* (Turin: Edizioni Ramella, 1955), 165-406.

⁴⁰ Vincenzo Malacarne, *Commentario Delle Opere E Delle Vicende Di Giorgio Biandrata Nobile Saluzzese Archiatro In Transilvania E In Polonia* (Padova: Tipografia Bettoni, 1814), 46-50.

had the task to organise synods where the religious debates could be concluded. Moreover, he declared that the spread of Antitrinitarian tenets should be in parallel with the protection of their opponents' beliefs which testifies to his inclination to religious tolerance.⁴¹ An anthology of Antitrinitarian writings, collected and edited by Biandrata and Dávid was published in Alba Iulia in 1568, under the title *De falsa et vera unius Dei patris, filii et spritus sancti cognitione*. Importantly, this volume consisted of Lelio Sozzini's interpretation of the First Epistle of John, titled *Brevis explicatio in primum Iohannis caput*, along with their own shared theological points.⁴²

John Sigismund was personally very interested in theology – he was highly educated, willing to read and hear about religious issues, and spoke several languages thanks to the multilingual court of his Polish-Italian mother, Isabella Jagiellon. Despite being loyal to the Roman Catholic Church in the first years of his reign, John converted to Lutheranism in 1562, became Calvinist soon after, and eventually turned towards Antitrinitarianism in the late 1560s – thanks to the explicit influence of his physician and confidante, Giorgio Biandrata, and his court pastor, Ferenc Dávid.⁴³ John Sigismund was eager to participate in public events where representatives of the different denominations discussed theological issues. His open-minded attitude can be considered another important cause of the 'Antitrinitarian success' – he gained full power from his mother and her counsellors only in 1559 so Stancaró's early attempts in 1555 had been hindered by a solid Catholic leadership. The two Antitrinitarian theologians had a gradually increasing influence over John Sigismund and the nobility, which induced the indignation of

⁴¹ Ferenc Dávid, *Refutatio scripti Petri Melii* (Gyulafehérvár: TRRH, 1567), preface – Library and Information Centre of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences / MTA, accessed May 14, 2020, http://real-r.mtak.hu/964/7/A_166_VI.pdf

⁴² Antal Pirnát, ed., *De falsa et vera unius Dei patris, filii et spritus sancti cognitione* (Utrecht: Bibliotheca Unitariorum, 1988).

⁴³ István Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities in East-Central Europe: Ethnic Diversity, Denominational Plurality, and Corporative Politics in the Principality of Transylvania (1526–1691)* (Leiden: Brill, 2009), 99-101.

other churches, particularly the that of the Calvinists. A long series of disputations started between Ferenc Dávid and Péter Méliusz Juhász (1532-1572), bishop of the Calvinist Reformed Church in Transylvania from 1561. Méliusz was engaged in a number of written and oral debates with Dávid on their conflicts about God's unity and the question of the Trinity. The most important encounter of differing Protestant views was the disputation organised in October 1569 in Várad where Méliusz identified Biandrata and Dávid with the sons of the Satan and argued that:

Seventh objection to the sons of Beelzebub

The Pater Noster only mentions the Father, therefore only the Father is to be adored, and the Son is not.

ANSWER: This is a false 'Consequentia'... because I can prove that everything that belongs to the Father, belongs to the Son as well, the Father has never been either a Father or a God without his Son...⁴⁴

At this event, John Sigismund expressed his sympathy with Antitrinitarians as well as his dedication to ensure religious tolerance:

We wish that in our country... freedom shall reign. We know furthermore that faith is a gift from God and that conscience cannot be constrained.⁴⁵

This effort aimed at synthesising the various theological controversies of the country. However, these events did not succeed in bringing together the different views, and the Calvinist and Antitrinitarian tenets became increasingly distinct.⁴⁶ In 1567, John Sigismund established a press house in Alba Iulia for the Antitrinitarians where several works of their leading theologians were published – remarkably, Dávid's *Brief Explanation of how the Antichrist has*

⁴⁴ 'Hetedik ellen vetesek a Belzebub fiaynak. A Pater nosterben csak attiat nevez, Hat csak az attia imadando nem a fia. Felelet: Hamis Consequentia imez harom okert: Első mert meg bizonyítok hogy a my az attiaie mind az fiuie, az attia soha fia nélkül nem volt, sem attia sem isten...' in Péter Méliusz Juhász, *Az egész Szentírásból való igaz tudomány* (Debrecen: András Komlós, 1570), 70 – MTA, accessed May 20, 2020, http://real-r.mtak.hu/303/1/RMK_I_0077-M_0061-b.pdf.

⁴⁵ 'Mert a mű birodalmunkban, ..., mű azt akariuc, Hogy szabáság legyen. Touábba, Tudgyuc, Hogy a hitt Istenec aiándékia, Es a lelki esmeret semmire erőszackal nem vitethetic.' in Lajos Nagy and Domokos Simén, eds., *Unitárius írók a XVI. évszázadból, I: A nagyváradi disputatio* (Kolozsvár, 1870), 130-131.

⁴⁶ Mihály Balázs, *Early Transylvanian Antitrinitarianism (1566-1571): From Servet to Palaeologus* (Baden-Baden: Éditions Valentin Koekner, 1996), 213.

obscured the true knowledge of God, a summary of Antitrinitarian principles. Dávid argued that the Reformation and the purification of Christianity would be perfected by Antitrinitarians and identified Catholic popes as the manifestations of the Antichrist – which was a common topos in contemporary Protestant arguments against the Catholic Church.⁴⁷

The most considerable political advancement of Antitrinitarianism took place in the renowned Diet of Torda which was organised between 6 and 13 January 1568, and attended by John Sigismund. The Transylvanian estates accepted the Edict of Torda which proclaimed the equality of the Roman Catholic, Lutheran, Calvinist, and Antitrinitarian beliefs. These so-called ‘received religions’ were freely chosen and practiced according to the will of each congregation:

The preachers shall preach the Gospel and proclaim it, each according to his own understanding, and if the congregation wants to follow, so be it, if not, no one shall be compelled, for a soul will not find peace in this way, rather every man shall follow the preacher whose teachings appeal to him. For this reason, no superintendent or any other person shall do harm to the preachers; none shall suffer at the hands of others for religious reasons... and it shall be permitted to no one to jail others or ban them because of their teachings, for faith is a gift of God and arises from the hearing that comes from God’s Word.⁴⁸

It is important to mention that the edict did not acknowledge all Christian denominations or the Jewish community, and John Sigismund even took steps to limit the rights of the Catholics. Nevertheless, it was the first document to proclaim the toleration of different and theologically clashing denominations, and thus, one of the most significant political decrees concerning religious issues in early modern Europe – along with the Peace of Augsburg in the Holy Roman Empire (1555), the Edict of Nantes in the Kingdom of France (1598), and the Peace of Westphalia (1648) that ended the Thirty Years’ War (1618-1648). An interesting parallel can

⁴⁷ Ferenc Dávid, *Rövid Magyarazat mikeppen az Antichristus, az igaz Istenről való tudomant meg homalosította* (Gyulafehérvár: TRRH, 1567). Cf: Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities in East-Central Europe*, 110.

⁴⁸ Quoted in Hungarian in Jenő Zoványi, *A magyar protestantizmus története* (Budapest: Attraktor, 2004, 23; and in English in Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities in East-Central Europe*, 111.

be drawn between the Edict of Torda and the Sandomierz Agreement which denoted a united Protestant front in Poland-Lithuania between 1570 and 1580 against the Counter Reformation activities of the Roman Catholic Church. However, the Polish Brethren did not participate in the agreement, and the success of this coalition itself was largely limited by the institutional difficulties that the radical wing caused within the Protestant Reformed Church.⁴⁹ Furthermore, the Edict of Torda contributed to the process of confessionalisation of Antitrinitarians, a radical Protestant community that was exceptional in sixteenth-century Europe. As for the secular aspect of this toleration, both Catholics and Protestants could hold public offices in Transylvania, but during John Sigismund's reign, Antitrinitarians were the ones mainly supported in doing so. By 1571, the majority of the Hungarian nobility followed their ruler's example in converting to Antitrinitarianism, for instance the chancellor Mihály Csáky (d. 1572) and the general Kristóf Hagymássy (d. 1577).⁵⁰ In his testament, John Sigismund donated money as well as his own library to the Antitrinitarian school college in Alba Iulia for the purpose of it to a university in later years.⁵¹

To conclude, the root of the Transylvanian denominational plurality and religious tolerance can be regarded as a compromise for the sake of stability – required by the political semi-independence from the Ottoman Empire and the internal conditions of a multi-ethnic, multilingual and multireligious society. As the legitimacy of Transylvanian rulers was subject to the sultan's support and incessantly contested by Habsburg monarchs, they could not allow a social tension to further weaken their power. Importantly, John Sigismund's personal fascination with theology and religious innovations was the key factor in the success of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania, at the court and beyond.

⁴⁹ Mark A. Lampert, *Encyclopedia of Martin Luther and the Reformation*, 2 (London: Rowman & Littlefield, 2017), 615-616.

⁵⁰ Ildikó Horn, "Az unitárius elit stratégiái (1575-1603)," *Keresztény Magvető* 105: (1999), 28-34.

⁵¹ Gusztáv Heckenast, ed., *János Zsigmond végrendelete* (Szeged, 1990), 155-169.

The radicalisation and legacy of Antitrinitarianism, 1571-1588

⁵² Despite the unique degree of religious tolerance in Transylvania, a conflict deriving from theological and political reasons resulted in the extraordinary punishment of Ferenc Dávid. In this last part, we shall analyse the political treatment of the Antitrinitarian radicalisation in the 1570s as well as how it influenced the later history of the denomination.

Image 5: Aladár Körösfői-Kriesch: Ferenc Dávid at the diet of Torda (1896, detail)

In the spring of 1571, John Sigismund died without an heir, and the diet in Alba Iulia elected the most powerful Transylvanian lord to be the next ruler – who was a devoted Catholic. Stephen Báthory (1571-1586) intended to revive the Catholic faith in Transylvania but his aspirations were confined by the influence and contrary interests of the estates.⁵³ Nonetheless, Báthory introduced a few measures to diminish Protestantism, especially the predominant Antitrinitarian community. In September 1571, he restricted the publication of Antitrinitarians' works by abolishing their supervision over the press house in Alba Iulia, and imposed a princely censorship on the printing of every book.⁵⁴ Furthermore, Báthory dismissed Antitrinitarians from leading political positions – Biandrata was allowed to remain a court physician by refraining from his involvement with theological issues. However, as the elite had become mainly Protestant by then, Báthory could not employ a Catholic preacher at the court instead of

⁵² Wikimedia Commons, 2008, accessed May 15, 2020.

⁵³ Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities in East-Central Europe*, 117-118.

⁵⁴ Stephen Báthory's public 'press order', 17 September 1571 in Endre Veress, ed., *Báthory István erdélyi fejedelem és lengyel király*, 1 (Kolozsvár, 1944), 142–143.

Ferenc Dávid, but only a Lutheran one, namely Dénes Alesius (1525-1577).⁵⁵ In his letter to Pope Gregory XIII (1572-1585), the prince stated that Transylvanian Catholicism was in a crisis, and that the ‘Arian sect’ was much more dangerous than the ‘Augsburg confession’ since it was spreading more quickly.⁵⁶ Most importantly, a 1572 diet of the estates accepted Báthory’s initiative, that is to say a decree that forbade any further theological innovations, which was confirmed at two additional assemblies in 1573: ‘If anyone is found believing in anything different and new, they will be excommunicated by His Highness...’⁵⁷ The decree stated that any new ideas born after John Sigismund’s death were considered ‘innovative’. Dávid had already stated in his 1569 *De Regno Christi* that baptism should be preceded by theological teaching, which had been argued in Servet’s *Christianismi Restitutio* as well.⁵⁸ Additionally, Dávid started to elaborate on the theory of radical nonadorantism, the rejection of the adoration of Christ in 1572. Evidently, Dávid’s constant eagerness for theological research contradicted Stephen Báthory’s ‘innovation law’. He complained about their situation getting worse day by day in a letter written on 27 December 1573 to the Greek Antitrinitarian theologian, Jacobus Palaeologus (c. 1520-1585).⁵⁹ As other Antitrinitarians introduced in Chapter 1, Palaeologus had to leave Rome, Geneva as well as Poland-Lithuania because of his nonconformist views, and lived in Transylvania between 1573 and 1575.⁶⁰

⁵⁵ János Erdő, “Adatok az Unitárius Egyház püspökválasztási jogának történetéhez,” *Keresztény Magvető* 82: (1976), 90-97, 91.

⁵⁶ Stephen Báthory to Gregory XIII, 14 September 1574 in Veress, *Báthory István... levelezése*, 298–299.

⁵⁷ ‘... ha külömb és új dolognak vallásában találtatnak, ő nagysága excommunicáltassa...’ Resolutions of the Torda Diet, 25-29 May 1572 in Sándor Szilágyi, ed., *Monumenta Comititalia Regni Transylvaniae*, 2 (Budapest: MTA, 1876), 528.

⁵⁸ Ferenc Dávid, *De Regno Christi Liber primus* (Gyulafehérvár, 1569), appendix: ‘Tractatus de paedobaptismo’, accessed May 22, 2020, http://real-r.mtak.hu/978/1/A_199_II.pdf

⁵⁹ Elek Jakab, *Dávid Ferenc emléke*, 2 (Kolozsvar, 1879), 208.

⁶⁰ Religious nonconformism was shared by several Antitrinitarians as their opinions did not fit the doctrines of any denominations.

March 1578 can be considered a turning point in the development of Transylvanian Antitrinitarianism because paedobaptism, the practice of baptising infants, was rejected at a synod. This step caused a crisis within the Antitrinitarian community since it was disapproved by the ‘conservatives’, including Biandrata. The Italian represented a direct tie to the Polish Brethren so after a series of ineffective internal disputes, he turned to Fausto Sozzini for help by inviting him to Transylvania to change Dávid’s opinion. Sozzini spent five months in Dávid’s house in Kolozsvár, where they debated about the worship and invocation of Christ on the basis of biblical references, without any consensus. In summary, Sozzini claimed that Christ had told that people could turn to him after his Ascension, while Dávid argued that the Son’s power was not equal to the Father’s and that the Holy Scripture did not call for addressing prayers to Christ.⁶¹ Dávid’s most significant supporter during his trial was Palaeologus, who later wrote an extensive essay in defence of Dávid’s nonadorantist views and right to proclaim them.⁶² Ferenc Dávid was arrested for religious innovation on Biandrata’s initiative who, fearing the political ramifications of Dávid’s statements, asked Stephen Báthory to intervene. In June 1579, a diet sentenced the ailing Dávid to imprisonment in the castle of Déva, where he died in November that year.⁶³ After the ‘Dávid case’, Biandrata lost his influence and distinguished position among the Antitrinitarians. In his later years, he reconverted to Roman Catholicism and retired from both written and oral theological disputes. He appointed one of his followers, Demeter Hunyadi (d. 1592) as superintendent of the Antitrinitarians who continued Biandrata’s ‘conservative’, politically cautious religious leadership – especially because Stephen Báthory’s successor, Sigismund Báthory (1586-1602) supported Catholics

⁶¹ “Responsio Fausti Socini”; “Domini Fransisci confutatio responsionis Faustinae” in Mihály Balázs, ed., *Ferenc Dávid: Defensio Fransisci Davidis and De dualitate tracta Francisci Davidis (Cracoviae) 1582* (Utrecht: Bibliotheca Unitariorum; Nieuwkoop: De Graaf, 1983), 4-23, 24-120.

⁶² Balázs, *Ferenc Dávid: Defensio...*, 260.

⁶³ Report about the trial by Catholic priest János Leleszi (c.1548-1595), 9 June 1579 in András Bodor, “Újabb adatok egy négyszázéves perről,” *Korunk* 27: (1968), 1208-1216.

against Protestants to an even greater extent.⁶⁴ Nonetheless, endeavours for further theological research and innovation did not cease with Dávid's death. 'Judaising', the adoption of Jewish tenets and traditions, was a frequent allegation against Antitrinitarians in later decades, particularly when the Sabbatarian movement separated from them. Sabbatarians united Antitrinitarian and Jewish principles and confessed the 'human nature' of Jesus Christ as well as the supremacy of the texts of the Old Testament.⁶⁵

Finally, it is worth looking at a remarkable intellectual accomplishment of an Antitrinitarian in sixteenth-century Transylvania. As this chapter has shown, Stephen Báthory turned against Protestants at the court at the beginning of his reign but soon recognised the limitations of this attitude in an overwhelmingly Protestant environment. He had to release the restrictions and keep his court open to Protestants, even refugees, as long as they proved to be loyal to him. Marcello Squarcialupi (1538-1592) was an Italian Antitrinitarian physician who fled from Italy for 'religionis causa' after his confrontation with the Inquisition. He was employed in Alba Iulia by Báthory between 1579 and 1586 to practice medicine and carry out scientific research.⁶⁶

The princely-supported Squarcialupi studied the aurora borealis, the phenomenon of the northern lights, and wrote its first explanation not based on religious and biblical interpretations, but entirely on scientific observations, calculations and analysis.⁶⁷ Therefore, it can be argued that the main ideas of the Protestant Reformation spread in parallel with the diffusion of humanist culture across Europe.

⁶⁴ Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities: in East-Central Europe*, 122-124.

⁶⁵ Róbert Dán et al., eds., *Matthias Vehe-Glirius: life and work of a radical antitrinitarian with his collected writings* (Leiden: Brill; Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1982), 18-36.

⁶⁶ Alessandra Quaranta, "Exile Experiences 'Religionis causa' and the Transmission of Medical Knowledge between Italy and German-Speaking Territories in the Second Half of the Sixteenth Century," in *Fruits of Migration: Heterodox Italian Migrants and Central European Culture 1550-1620*, edited by Cornel Zwielerlein and Vincenzo Lavenia (Leiden: Brill, 2018), 72-101.

⁶⁷ Miklós Kázmér and Gábor Timár, "Az északi fény első tudományos leírása – Marcello Squarcialupi: De coelo ardore (1580)", *Erdélyi Múzeum* 79: (2017), 82-87.

Image 5: Squarcialupi's observation of a 1577 comet⁶⁸

To sum up, radicalisation was the consequence of Ferenc Dávid's theoretical restlessness that crashed Giorgio Biandrata's wariness regarding the weakened position of Antitrinitarians under the Catholic Stephen Báthory.

⁶⁸ Thomas Erastus, András Dudith, Marcello Squarcialupi and Simon Grynaeus, *De cometis dissertationes novae* (Heidelberg, 1580), 53, own picture.

Conclusion

The radical nature of Antitrinitarianism derived from its Christology. The thoughts of the executed Michael Servetus spread swiftly in northern Italy, particularly in the religiously and intellectually tolerant environment of the University of Padua. Antitrinitarian theology was permeated by medical research and physicians who claimed that the Bible did not justify the veneration of Christ or the Holy Spirit. These statements were incompatible with Catholic theology and Protestant dogmas – both the Inquisition and Calvinist communities regarded them as ‘heretics’ which led to the progress of Antitrinitarianism in exile, in more tolerant areas such as Moravia, Poland-Lithuania and Transylvania.

This paper has demonstrated that the unstable political situation of Transylvania compelled its rulers to maintain the internal peace within the multid denominational society. Additionally, Antitrinitarianism gained significance through John Sigismund’s personal affiliation to the new belief which was a result of the influence of his physician and court preacher, Giorgio Biandrata and Ferenc Dávid. It rose to become the primary religion of Transylvania by 1571 to which the majority of the political elite belonged. Furthermore, the internal conflict of Transylvanian Antitrinitarians emerged because Giorgio Biandrata was contented with the unique legal position that the community had already achieved and preserved even under Catholic rulers, the Báthorys. However, Ferenc Dávid was not willing to conform to these conditions and continued his zealous biblical research to refine his theology. Dávid was sued by the authorities after the unsuccessful attempts of reconciliation made by Biandrata and the Italian theologian Fausto Sozzini. Later, the Antitrinitarian community was led towards a ‘moderate direction’. Antitrinitarian intellectuals continued their activities at the Transylvanian court since the Báthory princes’ endeavours to make Catholicism dominant again were obstructed by the pro-Protestant estates. The Unitarian Church is still one of the main denominations of Transylvania,

and Ferenc Dávid's figure has been preserved as a martyr in Unitarian collective memory. Andrew M. Hill has raised a historiographical debate by positing that Transylvanian Antitrinitarians 'owe more to Michael Servetus than they do to John Calvin'. The paper argues that from a theological point of view, Servet's ideas and, occasionally, complete works did appear in the publications of Biandrata and Dávid. Moreover, their interdenominational issue was a result of Dávid's pursuits of theological research beyond Servetian views, moving even further from Catholicism and Calvinism.

In conclusion, this paper has argued that Antitrinitarianism played a significant and proactive role in Transylvanian religious plurality as it was the primary religion of the elite, including John Sigismund, at the time of the Edict of Torda (1568), the first political document that officially acknowledged freedom of worship as a collective right of communities. The slightly changing religious situation provided a favourable environment for the confessionalisation of the various denominations present in Transylvania. As to further research, it would be beneficial to write a comparative or connected history from a transnational perspective on the development of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania and Poland-Lithuania since Antitrinitarians faced different political and denominational conditions. At the same time, as this paper has highlighted, several religious radicals were circulating between the two countries, so various personal and intellectual relations could be analysed.

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Charles V's letter to the Cologne estates (1546/47). A call for "Revolution" against Archbishop Hermann von Wied?

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Abstract

In the 1540s, Archbishop Hermann von Wied attempted to introduce some form of Reformation or at least church reform in his territory, the Archbishopric Cologne. This attempt at reformation was extraordinary in two aspects. Firstly, it was not clearly oriented along the principles of the Protestant or Reformed reformation in the way of Luther, Calvin or Zwingli, but it was rather an attempt to hold a middle position between the orthodox Catholic side and the Protestant one theologically as well as politically. Secondly, it failed and ended in the deposition of Hermann von Wied as archbishop. This is remarkable since it is not only removed of a church authority from its position but also of a prince and sovereign of a territory. This deposition in a legal sense followed the announcement of the imperial ban¹ and excommunication of Hermann von Wied, and in the end, was carried out after the decision of a Landtag (local diet). This Diet came together after a letter of Emperor Charles V to Cologne's estates in which he ordered them to meet. This paper analyses this letter as well as a pamphlet proclaiming the excommunication in German. It will show if the deposition by the estates

¹ The imperial ban, in German *Reichsacht*, was a legal act inside the Holy Roman Empire declaring a person outlawed throughout the empire.

happened from below by the estates and how they were influenced by the emperor and the pope as from the authorities on the level above their immediate liege, the archbishop.

Introduction

Historical scholarship has repeatedly dealt with Hermann von Wied and his failed attempt to introduce Reformation in the Archbishopric of Cologne. As early as the eighteenth and early nineteenth century, a debate took place in the context of the history of the Reformation. At the end of the nineteenth century, Georg Drouven produced a publication of the sources and Conrad Varrentrapp compiled a detailed biography. After the Second World War and the 400th anniversary, a number of shorter writings on the subject appeared, such as by Hubert Jedin and Lutz Hatzfeld, who focused on the Wetterau counts. More recently, Badea, with her examination from the perspective of the "Electoral Preeminence;" Stephan Laux, who worked on the Reformation in the estates; and Theodor Schlüter, with his edition of the publications in the context of the Reformation attempt, are worthy of mention. On the other hand, this work focuses on the act of deposition itself as well as the imperial call for it. The paper proposes the following research questions: How is the deposition of an early modern prince, especially a prince of the church, justified? By whom was this ultimately carried out? How far a political upheaval, such as the deposition of Hermann von Wied, can be interpreted as a revolution?

Definitions of "revolution" for the early modern period

What constitutes a revolution is disputed in historiography. Common definitions are mostly based on phenomena from the French Revolution onwards. In the *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit*, for example, Reichert differentiates between the “early modern revolution” of the old type and the “modern revolution,” among which the focus is on the French Revolution. For him, early modern revolutions are characterised by biblical fundamentalism and a movement that emerges from the people, in contrast to later ones.² Niggemann finds a minimal definitional consensus for revolutions: “Processes in the course of which comprehensive changes with regard to the political and social structures of a society as well as the exchange of political elites are achieved in a relatively short time by violent means.”³ For him, it is important to move away from the template of the French Revolution and to take earlier events into account as well.⁴ Pincus, on the other hand, follows Reichardt’ and Niggemann’s definitions insofar as he describes revolutions as a structural and ideological break with the previous regime, which leads to upheavals of political and socio-economic structures. This can be linked to a violent movement from below. What is also decisive for him is the question of when revolutions occur. He does not see them as a conflict between the conservative and a modernisation movement, but rather as a directional decision in an already ongoing transformation process.⁵

² Reichardt, Rolf, “Revolution”, in: *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit Online*. Consulted online on 14 December 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2352-0248_edn_COM_339983>. First published online: 2019.

³ “Vorgänge, im Zuge derer mit gewaltsamen Mitteln relativ kurzfristig umfassende Veränderungen im Hinblick auf die politischen und sozialen Strukturen einer Gesellschaft sowie der Austausch der politischen Eliten erreicht werden” Ulrich Niggemann, *Revolutionserinnerung in der Frühen Neuzeit: Refiguration der “Glorius Revolution” in Großbritannien (1688-1760)* (Boston: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2017.), 5.

⁴ Niggemann, *Revolutionserinnerung*, 12.

⁵ Steve Pincus, *1688: The first modern Revolution* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2009), 33.

The Archbishopric of Cologne under Hermann von Wied

Hermann von Wied was born in Wied in 1477 into the local dynasty of counts. The Counts of Wied were members of the Wetterauer Grafenverein (Wetterau Counts' Association),⁶ which represented an important power bloc in the environment of the Archbishopric of Cologne, especially as its members were *stiftsfähig*⁷ in Cologne. In 1490, at the age of 13, Hermann von Wied became a canon in Cologne, and in 1503, he was appointed as head of the chancery of the archbishopric by the cathedral chapter. On 13 April 1515, he was elected as Archbishop of Cologne, succeeding Philipp von Daum. This made him not only an ecclesiastical authority but also a secular sovereign who, as Elector, stood at the highest level, below the Emperor, in the hierarchy of the Holy Roman Empire of the German Nation. Notable events from the first years of his reign include his consecration as bishop, which did not take place until 1518, the royal coronation of Charles V, which he performed in Aachen in 1520, and his conflict with the city of Cologne, which did not allow him to ceremonially enter Cologne until 1522.⁸ The city of Cologne had been politically independent from the archbishops since the thirteenth century, but it continued to be the regional centre of the Rhineland and was significant for the archbishops who moved to Bonn.

In the 1520s, Hermann von Wied found himself on the Catholic-imperial side in the conflicts over the Reformation. In 1521, he supported the ban of Martin Luther (1483-1546) and was among the signatories of the Edict of Worms.⁹ As a result, Luther's writings were outlawed in Hermann von Wied's territories and the persecution of Protestants as heretics began in the

⁶ Stephan Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln (1542-1548): Fallstudien zu einer Strukturgeschichte landständischer Reformation (Neuss, Kempen, Andernach, Linz)* (Münster: Aschendorff, 200), 67-68.

⁷ *Stiftsfähigkeit* describes the eligibility of a certain group for the post of canon at a cathedral.

⁸ Stupperich, Robert, "Hermann V." in: *Neue Deutsche Biographie* 8 (1969), S. 636-637 [Online-Version]; URL: <https://www.deutsche-biographie.de/pnd118702793.html#ndbcontent>.

⁹ Andreea Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz, Landesherrschaft und Reform: Das Scheitern der Kölner Reformation unter Hermann von Wied* (Münster: Aschendorff, 2009), 185. The Edict of Worms proclaimed the imperial ban over Martin Luther and with that made him an outlaw in the empire.

course of the 1520s. This was carried out in the Duchy of Westphalia as well, since Hermann von Wied's appointment as administrator of the Bishopric of Paderborn in 1530 it was an integral part of the territories controlled by the Archbishops of Cologne again. According to Jedin, this action against Lutherans is to be seen more like the action of an imperial prince than that of a bishop.¹⁰ For Hermann von Wied, Lutheranism was not a theological problem but a political one. His actions were not driven by the dissenting beliefs per se but by the resulting unrest and threat to the *Landfrieden*.¹¹

As a solution to the question of the Reformation, Hermann von Wied strove for a conciliar solution for the empire, which could have led to a special path within the Catholic Church for the territories of the Holy Roman Empire which, however, never came about. He stuck to this plan until his deposition. Latest by the 1530s, Hermann von Wied assumed a special role in his external perception. In 1530, Hermann von Wied was described by Emperor Charles V as “neither Catholic nor Lutheran, rather a pagan”.¹² Although von Wied was perceived by others as distancing himself from Lutheranism and the Protestant princes of the Holy Roman Empire, this deviation from Catholic orthodoxy posed a problem for the Emperor in terms of imperial policy. In the course of the decade, criticism about von Wied came from all sides, the papal nuncio and Luther himself.¹³ As late as 1540, other Rhenish princes, namely Trier, Jülich and the Electoral Palatinate, were still perceived as “impartial” in the conflict between the emperor and the Protestants.¹⁴ The 1530s were also marked by the beginning of Hermann von Wied's reform programme in the Archbishopric of Cologne. On the one hand, comprehensive

¹⁰ Hubert Jedin, “Fragen um Hermann von Wied,” *Historisches Jahrbuch* 74 (1954): 692.

¹¹ *Landfrieden* describes the concept of internal peace in a territory in the late medieval and early modern period. This peace was to be achieved by jurisdictional measurements and should stop feuds and revolts.

¹² “Weder katholisch noch lutherisch, eher ein Heide” Jedin, *Fragen um Hermann von Wied*, 692.

¹³ Jedin, “Fragen um Hermann von Wied,” 692.

¹⁴ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Päminenz*, 5.

administrative reforms took place,¹⁵ which concerned the judicial system,¹⁶ the police code,¹⁷ a mining code, and the coinage system as well. These reforms aimed to get the administration of the territory up to the standards of the time but, above all, to preserve the Landfrieden. On the other hand, a first attempt at reforming the church order was carried out in 1536. This came about through a provincial synod in the archdiocese. The Enchiridion of Johann Gropper was the authoritative document of this first church reform under Hermann von Wied.¹⁸ This reform was supported by the Erasmian circles surrounding the archbishop, the neighbouring territories of Jülich-Kleve-Berg and the imperial city of Cologne.¹⁹ However, a complete church reform in the Erasmian sense did not take place in Cologne, in contrast to the neighbouring Jülich-Kleve-Berg.²⁰ Humanism as a drive for church reform on the archbishop's side, remains questionable, since Hermann, according to Jedin, was not a humanist in the sense of Erasmus, not even an “intellectual” by contemporary standards.²¹

¹⁵ Wolf-Dietrich Penning, *Die weltlichen Zentralbehörden im Erzstift Köln: Von der ersten Hälfte des 15. bis zum Beginn des 17. Jahrhunderts* (Bonn: Ludwig Röhrscheid-Verlag, 1977), 60-61.

¹⁶ Elisabeth M. Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger als politische Reformer: Humanismusideal und Herrschaftspraxis am Niederrhein im 16. Jahrhundert* (Köln: Böhlau, 2006), 37-45.

¹⁷ Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 34-37.

¹⁸ Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 59.

¹⁹ Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 54-59.

²⁰ The church reforms that are called erasmian oriented are rooted in the humanistic movement and oriented themselves along the teachings of Erasmus of Rotterdam (1466-1536) and other humanists influenced by him. Via new church order and clerical and public education they tried to find a way to remedy the insufficiencies that led to the Reformation without taking a reformatory or orthodox Catholic standpoint.

²¹ Jedin, *Fragen um Hermann von Wied*, 691-692.

The Cologne Reformation

Instead of continuing these reforms, Hermann von Wied turned away from the Catholic orthodoxy from 1540 onwards and moved closer to Protestantism. This happened under the impressions of his participation as a moderate Catholic representative at the religious discussions of Hagenau, Worms and Regensburg in 1540 and 1541.²² On these occasions, he also got to know Martin Butzer(1491-1551), who took part in them on the Protestant side. Butzer had already turned to Protestantism in the early 1520s and was active as a reformer in the following years in the regions of modern-day south Germany and eastern France, especially in Strasbourg. As a reaction to the Regensburg Interim of 1541, in which a provisional church reform within the dioceses by the imperial prelates was demanded, Hermann initiated a new church reform - even though the validity of this part of the Regensburg Interim for the territory of Electorate Cologne was questionable.²³ Johann Gropper(1503-1559), who aimed to continue the internal Catholic reform, was entrusted with the task to formulate a new church order. Gropper, being a cleric that rose through the ranks in the Archbishopric of Cologne, had already been entrusted with the earlier administrative reforms of the territory. In 1542, Martin Butzer was also called to Cologne by Hermann von Wied. After initial cooperation between Gropper and Butzer, a break occurred in 1543 with the beginning of Butzer's sermons in Bonn. In these sermons, it became clear that Butzer and his patron, the archbishop, did not have a purely internal Catholic reform in mind but that reformatory ideas were to be implemented. This led to a letter of protest from the majority of the cathedral chapter. This resistance was mainly carried out by the university, priest canons and the secondary clergy of the Archbishopric of Cologne. In the following years, the university embodied the resistance to the Reformation by

²² Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln*, 70-71.

²³ Badaea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 18.

educated bourgeois circles in the city of Cologne.²⁴ In reaction to Butzer's sermons, Johann Gropper ventured a final proposal for Catholic reform. This was taken up by Hermann von Wied, who tried to pacify Catholic and Protestant groups in the archbishopric by involving both Butzer and Gropper. Through this and the assertion that the new church order was an implementation of the recess of the imperial Diet of Regensburg, Hermann von Wied succeeded in gaining approval for his reform plans at the Märzlandtag, a diet of the estates of Cologne in March 1543. Butzer was now exclusively entrusted with the implementation, Gropper from now on formed an opposition from the city of Cologne with the majority chapter that remained Catholic.²⁵ After the approval of the Estates, Butzer sought Protestant support for the project. After Johann Pistorius the Elder(1504-1583), a reformer in Hesse, could not be won over, Philipp Melanchthon(1497-1560) was brought in.²⁶ Butzer and Melanchthon drew up the *Einfältige Bedenken*, which was the central document of the Cologne Reformation attempt. It was completed in July 1543, and after its acceptance by the Estates, was printed in September of the same year. In terms of content, this new church order combined traditional church institutions, such as monasteries and convents, with reformatory ideas in the doctrine of justification and the sacraments. A special emphasis was placed on improving pastoral care.²⁷ In addition to rejection by the *Altgläubigen* (those who remained catholic) and by the protest faction of the cathedral chapter, it also received criticism from Protestants, and even from Luther himself. The dissent originated in the Marburg Colloquy of 1529, and the differing views on the issue of the sacraments. The *Einfältige Bedenken* was influenced by various church constitutions of Protestant territories in the empire that had already been written in the 1530s.

²⁴ Lutz Hatzfeld, "Dr. Gropper, die Wetterauer Grafen und die Reformation in Kurköln 1537/1547," *Archiv für Kulturgeschichte* 36 (1954): 225, <https://doi.org/10.7788/akg-1954-jg11>.

²⁵ A list of all the members of the cathedral chapter of Cologne and their positioning can be found with Hatzfeld, "Die Wetterauer Grafen", 228-229.

²⁶ Jedin, "Fragen um Hermann von Wied," 696.

²⁷ Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln*, 72-73.

Hermann von Wied himself intervened in the creation of the *Bedenkens* in favour of the *landständische nobility* (landed nobility) so that he would not lose their support.²⁸ In terms of foreign policy, this phase of the Cologne Reformation is marked by the Geldrian War of Succession between Emperor Charles V and Wilhem of Kleve-Jülich-Berg. The primary issues were the inheritance of the Duchy of Guelders and influence in the Netherlands and on the Rhine, which was of decisive importance for the Archbishopric of Cologne due to the geographical proximity and the episcopal responsibility for the territory.²⁹ However, Catholic orthodoxy represented by the Emperor was opposed by a more reform-oriented prince, William of Cleves(1539-1592). Although the church reform in Jülich-Kleve-Berg was Erasmian, the support of this regional power was necessary for the implementation of Hermann von Wied's plans. The defeat of William of Cleves at Düren was the first major setback for the Reformation on the Rhine. Nonetheless, Hubert Jedin does not see this as the end of the Reformation, as various twists and turns were taken before his deposition.³⁰

In 1544, the Catholic majority of the cathedral chapter appealed to the pope and emperor, asking them to intervene for the Catholic cause.³¹ They were not supported by the cathedral chapters of the other Rhenish electors³², but by the bishops of Liège and Utrecht who were subordinate to the Archbishop of Cologne in religious matters.³³ The conflict between the cathedral chapter and the archbishop was going on in court trials before the emperor and the pope. While a break with Rome became increasingly clear, Hermann tried to prevent condemnation by the emperor. The controversial question was whether the *Einfältiges Bedenken* and the innovations in the

²⁸ Jedin, "Fragen um Hermann von Wied," 696-697.

²⁹ Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 73-74.

³⁰ Jedin, "Fragen um Hermann von Wied," 697.

³¹ Badaea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 78-86.

³² Jedin, "Fragen um Hermann von Wied," 697-698.

³³ Paul III., *Das Päpstlich vrteil*, fol. Av.

church constitution, as general questions of faith, could be decided on without a resolution of a new provincial council.³⁴ Just like the War of the Geldrian Succession had an influence as a foreign policy framework at the beginning of the Cologne Reformation, this was all the more the case with the conflict between the Schmalkaldic League and the emperor. This alliance of Protestant princes had tried to win Hermann over to their side and supported him against the emperor. However, the Electorate of Cologne never joined the Schmalkaldic League, as Hermann continued to try to play both sides and was never fully prepared to break with the Emperor. The differing interests of Saxony and Hesse, the two leading powers of the League, made concrete support difficult.³⁵ Nevertheless, in the archbishop's environment, the counts of Wetterau had little interest in a possible strengthening of Hesse.³⁶

The intervention of the authorities

The trial in front of the emperor came to an end on 26 January 1546 with the imposition of the imperial ban on Hermann von Wied, before the Schmalkaldic League had been able to provide any considerable support.³⁷ This, however, did not mean the end of Hermann's rule. The cathedral chapter and the estates did not want to enforce the ban without a papal judgement. In the spring of 1546, the papacy finally intervened in the conflict. On 16 April 1546, Pope Paul III(1534-1549) excommunicated Hermann von Wied, but this was not publicly announced until 16 August 1546.³⁸ The pope did not intervene of his own accord, but acted on an appeal by the

³⁴ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 82-83.

³⁵ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 111-120.

³⁶ Hatzfeld, *Die Wetterauer Grafen*, 214.

³⁷ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 183-186; Dorothee Mußnug, *Acht und Bann im 15. und 16. Jahrhundert* (Berlin: Duncker & Humblot, 2016), 264. Mußnug sees in the *Declaratoria Sententia* a mere renouncement of the degrees, in which an imperial ban was only threatened by acting against. This stands in contrast to the bans against the heads of the Schmalkaldic League.

³⁸ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 199-200.

Catholic party at the Curia. The plaintiffs here were not only the Catholic majority chapter which had turned away from Hermann but also the University of Cologne and the bishops of the Bishoprics of Liège and Utrecht, both subordinate to Cologne. These parties, too, would ultimately have been affected by such a church reform on the ecclesiastical level.

Although the Latin excommunication was also distributed in printed form³⁹, the decision probably became known by the wider public rather through the German-language writing of Johann Baptista Cicada (1543-1554), the bishop of Albenga.⁴⁰ In this text, printed in Augsburg, he summarises the papal sentences. Particularly impressive is the frontispiece of the pamphlet, which consists of two text pyramids with a German translation of the excommunication. In the upper one, the pope at the behest of the “dignified Clergy”, the majority of the cathedral chapter and the “high school,”⁴¹ that is to say the University of Cologne, recognised that Hermann had become unfit as Archbishop of Cologne and administrator of the Bishopric of Paderborn since he had been deprived of all honour and dignity in the archbishopric and bishopric due to “many improper reforms in the question of religion”.⁴² There is a clear reference to the appellants and the reason for the excommunication - the new church order. His unfitness for the office of archbishop derived from his actions. The second pyramid proclaimed that the Pope had absolved all the ecclesiastical and secular estates committed to Hermann von Wied of all oaths and duties to him.⁴³ This way, von Wied was practically deposed politically as well, and continuing to hold power would have been conceivable only as a Protestant sovereign detached from the Church. What is astonishing is that Cicada added the appellation as the second part of

³⁹ Theodor C. Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften zur “Kölner Reformation”*: Die Publizistik um den Reformationsversuch des Kölner Erzbischofs und Kurfürsten Hermann von Wied (1515-1547) (Wiesbaden: Hassarowitz Verlag, 2005), 307-308.

⁴⁰ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 309.

⁴¹ “Erwürdigen Clereseey”; “hohen Schul”; Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 309.

⁴² “viler unzimlicher newerung in der religion” Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 309.

⁴³ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 309.

the text after publishing the papal judgment - as announced in the second pyramid. The appeal practically became the justification for the judgment. The final section of the leaflet made it clear how serious the Catholic Church was about banning the Archbishop of Cologne. An indulgence written in the style of a “crusade indulgence” for the fight against heretics was proclaimed,⁴⁴ which became even more explosive given the raging Schmalkaldic War.

As a result of the excommunication of the archbishop, the previous coadjutor Adolf von Schauenburg was appointed as administrator of the archbishopric. This had happened even before the excommunication was published, at the beginning of July 1546.⁴⁵ However, as in the case of the ban, the execution of this decision was to take some time.

⁴⁴Paul III., *Das Päpstlich vrteil*, fol. IV Br-Bv .

⁴⁵ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*. 200.

The imperial letter to the estates

Encouraged by the excommunication and the papal action, Emperor Charles V also became active again in the Causa von Wied in December 1546. In a mandate, he addressed the estates of the Electorate of Cologne in order to finally achieve the deposition of the archbishop after the ban and excommunication had been imposed. Issued on December 21, the publication was printed in Cologne on January 3.⁴⁶

Jaspar von Gennep

The imperial mandate was printed by Jaspar von Gennep.⁴⁷ From 1544, during the entire conflict over the Reformation attempt, he was the house and court printer of the Catholic party, especially of the majority chapter in the city of Cologne, which had turned away from Hermann von Wied, as well as of the university. Through him, the Catholic side had the opportunity to print outside the archbishop's reach by distributing anti-Protestant writings along with letters from the pope and emperor in the city of Cologne, and thus, to enter into a competition via leaflets and propagandistic publications with the archbishop.⁴⁸ This, together with the Protestant counterparts printing in Bonn,⁴⁹ led to a veritable propaganda war for public opinion in the archbishopric and its subordinate dioceses. This can be seen in the immense number of over 250 prints published between 1540 and 1553, the death of Hermann von Wied, in the context of the Reformation attempt, which can be found in Schlüter's work.

⁴⁶ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 329.

⁴⁷ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 45.

⁴⁸ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 3-5.

⁴⁹ The main printer for the reformation side, which fled from the city including the archbishop and the minority cathedral chapter, was Laurenz von der Mühlen. Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 3-4.

The frontispiece

In a pamphlet of this kind, the frontispiece can be considered a *regestum* or abstract. It summarises the main text along with the imperial decision. The text is followed by an imperial coat of arms.⁵⁰ This consists of a double-headed eagle, crowned with the imperial crown, with a breast shield *party per pale*. On the right-hand side, it is defined by a *Fesse*, on the left-hand side, by a *bendy*. Due to the monochrome print, the tinctures are missing, but it can be assumed that the shield on the right is the Austrian shield, *gules a fess argent*, and on the left the coat of arms of Burgundy, i.e. *bendy or and azure*. In this case, however, the depiction of the Burgundian coat of arms would be inaccurate, as it should consist of *Bendy of six or and azure, a bordure gules*. Nevertheless, contemporaries of this pamphlet probably recognised it as the coat of arms of the empire and the emperor. This coat of arms makes it clear that Charles V appears in the following pages as Emperor of the Holy Roman Empire, ruled by the House of Habsburg, which is connected with Burgundy. A complete coat of arms of Charles V, on the other hand, would also have included the arms of the Spanish crown, possibly evoking ideas of Spanish servitude, which was perceived as a contrast to *Teutscher Libertät*.⁵¹

The text on the frontispiece already summarises the content of the imperial mandate, and thus, informs the reader about the most important information of this publication. Since this was an imperial mandate, it was sent to the estates of the Archbishopric of Cologne. These estates are

⁵⁰ Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.1r.

⁵¹ *Spanischen Servitut* was for the contemporaries the tyrannical rule of Charles V and his successors in the colonies. It was strongly connected with the *leyenda negra* which developed with the appearance of the reports of Bartolomeo de las Casas. Schmidt, Peer. Schwarze Legende, Schmidt, Peer, “Schwarze Legende”, in: *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit Online*. Consulted online on 14 December 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2352-0248_edn_COM_347405>. First published online: 2019.

In contrast to this, the concept of *Teutscher Libertät* can be seen as the self-image of the imperial princes. Schmidt, Georg, Freiheit, Schmidt, Georg, “Freiheit”, in: *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit Online*. Consulted online on 14 December 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2352-0248_edn_COM_266320>. First published online: 2019.

mentioned one by one in order to address each of these groups directly - Counts, Lords, Knights, Nobility, Estates and Cities. They are summoned by the “kaiserlicher Macht” (imperial power) to appear before the cathedral chapter, the first institution in the territory, and before the imperial commissars on January 24, 1547, in the Domkapitel Haus in Cologne and to act in accordance with the following mandate.⁵² Thus, it was not only already obvious that a Landtag (diet for the territory of the archbishopric Cologne) was convened by the Emperor, for which the time and place had already been determined, but also that it would take place under the supervision of imperial commissars. This frontispiece shows astonishingly clearly that Archbishop von Wied, who had been excommunicated but still held on as sovereign, was not regarded as the head of the archbishopric. This role was rather assigned to the cathedral chapter, in this case, the part of the divided cathedral chapter recognised by the emperor. This elevation of the chapter indicates an attempt on the part of the emperor to bypass the level of his direct subordinate, the archbishop, as a prince of the empire, in order to find partners for handling the situation in Cologne at the level of the estates instead.

The aforementioned estates were not only the addressees of the imperial mandate but also the presumed recipients of this and other printed copies. Schlüter mentions in particular the Catholics or those in opposition to Hermann von Wied as the recipients of the prints commissioned by the cathedral chapter and von Gennepe.⁵³ In the case of this invitation to the Diet, which meant nothing other than the final deposition of the archbishop, it can also be assumed that it was sent to the reform-minded estates and published for the wider population in the city of Cologne and the towns of the archbishopric as well.

⁵² Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.1r.

⁵³ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 3.

The date and attestation of the mandate

The location and dating of the imperial mandate were given in a dateline at the end of the text of the original document. “Given in our’s and the empires city Hall in Swabia the one and twentieth day of the month December Anno 7c. In the six and fortieth of our emperorship in the seven and twentieth and our realms one and thirtieth.”⁵⁴ It was thus given in the imperial city of Schwäbisch Hall by Emperor Charles V on December 21 1546. In addition to the date adjusted to the birth of Christ, a date according to the start of Charles' reign is also used. Here, both his twenty-seven years of reign as Emperor of the Holy Roman Empire of the German Nation and his thirty-one years of rule in “his realms” are mentioned in the text of the original document. This was presumably counted from his coming of age and the start of his reign over the Duchy of Burgundy. In the date according to the incarnation, the full spelling of the formula “*Anno Domini*” and “*Anno Incarnatione*” as well as the century after Christ's birth is dispensed with and simply represented by an abbreviated et cetera. The readers were aware of what had to be inserted for this ‘*et cetera*’, since these formulas were probably known to the intended readers of such documents. The text is signed with “*Carolus*” for Charles V. In print, this was of course not an authentic signature. For these reasons, and in order to ensure the authenticity of the contents of the text, various authentication features were also included in this print. Directly below the “signature” of Charles V, one can find “*Vidit Naves*”, a confirmation that the original document was seen and authenticated by Imperial Vice-Chancellor Johann Naves(1500-1547). As Imperial Vice-Chancellor, he was the head of the Chancellery of the Holy Roman Empire and the highest authority in charge of issuing documents. In the matter of Hermann von Wied's attempt at reformation, however, Naves also appeared as a diplomat, and

⁵⁴ “Geben in unser und des Reichs Stat Hall in Schwaben am eyn und zwentzigsten Tag des Monats Decembris Anno 7c. Im Sechs und viertzigsten unsers Kaiserthumbes im sieben und zwentzigsten und unserer Reiche im eyn und dreissigsten.”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.3r.

in 1545 and 1546, tried to intervene on behalf of the imperial Catholic side in order to prevent Hermann, and thus Kurköln, from turning to the Schmalkaldic League.⁵⁵

The notarial certifications

In a copy of the Erzbischöfliche Akademische Bibliothek Paderborn⁵⁶, handwritten authentications by two Cologne notaries follow the print of the imperial mandate. In contrast to the rest of the Early High German text, these authentications were written in Latin. Leonard von Fossa and Jakob von Dulcken confirmed the authenticity of the document on 3 January 1547. Leonard von Fossa was the secretary of the Cologne Cathedral Chapter or, as he wrote, “Public notary and secretary of the metropolitan church of Cologne.”⁵⁷ Jakob von Dulcken described himself as a cleric of the Cologne diocese, public scribe and notary for the matter of the archbishopric of Cologne by the imperial authority.⁵⁸

These handwritten notarial authentications could be particularly necessary for those copies that went from Cologne to the estates of the archbishopric, which tended to side with von Wied and the Reformation. A notarial certification was supposed to guarantee the authenticity of the content and pre-empt the fear of possible changes by the Catholic majority chapter or the pro-Catholic printer von Gennep. This seems especially expedient given the controversial nature of

⁵⁵ Aulinger, Rosemarie, “Naves, Johann von” in: *Neue Deutsche Biographie* 19 (1999), S. 1-2 [Online-Version]; URL: <https://www.deutsche-biographie.de/pnd137999100.html#ndbcontent>.

⁵⁶ As a digitised version found as EAB Paderborn VD16 ZV 4427, it is probably identical with the EAB Paderborn Th 1440a n.27 that Schlüter named. Schlüter, *Flug- und Streitschriften*, 329.

⁵⁷ “Notarius publicus, ac Metropolitana ecclesiae Colonien. Secretarius”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.3v.

⁵⁸ “Clericus Colonien. Dioecesis, publicus sacra Imperiali autoritate, et in venerabili curia Archiepiscopali Colonien. Causarum Notarius et Scriba”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol. 4r.

the imperial mandate since it contained nothing less than a call for the deposition of the sovereign by the estates.

The text of the imperial mandate

Following the protocol of imperial mandates, which had already developed in the High Middle Ages, the text of the printed document began with the Intitulatio and Salutatio. Emperor Charles V calls himself “by the grace of God Roman Emperor, semper Augustus, in Germania, Hispania, both Sicily, Jerusalem, Hungary, Dalmatia, Croatia, etc. King, Archduke of Austria, Duke of Burgundy, etc., Count of Flanders and Tyrol, etc.”⁵⁹ He addressed the “noble and honourable nobles loyal to us and the empire, all counts, lords, knights, nobles and towns of the archdiocese of Cologne”⁶⁰, to whom he offered his grace and wished all the best. Even in this highly formalised section of the mandate, it is clear that Charles V was concerned to address the estates of the Archbishopric of Cologne as subjects of the Empire and not those of the archbishop. On the one hand, they were to be flattered by being called noble, honourable and loyal;. On the other hand, the reference to loyalty is also a reminder of their duty to the empire and loyalty to the emperor and the Catholic cause, and not to the archbishop as sovereign.

⁵⁹ “von gottes gnaden Römischer Kayser, zu allen Zeiten mehrer des Reichs, in germanien, zu Hispanien, beyder Sicilien, Jerusalem, Hungeren, Dalmatien, Croatien, etc. Künig, Erzherzog zu Österreich, Herzug zu Burgundi etc., Graue zu Flandern und Tirol etc” The big Titulation is although only down to the level of counties. In the individual ranks, it was not used as a complete enumeration of all claimed territories - only the most important ones were mentioned while the rest was shortened with an “et cetera”’s in the Americas. It looks like this again is a try to focus solely on Charles V acting as emperor and the whole conflict only being an internal issue in the empire. All possible connections to the rule in the colonies as well as the leyenda negra should be averted as much as possible. See Footnote 50.

⁶⁰ “edelen ersamen unseren und des Reichs getrewen Nobiles, allen Graven, herrn, ritterschafft, adel stenden, und stätten des Erzstiftes cöln”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

The following *narratio* describes the situation in the Archbishopric of Cologne, which was perceived as maladministration and led to the issue of the imperial mandate. Charles V reported that these events were brought to his attention, so he did not act from a purely external point of view. “us reached believably”⁶¹ Here he referred not only to simple reports that had reached him but also to the appeals of the Catholic estates from the past years and the trial against the archbishop that had been going on since 1444. As the origin of the complaints, reference is made to the “newly established preachers”.⁶² These new preachers were Martin Butzer as well as those Protestant preachers who had contributed to the spread of the Einfältiges Bedenkens after its publication.⁶³ Martin Butzer's sermons from 1542 onwards revealed that Hermann von Wied's plans for reforming the church constitution had not been within the framework of the Catholic Church and of the changes demanded by the emperor at the Regensburg Diet, but would also take up reformatory ideas. Since Butzer's sermons, however, the situation had only worsened. This mandate aimed to ensure that Cologne did not fall into “apostasy and ruin”⁶⁴ for lack of “understanding”⁶⁵ on the part of the Reformation-minded estates. The “lack of a proper head”⁶⁶ was made responsible for this possible decline. The blame was thus placed directly on Hermann von Wied, even though he was not even mentioned by name in the entire text since he was not qualified to preside over his territory as sovereign. The urgency of installing his successor Adolf von Schauenburg, who was never mentioned by name either, also alluded to the fact that the Electorate of Cologne had been in practice without a recognised sovereign due to Hermann von Wied's ban and excommunication. This could probably only be expressed this clearly since the excommunication had been imposed on him a few months

⁶¹ “*uns gelangt gläublich an*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁶² “*Newen aufgestellten Predicandten*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁶³ Badaea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 78.

⁶⁴ “*abfall und verderben*”

⁶⁵ “*Einsehens*”

⁶⁶ “*mangel eines ordentlichen Haupts*”

earlier. The Emperor wanted to lead the Archdiocese of Cologne with its estates and subjects back to “grace and the good”.⁶⁷ In addition to this return to the grace of the Catholic Church and the empire, the dignity, status and nature of the archbishopric should be preserved, and harm and disadvantage should be averted from the subjects who were dependent on the sovereign. The status quo ante was presented as the ideal perspective, in other words, “the good old days” before the Reformation. However, this projection was not entirely honest, since the need for reform had been recognised and negotiated in Regensburg. The Regensburg Interim may have not applied directly to the Archbishopric of Cologne, but the need for reforms was just as prevalent there. Appeals were also made to the dignity of the archbishopric as an entity; it was hardly just a question of the loss of an albeit important Catholic metropolitan see, but for Charles as a Habsburg, the majority of the electorates for the Catholic side and the election of a successor from his dynasty were in danger. In Saxony and Brandenburg, two electors were already Protestant, the Electoral Palatinate still belonged to the group of the indecisive, and the Catholic majority consisted only of Habsburg-controlled Bohemia and the three ecclesiastical electors. A possible turn away of Cologne from Catholicism was connected with a threatening institutional crisis for the empire or at least with the threatening loss of the imperial throne for the House of Habsburg. This became particularly clear when the Emperor spoke of the Archdiocese of Cologne as “our and the Empire's most noble member”.⁶⁸

As a positive counterpart to the imperial action, the action of the estates “among themselves”⁶⁹ was now mentioned. They were given the actual role of governing the territory, since the head, the sovereign, cannot be relied upon, or at the time of the mandate, there was no legitimate

⁶⁷ “*gnaden und gutem*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁶⁸ “*unseres und des Reichs vornehmsten Glieder*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁶⁹ “*unter sich selbst*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

office bearer. The Emperor's intensified intervention is justified by his and the estates' unsuccessful attempts to solve the problems of church reform and the defiance of Hermann von Wied. Here, too, the mandate remains relatively vague as to what has been done and what has failed, and it does not go into any further detail about the situation that is perceived as a problem; the aim is once again to avert further evil, or more precisely “bad advise and disadvantage”, from the archbishopric but also from the subjects. The emperor had decided to finally act with the “inspiration of the Almighty”.⁷⁰ This divine inspiration was probably less a vision of Charles than of the papal excommunication in the early summer of 1546. In the following part, the emperor alternates between flattering words towards the estates and implicit threats. He emphasises that his action would only promise success, “could be done most conducive” if it were done with the knowledge and assistance of the Estates.⁷¹ The Emperor wanted to refrain from a deposition from above, but instead, carry it out consensually with the involvement of the Estates of Cologne. Not only should action by the emperor alone be impossible, but even the decision of the *Disputatio* has disguised him as the decision-maker. The summoning of the estates was done by the cathedral chapter and the “*Afterdechant*” (Subdeacon), which he describes as “honourable and our dear ones”.⁷² Even though Charles names them as the inviting ones, the summoning to the Diet was done by him. This is the actual legal content of the mandate. The estates are summoned to meet in Cologne on January 24 1547 in the house of the cathedral chapter to discuss the case of Hermann von Wied and to reach a decision on the solution of the problems under the supervision of the cathedral chapter, that is to say, the Catholic majority chapter, and imperial commissioners. Even in this most concrete part of the mandate, Hermann's deposition is not mentioned, but only implicitly alluded to. Instead, peace

⁷⁰ “*unrath unnd nachtheils*”; “*verlehung des Allmächtigisten*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷¹ “*am füeglichsten geschehen könnte*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷² “*ehrsam und unsere lieben*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

and unity among the estates and subjects (*Landfrieden*) were to be maintained and the “prevention of further disputes and bad advise” was to be achieved.⁷³

The presence of all the estates at the Diet is to be ensured in a particularly forceful manner. Thus, they are not only requested and required by the Emperor, but he also seriously commands them to appear with this letter. That this is not just a request from the Emperor, but rather an order, is clear from the fact that this call is made “especially by roman imperial power” and is linked to a reminder of the duties towards the emperor, the empire and the archbishopric.⁷⁴ Excuses and refusals would not be tolerated, but anyone who is genuinely prevented from attending would be given the opportunity to send an envoy with extensive decision-making authority.⁷⁵ The repeatedly mentioned unity of the estates is to be achieved through complete or at least extensive presence at the Diet, in order to lend a broader legitimation to the deposition of the archbishop and the appointment of his successor. The deposition should not only be carried out by the remaining Catholic majority chapter, but by the Diet itself.

That this Diet and the question of the deposition weren't an open-ended question becomes clear in the following paragraph. Imperial commissars will also be present, who are to report on the emperor's behalf which measures are most suitable to ensure peace and pacification. The estates were asked to listen to these proposals and to decide “to do and act, execute and help to carry out that” as the urgency of the situation required.⁷⁶ “That” in this case referred to the emperor's plans, that is to say the deposition of Hermann von Wied and the appointment of the coadjutor

⁷³ “*verhütung vorstehender weiterung und unrath*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷⁴ “*insbesonds von Römisch kayserlicher macht*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷⁵ Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷⁶ “*das jenig zu tun und zu handeln, vollstrecken und zu vollziehen helfen*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.3r.

von Schauenburg as his successor. A different decision would be neither expected nor tolerated. This is also evident in the last sentence of the text before the date. Instead of formulating a concrete legal consequence for the violation of this imperial mandate in the sense of a *sanctio*, another appeal is made to the estates. A violation, a non-attendance, but obviously also a non-unanimous Diet resolution not agreeable to the emperor should be avoided in order to prevent a continuation of the grievances and to avert harm to the archbishopric, its estates and subjects.⁷⁷

The threat of the imperial army under Maximilian von Büren, which was on its way to Cologne and was at the gates of Cologne at the time of the Diet, hangs over the whole scene.⁷⁸ Acting against this mandate would cause negative consequences - for instance, military intervention in Electoral Cologne by imperial troops, and thus, far greater material ramifications than the battle by leaflets and other prints; or the excommunication and ostracism of the sovereign. The seriousness of such a danger was also known to the population and the estates, through the indulgence against heretics granted by the pope and through the letter of Johann Baptista Cicada from the previous year. After this letter, it was clear to everyone that the emperor had given the estates two options - to depose Hermann von Wied and recognise Adolf von Schauenburg, which would mean a return to the bosom of the Church and the empire; or to continue the conflict and side with Hermann, which would have resulted in military intervention by the emperor. In the end, Charles V decided to depose Hermann himself, but the emperor kept up the semblance of an orderly process and deposition from “below” - although a deposition from “above” had already taken place through the ban and excommunication.

⁷⁷ Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol. 3r.

⁷⁸ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 215.

Consequences of the imperial mandate

Hermann von Wied, who in the course of 1546 had sent notes of protest against his imperial ban and excommunication, and had also tried to circumvent a demand for his abdication, planned to make a last attempt to remain in power at this Diet.⁷⁹ He wanted to appear before the estates in Cologne in person, and thus, to prevent his final deposition. Nonetheless, this endeavour failed as the imperial commissars already reached Cologne on 22 January 1547.⁸⁰ As already indicated in the imperial letter, the presence of the imperial troops outside the city and the presence of the commissars at the Diet were necessary to prevent the secular estates from once again avoiding a final decision on the deposition of the archbishop. In the end, however, they decided to depose Hermann von Wied and install Adolf von Schauenburg as administrator. Historians disagree on the question of whether Hermann subsequently abdicated on 24 or 25 January or February. Badea explains conclusively why this could not have happened, but this theory is still found in older scholarship - for example, Stephan Laux has phrased it as “*Resignation*” (resignation), Dorothee Mußnug, as “*Verzicht auf seine Ämter*” (Renunciation of his offices) and Kloosterhuis, as “*Abdankung*” (Abdication).⁸¹ The candidacy of Adolf von Schauenburg represented the ideal compromise for the succession. He had family connections to the Wetterau counts, was probably a good Catholic, despite rumours of his sympathies for Protestantism, and had already been active as coadjutor at the centre of the archbishopric's power since 1533.⁸² After his deposition, Hermann von Wied remained in the

⁷⁹ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 202-215.

⁸⁰ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 216.

⁸¹ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 217; Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln*, 74; Mußnug, *Acht und Bann*, 265; Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 75.

⁸² Hatzfeld “Die Wetterauer Grafen”, 228.

territory of Kurköln and retired to his hunting lodge at Buschhoven before returning to Wied Castle, where he died in 1522.⁸³

Conclusion

So can Hermann von Wied's deposition be described as a revolution? In addition, is the imperial mandate to be understood as a call for revolution? Of the characteristics of a revolution as defined by Niggemann, Reichardt and Pincus, hardly any can be found in the Cologne Reformation. Hermann von Wied was deposed and the Protestant part of the Cologne elite lost its influence and power. Nonetheless, his successor Adolf von Schauenburg came from the same circles and the Catholic ruling class of the Archbishopric Cologne consolidated their position, even though it had been weekend during the Attempt at Reformation. What is given, however, is an ideological, and in this case religious, reorientation. Economic structures did not play a considerable role in the entire conflict. A violent upheaval did not take place either, certainly not carried out by a movement from below. However, had the decision of the estates in January 1547 been different, this could even have led to a possible conflict with the emperor and further disruption of the Landfrieden, which then would have had to be referred to as a revolution. The possibility of unrest during the diet seemed at least likely enough for the imperial troops to be ordered to intervene in an emergency.⁸⁴ Thus, Hermann von Wied's deposition could, to a certain extent, be described as a prevention of a revolution. From the point of view of a revolution, the Cologne Reformation attempt and its end appear to fit perfectly into the framework. For example, Pincus' thesis of revolution as a decision of direction within a process of modernisation, can be found. The church constitution had to be reformed but the question that arose was whether it should be an internal Catholic reform, an Erasmian-

⁸³ Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln*, 74.

⁸⁴ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 215.

inspired one, or oriented towards one of the Protestant denominations. This did not lead to a revolution, but no less significantly, to the deposition of an elector, through a complex interplay between the estates, the church and the emperor.

Although it is not a call for revolution, Charles V's Imperial Mandate, in which he addresses the Cologne estates, shows the complexity of deposing a prince in the sixteenth century. Since violence and a breach of the Landfrieden were to be prevented, an interplay between the emperor, the pope and the estates was necessary to depose Hermann von Wied as archbishop of Cologne. Institutionalised trials were followed by an imperial ban by the emperor and excommunication by the pope. Since even these depositions from "above" did not ultimately lead to an end to the rule, Charles V felt compelled to exert pressure on the estates to avoid a forcible deposition by military means, so that they decided to depose the archbishop from "below" at the Landtag in 1547, thus putting an end to the Cologne Reformation attempt.

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How do historians study the uprisings of 1911 in Champagne? State of Literature.

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Abstract

Today, it is rare to find remnants of the subversive events which unfolded in 1911 in the two French departments of the Marne and the Aube in the Champagne wine region (situated in the northeast of France, 130 km from Paris). The year 1911 in Champagne is usually described as a “revolution,” a “revolt,” a “riot” or even a “crisis.” However, it is also considered as a founding event of the notion of the “modern vineyard.” According to the current narratives of local territorial actors (winegrowers, politicians, professionals in the tourism, wine market and heritage sector), the events played an important role in the delimitation of the Champagne wine region in 1927. It is also considered that the events contributed to the establishment of the Interprofessional Comity of the Champagne wine in 1941 which represents the interests of winegrowers and trade houses.

Indeed, tension was at the edge of eruption among winegrowers in the Marne and the Aube. Despite the fact that the demonstrations had different objectives in the two departments, numerous shared reasons caused their discontent: the devastation caused by the phylloxera, fraud of the wine market, the delimitation process of the wine region, poverty among winegrowers and the growing emphasis for white sparkling wine at the expense of the traditional red wine. When studying these events, historians have largely analysed these social and economic factors, as well as the role played by winegrowers in the events.

The objective of this paper is, first, to outline the main features and phases of the delimitation process of the wine region from 1903 to 1927, which appeared in the media in 1911 as a synonym of a “20 years of war” period and which has contributed to the events unfolding in 1911. Second, the article will analyse the various interpretations of the events of 1911 proposed by scholars and amateur historians since 1930. The aim would be here to draw the contours of the Francophone historiography of these events. The article concludes by reconsidering the different meanings of the notions of revolution, revolt, riot and crisis, through the lens of this historiography.

Introduction

One of the particularities of the nomination file of the Champagne Hillside, Houses and Cellars UNESCO World Heritage site is its focus on the historical events occurring from the end of the nineteenth century up to the middle of the twentieth century. The narrative constructed in the nomination file puts a strong emphasis on the circumstances which lead to the establishment of an inter-professional organization between winegrowers and trade houses in 1941. Progressively, the model of this organization has multiplied, leading to a complex system of organizations, setting out a model that is adopted today worldwide.¹ One of the main factors that led to the creation of an organization system was the multiple tensions between winegrowers and trade houses especially which concerned the delimitation of the Champagne wine region. The delimitation aims to control the wine market and to protect the *appellation* against usurpation as well as to differentiate the products of the Champagne wine region from

¹ Haut Conseil de la Coopération Agricole, La filière viticole Française, (2017): 14.

other concurrent wines. The delimitation process lasted nearly 25 years, from 1903 to 1927. It was characterized by harsh debates from which a central state controversy emerged and became subject of national policy. The revolt of the winegrowers in the departments of the Marne and of the Aube in 1911 was a turning point.

Many researchers in social sciences focused on the events of 1911. Described by some as a riot, or as a revolution by others, it is also considered as a founding event of the notion of the “modern vineyard.”² A hundred years after, a local journal remembered the events of 1911 as the “revolt which laid the foundations for the most famous wine in the world”.³ However, before accepting any denomination proposed by scholars, it seems important to look at France’s political context in which the events took place. In 1905 the National Assembly approved the law on the separation of Church and State, and the French Section of the Workers' International was founded. As for the question of social unrest in the sector, protests emerged by wine growers in the Languedoc area situated in the south of France in 1907. The harsh rebellion caused the death of multiple victims, rapidly reaching regional scale, but was finally repressed by the government of Georges Clemenceau.⁴ Consequently, the media and the politicians asked questions about the rioters in Champagne. Who initiated the revolt? Was there any political idea behind the events? Was there any foreign interference aiming to manipulate the rioters? When looking at these questions, one should not forget that at the end of the French “*Belle époque*,” there were many political tensions in the French society and the enemies could have been foreigners (Germans, English, Russians), as well as fellow citizens (Socialists, Anarchists).

² Aline Brochot, “Analyse comparative des processus de construction sociale et territoriale du patrimoine dans les vignobles de Champagne et de Tokaj”, (Paris, Ministère de la Culture et de la francophonie, 1997), 109.

³ Stéphane Guerrini, “Il y a un siècle... Révoltés, les vigneron s'unissaient”, *L'Union*, (2011).

⁴ Jean Sagnes, “Le mouvement de 1907 en Languedoc-Roussillon: de la révolte viticole à la révolte régionale”, *Le Mouvement social* 104 (1978): 3.

In the first part of this article, I will describe the social and economic context of the Champagne region from 1890, in order to understand the circumstances in which the events took place in 1911. In the second part, we will discuss the delimitation process of the wine region which pays particular attention to the triggering factors of the events. Finally, in the third part, we will study how historians addressed the events of 1911 through the analysis of the relevant historiographical literature. Without trying to answer the question of whether the events in 1911 constituted a revolution, a revolt or a riot, I seek to explore why and when these events were perceived as such.

The social and economic context of the Champagne wine region from 1890 to 1911

The white sparkling wine market in Champagne was very successful in production during the second part of the nineteenth century. In 1780 more than 350.000 bottles were sold, in 1830 more than 3 million bottles, and between 1895 and 1910 the number of bottles sold reached 40 million.⁵ While white sparkling wine was traditionally produced in the abbeys and the homes of bourgeois landowners in Epernay between 1720–1730, and in Reims between 1760–1770, traders from mainly the textile industry and banking sector invested in the production and the selling of white sparkling wine at the turn of the 18th century.⁶ The industrial revolution also facilitated its development (development of transport, urbanization, progressive control of the oenological process, modernization of cellars). The production of white sparkling wine became an industrial process and the trade houses became fully-fledged industrial establishments. The mass production of champagne also required many infrastructures which were singularly visible

⁵ UNESCO nomination file of the site “Hillsides, Houses and Cellars“, Association Paysages du Champagne, (2014), 170.

⁶ UNESCO nomination file of the site “Hillsides, Houses and Cellars“, Association Paysages du Champagne, (2014), 159.

in the architecture of the trade houses and in the urban development of the towns like Reims, Épernay, Châlons-en-Champagne or Aÿ where the most trade houses were set up. It created an agro-industrial system that has profoundly marked the spatial and social organization of the Champagne region.⁷

As nearly a quarter-century passed, the wine began to deteriorate in the Gard area (situated in the south of France) because of the arrival of the phylloxera. It reached the department of the Aube in 1887.⁸ But, despite the deplorable harvest quantity, the region doubled its selling on the wine market. The trade houses purchased grapes and wine from other wine regions outside of Champagne (Anjou, Touraine, Metz etc). In consequence, it dropped the price of the grapes. The economic situation of the winegrowers worsened. This phenomenon was also remarkable in the statistics of the surface area of the vineyard. When 62.000 ha of wine area were registered in 1840, the surface area was only 49.000 ha fifty years later.⁹ The damages of the phylloxera (high expenses, uprooting vines, loss of harvest, abandonment of the work of wine growing) caused important economic and social difficulties in the region. Many winegrowers lost their revenues and impoverished. Their income depended mainly on the purchase volume of the trade houses. Besides, as mentioned before, the Champagne wine region was mainly a red wine-producing region until the end of the nineteenth century, when the production of sparkling white wine became dominant. Though, the production of white sparkling wine was more expensive for winegrowers. Thus, the overall dependence of winegrowers on the trade houses increased. Market fraud and the devastating consequences of phylloxera further increased the demand to

⁷ UNESCO nomination file of the site “Hillsides, Houses and Cellars“, Association Paysages du Champagne (2014), 173.

⁸ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, Champagne ! Histoire inattendue (Paris: Les éditions de l’Atelier), 112

⁹ UNESCO nomination file of the site “Hillsides, Houses and Cellars“, Association Paysages du Champagne (2014), 175.

establish strict regulation on wine trading, with the aim of protecting the origin of the grape variety and the production of wine with a geographical delimitation.

The delimitation process of the Champagne wine region

The Champagne wine region is situated in the northeast of France and it stretches over five departments, covering 34.000 ha: Aisne, Aube, Marne, Seine-et-Marne, Haut-Marne. The Marne and the Aube departments are the most densely covered by vineyards. This production area was defined in 1927 by the result of a delimitation process which was analysed by historians such as Claudine Wolikow and Claire Desbois-Thibault. I present the delimitation process on the basis of their research. According to them, the process can be described in three stages.¹⁰ First, the preliminary work carried out by the General Council (departmental level) of the Marne from 1903 to 1914. Second, the circumstances of the adoption of the law on the appellation (designation) in 1919 will be. And third, the finalization of the delimitation process of the Champagne wine region in 1927.

The delimitation process in the Champagne wine region was launched in 1903 by the General Council of the Marne's Department and the Champagne Wine Trade Union, created in 1882 on the initiative of the champagne trade houses like Heidsieck, Mumm and Moët. Their main objective was to protect the market of the sparkling wine which was processed in the Champagne region by forbidding the use of the name of champagne for other wine regions. The members of the Union proposed to geographically delimitate the wine region. The demand emerged from the local level, but it was actually a part of a national process that was started

¹⁰ Claire Desbois-Thibault, "La délimitation de la Champagne viticole: un processus lent et tumultueux", June 17, 2016, in *Inauguration de l'Institut Georges Chappaz de la Vigne et du Vin en Champagne* conference, video, 28: 53, <https://mediacenter.univ-reims.fr/channels/GeorgesCHAPPAZ/media/MEDIA161003084738991>.

with the approval by the National Assembly of the so-called Chaptal Act on 28 July 1894, named after the rapporteur of the text.¹¹ This law enforced the protection of the commercial name and the geographical origin of the products against alterations of names, within the framework of the protection of commercial property. Since 1820, sparkling wines were produced in Metz, Toul, Arbois under the name of champagne. Mainly trade houses initiated legal procedures against this kind of usurpation. Concerning the denomination of the Champagne region, the first restrictions were established in 1887: from this date, only the sparkling wine which was harvested and produced in Champagne was eligible to the name of “champagne” or “vin de champagne” on the bottles. The State High Court required that the perimeter of the geographical delimitation area correspond to the borders of the government of Champagne and Brie which was an administrative area of the Ancien Régime (1589-1789).¹²

Furthermore, an act repressing fraud was approved in 1905. This law allowed to begin the work on the delimitation of the area by the Council of the Marne and the Champagne Wine Trade Union. Thus, in November 1905, a first reunion was organized at the Ministry of Agriculture, with the participation of the Union and the Federation of the unions of winegrowers from the Marne, created in 1904. The members of this Federation were local anti-fraud unions which became later the Champagne growers union in 1919, setting out as a principal objective the total repression of fraud.

The delimitation proposed to cover the department of the Marne and a part of Condé-en-Brie's region. The proposition was forwarded to the State Council in June 1907, provoking the first manifestations in the department of the Aube against the proposition.¹³ The manifestations

¹¹ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 142.

¹² Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 146.

¹³ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 147.

notwithstanding, the State Council published a decree on the 17th of December 1908. The decree covered a delimitation of an area of 15.631 ha which involved the Marne department, 44 villages of the district of Château Thierry, and 36 villages of the district of Soissons.¹⁴ Aube's department was beyond the decree's scope as the image below illustrates. In this context, winegrowers in the Marne department chose to ask additional regulation to repress fraud, but in the Aube, demonstrations were growing rapidly as being excluded from the Champagne

production area and by then forbidding to produce wine under the designation of Champagne.

Image 1: Delimitation area according to the decree published on the 17th of December

¹⁴ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 146.

(Source: Claude Wolikow <https://preo.u-bourgogne.fr/territoiresduvin/index.php?id=1444>)
modified by Krisztina Albert

Indeed, a series of demonstrations took place in October 1909 in the Marne demanding additional regulation from the authorities. On the 16th of October 1910, 10.000 demonstrators gathered in Epernay. More than two months of tax resistance actions were launched. At the same time, the department of the Aube was claiming the right to be part of the Champagne wine region. On the 19th of March 1910, further demonstrations were organized in Bar-sur-Aube, regrouping more than 5.000 persons.¹⁵ Gaston Cheq, deputy mayor in the municipality of Bar-sur-Aube was one of the leaders of the manifestations in the Aube. He created the Federation of wine growers of the Aube by the establishment of central committees in Bar-sur-Aube and Bar-sur-Seine, two central towns in the Aube. However, a difference can be discerned in the composition of these committees: in Bar-sur-Aube wine growers were in minority compared to notabilities, unlike in Bar-sur-Seine the central committee was dominantly composed of wine growers compared to elected notabilities, mayors, town councils etc.¹⁶

Finally, on the 10th of February 1911, additional measures were voted by the Senate. However, these measures blocked the winegrowers who were situated in the Aube, by providing grapes or wine to the trade houses situated in the Marne. This measure was judged unfair because winegrowers from the Aube were providing wine to trade houses in the Marne since 1849.¹⁷

Afterwards, a decision increased the manifestations in the Marne: the Senate deleted the decree on the administrative delimitation on 11th of April 1911. This decision made the Marne's wine growers furious. Indeed, the winegrowers of the Marne relaunched the demonstrations because due to this decision all measures gained during their work on the delimitation since 1903 were

¹⁵ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, *Champagne ! Histoire inattendue* (Paris: Les éditions de l'Atelier), 112

¹⁶ Fabrice Perron and Yann Harlaut, *Les révoltes du champagne*, (Editions Dominique Guéniot, 2011), 53.

¹⁷ Fabrice Perron, "L'approvisionnement aubois des maisons de champagne marnaises avant 1911", *Annales de la Société Historique de Bar-sur-Aube et du pays baralbin* 1 (2018): 17.

being deleted. We can observe here how the demonstrators responded separately to the different decisions made by the Senate. Demonstrators were considered by the media as revolutionaries.¹⁸ Wine growers refused to pay taxes, and the elected representatives resigned.¹⁹ Finally, the agitations were repressed by 15.000 soldiers.²⁰ The arguments coming from the Marne against the inclusion of the Aube was referring to the issue of overproduction which could have lower prices and could have led to poor sales.²¹

Similarly, in Aube, the abolition of the decree did not calm the situation and demonstrations increased. On the 7th of June 1911, a new ministerial decree was adopted, in which the Aube department was qualified as a “second zone of Champagne”. Due to this qualification, the winegrowers of the Aube felt humiliated. On the 30th of June of 1911, the Minister of Agriculture called Jules Pams proposed a new project of law that completed the law of Chaptal by creating a protection of the *appellations d’origine* (designation of origin).²² In 1913, the process to adapt the law was interrupted because of the start of the First World War. The project was reconsidered in February 1919 and was finally adopted in May 1919. From this time, the declaration of the harvest and stock was an obligation.²³ In 1925, 6 villages in Aube acquired the appellation. In 1927, the delimitation of the Champagne wine region was reviewed, and a new delimitation area was decided with the inclusion of the villages of Aube: 272 villages of the Marne, 71 from the Aube, 51 in the department of the Aisne, 5 in the Seine-et-Marne and 2 in the Haute-Marne.²⁴

¹⁸ Gérard Munier, “La révolte marnaise 1911”, *Folklore de Champagne*, 78 (April 1982): 10

¹⁹ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, *Champagne ! Histoire inattendue* (Paris: Les éditions de l’Atelier), 148

²⁰ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, *Champagne ! Histoire inattendue* (Paris: Les éditions de l’Atelier), 148

²¹ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, *Champagne ! Histoire inattendue* (Paris: Les éditions de l’Atelier), 140

²² Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne” in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 152.

²³ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne” in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 155.

²⁴ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne” in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 158.

Bibliographic review on the events erupted in 1911 in Champagne

According to Claudine Wolikow, the history of the uprisings in 1911 is intimately linked with the history of the delimitation of the Champagne wine region. Indeed, the delimitation process exploded social and economic factors in both of the departments of the Marne and the Aube. Since 1930, the academic field and in particular social sciences studied this specific event under different perspectives. Historians with local and national approaches studied the social origins and the role played by winegrowers and political parties in the events.

Claudine Wolikow is a historian from the department of the Aube and a member of the UNESCO Chair “Culture and Traditions of Wines” at the University of Burgundy. Her research is devoted to the history of the implementation of the French certification called *appellation d’origine contrôlée*. The certification is a legal regulation of the production and commercialization of specific products such as wine and cheese. It protects the name of the products corresponding to specific geographical areas. She is studying this question in relation to the Champagne wine region between 1903-1927. Her analysis is based on parliamentary debates, decrees, laws and other legal documents. Wolikow believes that the delimitation process was launched locally as part of the national agenda that had begun in the early nineteenth century, and in particular with the adoption of the Chaptal act in 1824. She explains by several arguments the different reasons of the events in the article untitled “La delimitation de la Champagne viticole” (The delimitation of the Champagne wine region) published in 2010 in the revue of the International Institute of wines of Champagne. As for that matter, she argues, based on the archive of the local and national press, that the events of 1911 were “revolts” which transformed into “riots”²⁵. While the events in the Marne were qualified in the press as riots and

²⁵ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne” in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 147.

jacquerie at the national level, in the Aube, the events were described as pacific manifestations and symbolic violence. With regard to the explanation offered for the reasons of the events, Wolikow begins by stressing that the revolt was a reaction to the fraud that drove prices downward. Besides the fraud, the low quantity of the harvest between 1907–1910 caused mainly by the phylloxera and the bad meteorological conditions gave rise to existential uncertainty among the winegrowers. In the second place, she argues that the delimitation process played an important role in the uprising as it added to the growing tensions. Finally, she evokes that it is important to note that an opposition existed, presented further, between the two departments at the beginning of the 20th century caused by two political majorities that governed the two departmental assemblies.²⁶

Indeed, Wolikow further argues that in addition to the economic difficulties, the political context varied in each department of the Marne and of the Aube. She explains that behaviours in the department of the Marne were characterized of two major political currents: corporate solidarism and Christian socialism. On the one hand, solidarism was embodied locally by the figure of Léon Bourgeois who was supported by the majority of elected representatives and a large number of trade union leaders. On the other hand, Christian socialism was widespread among some of the directors of the champagne trade houses (for example Veuve Clicquot). Although ideologically the two branches are different, they converge in the sense that both reject the idea of class struggle and seek to promote the reconciliation of social interests. In the Aube, “guesdisme” named after the leader Jules Guesde and the founder of the French Workers' Party is reputed.²⁷ However, the figure of the events of 1911 was Gaston Cheq. He was a

²⁶ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 151.

²⁷ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 151.

socialist and the founder of the Federation of winegrowers of the Aube. He underlined the importance of “staying in union” to confront the decision of the Senate on the delimitation area.²⁸

Compared to Wolikow, Jacques Girault, a historian at the Paris-Sorbonne University and specialized in the labour movements is more critical about the role of the socialists in the events of 1911 in the Aube. Girault published an article entitled “*Le rôle du socialisme dans la révolte des vigneron de l’Aube*” (The role of socialism in the revolt of the Aube winegrowers) in 1969 in a revue entitled “*Le Mouvement social*” (The social movement). Girault is interested in the question of the degree by which the socialists influenced the events which he qualifies as a matter of fact as “movements,” “protests” and “revolts.” His article discusses the relationship between the share of the vote of socialists in the result of the local elections in wine growing and non-wine growing villages in the Aube. He analyses the percentage of winegrowers who voted for socialist elected representatives (from the French Section of the Workers’ International party), meanwhile he attempt to explicate that it is hardly possible to carry out a generalization on winegrowing villages that are more socialist than others.²⁹ Thus, in the final analysis, Girault argues that the events of 1911 were not inspired by socialist ideas. Yet, he specifies that it was actually a struggle of small property owners. Indeed, winegrowers rarely owned more than two hectares of vine that were also, in many cases, dispersed in the region.³⁰ Girault’s point is that socialists did not manage to lead the protest. He notes that the only socialist who has played a leading role as a reformer in the figure of Gaston Cheq. According to Girault, the socialists have allowed themselves to be dragged along by the radicals for solutions by proposing reforms.³¹

²⁸ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne” in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 152.

²⁹ Jacques Girault, “Le rôle du socialisme dans la révolte des vigneron de l’Aube”, *Le Mouvement social* 67 (1969): 90.

³⁰ Claire Desbois-Thibault, “La Champagne face à son histoire” *La Champagne viticole*, hors-série (2011):13.

³¹ Jacques Girault, “Le rôle du socialisme dans la révolte des vigneron de l’Aube”, *Le Mouvement social* 67 (1969): 109.

He adds that social transformations appeared in the argument of the demonstrators in a general way even if, for some, these events remain "socialist in the manner of the great Jaures."³²

In the same review, Jacqueline Saillet analyses the events in the Marne in an article titled "*Les mouvements vignerons de Champagne*" (The movements of the Champagne winegrowers). Her analysis invokes the role of the socialists, the Federation of the unions of the Marne, the anarchists and the trade houses in the events. In an absorbing introductory chapter, the author describes first the role of that Federation which was, according to her, mainly in contact with the deputies. Second, she explains, that as for the trade houses, the events turned out to be a commercial tool in their publicities to communicate the renewal of the champagne region. Three, as for the designation of the events of 1911, Saillet argues for the use of the term "social riots," as they expressed primarily a discontent of wine growers, viticultural laborers and craftsmen, with regard to unpredictable economic and social situation. Four, she concludes, as Girault, that the demonstrations were not inspired by Socialism, and its origins were not related to the vote of the Senate on the delimitation of the wine region, but rather to poverty.

The Society of the amateurs of Champagne folklore and arts, created in 1958 which pooled local amateur historians, published three special issues in their revue entitled "*Folklore de Champagne*" about the uprisings in the Aube and in the Marne. The first was published in 1979, written by Françoise Weinling. This issue of the revue addressed the events in the Aube in 1911, in particular in Bar-sur-Aube and Bar-sur-Seine. Weinling qualifies the events as "movements" and as "revolts." She describes the different striking methods used during the manifestations, such as the red flag, or the international anthem. Although she believes that these two main symbols of the socialism were not linked to political ideas but were borrowed to symbolize the

³² Jacques Girault, "Le rôle du socialisme dans la révolte des vignerons de l'Aube", *Le Mouvement social* 67 (1969): 109.

discontentment of the winegrowers and to express their opposition to the government concerning their decision on the delimitation area. She argues that the objective of the manifestations was not to change the social system, even if the question on social class appeared, but to be part of the Champagne region and thus to assure livelihoods from wine growing. Weinling points out that the idea to “stay in unity” spread by Gaston Cheq was possible because of the misery.³³

Image 2: “Bread first. Politics after.” A call to the Union of the Central Committee of Barsur-Aube ends with these terms.³⁴

The second review was published in 1981 on the events in the Marne between 1894 and 1911. The third one was published one year later and it analyzed the revolt in the Marne of the year of 1911, from January to April. The author of the two reviews was Gérard Munier, a local amateur historian. He defined the events as a “popular revolt,” and described two “revolutions”³⁵ in Champagne. The first one took place in 1894 and the second one in 1911. He

³³ Weinling Françoise, “La révolte dans le Barséquanaise, 1991. Une grande année dans le vignoble aubois“, *Folklore de Champagne* 67, (1979): 21.

³⁴ Weinling Françoise, “La révolte dans le Barséquanaise, 1991. Une grande année dans le vignoble aubois“, *Folklore de Champagne* 67, (1979): 23.

³⁵ Munier Gérard. “Les révoltes en Marne“, *Folklore de Champagne* 75, (1981):16.

argues that the discontentment of the winegrowers had already begun with the establishment of the Departmental Defence Union, created in 1891 in order to implement measures against the phylloxera. The Union was financed by the Ministry of Agriculture, the municipalities of Reims and Epernay and the Chamber of Commerce of Reims. The articles of the Union prescribed 58 members and 25 elected representatives with a director of the Union. An official list was represented by mainly trade houses, on the head M. Verrier, and an opposition list was also represented by wine growers with René Lamarre.³⁶

Despite the elected opposition list, due to the subsidies granted, the representatives of some of the trade houses (de Cazenave, Mercier, Bollinger, Chandon etc.) also became members of the Union. By then, wine growers refused to cooperate. They rejected the measures taken by the Union to treat phylloxera, because they appeared to them as imposed from above. When vineyard inspectors appeared on their property, winegrowers drove them away. René Lamarre founded a local journal called "*La Révolution Champenoise*" (The Champagne Revolution) in 1891, and initiated a protest movement in June 1892. He accused the trade houses of being the source of the misery of the wine growers: "Phylloxera isn't the only parasite in our vineyards."³⁷ The protesters demanded the abolishment of taxes for 1892, and that they be value-added (and not be defined based on the land value of the wine). However, the Union ceased its activity in 1896.

Munier considers that the revolt which took place in April 1911 was the second one. He explores the events from April to June 1911 with rich photo documentation. He argues that the events had a double aspect which created an "air of revolution."³⁸ According to Munier, political

³⁶ Munier Gérard. "Les révoltes en Marne", *Folklore de Champagne* 75, (1981): 17.

³⁷ Munier Gérard, "La révolte marnaise, 1911", *Folklore de Champagne* 78, (1982): 35

³⁸ Munier Gérard, "La révolte marnaise, 1911", *Folklore de Champagne* 78, (1982): 78.

parties did not participate in the revolt, but political ideas played a large role in it, such as reforming society, fighting misery, injustice and exploitation by putting the emphasis on trade unions and cooperatives.³⁹ He concludes that if socialists did not play an important role in the demonstrations, they nevertheless influenced the “revolution of social relations through new economic relations,” for instance by the creation of the unions and cooperatives.⁴⁰ This argument is based on evidence which shows that the objective of many winegrowers was not to change the government or the political regime, but to take action in order to bring in new regulations which could repress the fraud.⁴¹

Paul Piard, in his thesis entitled “*Des syndicats vers la corporation: L’organisation de la Champagne viticole*” (From unions to the corporation: The organization of the Champagne wine region), defended in 1937 at the Faculty of Law of Paris analyzed the legal regulations and administrative measures which have governed the production and the sales of champagne wines in the beginning of the 20th century.⁴² He studies a period of thirty years. He relates the events of 1911 to the delimitation process and the fraud. For Piard, the events can be considered as riots, rebellions, agitations and protestations. He analyzes the role and the interests of different organizations taking part in the wine commerce on a local level. According to him, it was the erroneous ideology of liberal economy, developed by certain economic theorists, that allowed the emergence of fraud.⁴³ The unions marked the first step towards the constitution of a corporation of the champagne wine producers. As a result, the components of this corporation were based on three levels: on the basis are the traders' and winegrowers' unions; above them,

³⁹ Munier Gérard. “Les révoltes en Marne“, *Folklore de Champagne* 75, (1981): 15.

⁴⁰ Munier Gérard, “La révolte marnaise“, 1911, *Folklore de Champagne* 78, (1982): 54.

⁴¹ Munier Gérard, “La révolte marnaise“, 1911, *Folklore de Champagne* 78, (1982): 41.

⁴² Paul Piard, “*Des syndicats vers la corporation: L’organisation de la Champagne viticole*“, (Université de Paris – Faculté de droit, 1937), 12.

⁴³ Paul Piard, “*Des syndicats vers la corporation: L’organisation de la Champagne viticole*“, (Université de Paris – Faculté de droit, 1937), 290.

there is a special commission for champagne wines; and a national committee is situated on the top for controlled designations of origin. Piard concludes that even if individual interests motivated the local actors until the beginning of the 20th century, finally a common organization system had been set up representing the collective interests of wine growers and trade houses.

Hereafter, we can conclude that the events of 1911 were widely studied by historians in different formats: scientific and critical articles, thesis, local reviews. Furthermore, we can mention entire books which were dedicated to the subject, for example, one published in 2011 by Dominique Fradet entitled “*1911 en Champagne, Chronique d’une révolution*” (1911 in Champagne, Chronicle of a revolution) which adopts the tone of a novel as it narrates the events from October 1910 to November 1911 in the Aube and the Marne. Another two books, marking the centenary of the events, were published as well. One, entitled “*Les révoltes du champagne*” (Champagne revolts), written by Yann Harlaut and Fabrice Perron and the second entitled “*Champagne! Histoire inattendue*” (*Champagne! Unexpected history!*) by Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow. The authors of the first book are historians at the Reims Champagne-Ardenne University. Their book provides a narrative of the uprisings, from the arrival of the phylloxera, through the manifestations against the fraud and the delimitation process. Regarding its format, the book is close to an album with rich photo archive illustrations. The second book of Wolikow’s presents a global history of the Champagne wine region from the start of the production of white sparkling wine dating back to the XVII century until nowadays. The various interpretations presented above show the different formats and styles adopted to narrate the events of 1911 in Champagne. Beyond the characteristics concerning the style and format of the publications, we can also observe that different terms are used to qualify the events, such as riot, revolt, revolution or crisis. The textual approach draws attention to the lack of the definition of these terms, which appears rather to express an upheaval and unforeseen

change or fight. Thus, we can argue that the notion of revolution or revolt is a flexible idea that can be adapted to a wide variety of contexts. It supposes a constantly changing definition of the concept of revolution since the seventeenth and the twentieth centuries.⁴⁴ The examination of the different research (legislative, political, sociological, economic) carried out by historians allows to compare the various interpretations of the events. The research proposes a broader and more nuanced understanding of the society of viticulture in the end of the nineteenth and the beginning of the twentieth century in France and in particular in Champagne. If authors like Claudine Wolikow or Desbois-Thibault closely connected the unfolding events to the delimitation process, others, like Girault or Saillet highlighted the fact that the main factor of the eruption of the events was the misery of the winegrowers. Based on the analysis of Piard and Meunier, the events contributed to the development of numerous trade unions.

Nevertheless, the subject of the delimitation process was present in all of the analysis carried out by the authors. In the Aube, the first manifestations appeared after the decision of the Senate in 1908 excluding the department from the Champagne production area. In the Marne, the fraud and the economic uncertainty followed by the phylloxera provoked the first manifestations. The demonstrations raised the question of poverty in both of the regions. The initiation of the delimitation process by trade houses in the Marne appeared as a tool to regulate the wine market and to propose a legal economic frame for the production of sparkling white wine. The impact of the events overpassed the delimitation issue on the local level, and it became a subject on a national level. In 1935, the National Institute of the Designation of Origin has been created with the *appellation d'origine contrôlée* certification. The harsh tensions between trade houses and winegrowers increased the demand to establish a strict organization in the wine market. This

⁴⁴ Rachel Hammersley, "Introduction", *Revolutionary moments, Reading revolutionary texts*, (Bloomsbury Academic, (2015).

organization was created in 1941: Interprofessional Comity of the Champagne, representing the interests of winegrowers and trade houses. This inter-professional organization in Champagne became a model and has subsequently been adopted in other wine regions, such as Burgundy, Bordeaux, Languedoc etc.

Conclusion

This article attempted to present the events which took place in 1911 in two different administrative areas: the departments of the Marne and the Aube, situated in the Champagne wine region. In the first part of the article, we described the social and economic context of the Champagne region from the end of the nineteenth century until the beginning of the 20th century. In the second part, we presented the legal history of the delimitation process of the wine region which was connected by some historians as one of the main reasons of the events, beyond the consequences of the phylloxera and the prevailing misery of social conditions. We also reconstructed the demonstrations that responded to the delimitation process. Finally, in the third part, we proposed an analysis of how historians and amateur ones interpreted the events of 1911. The range of texts examined is deliberately broad which gives particular attention to the sequence of events. It also shows that in the majority, local historians (from the Aube and the Marne) studied the triggering factors and circumstances of the events, by calling it a revolution, revolt or riot inspired by headlined of local journals to show mainly the upheaval of the events.

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A trapped generation: Letters from Sent-down Youth in the Chinese Cultural Revolution (1966-67)¹

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Abstract

In the wake of 1960s student movements all around the globe, Chinese youth initiated a country-wide revolution against the “capitalist” elements in the ruling communist party and in Chinese culture. In 1968, as the movement caused massive chaos in the country, Chairman Mao Zedong called for the youth to resettle in rural area in China to restore the order in cities. This is referred to as the “Up to the Mountains and Down to the Countryside Movement,” of “educated youth,” who graduated from middle schools or high schools. Estimated 17 millions of young people went to the rural villages, border areas, military farms, and outskirts of cities during the sent-down movement which formed a special generation of mass displacement.

It is acknowledged by many, though certainly not all, historians that these youth suffered severely under hard labour, food shortage, and separation with families, etc. While historical research on the educated youth is expanding their depth and scope, many are based on secondary sources, fictions, and official reports, which are further away from the real fabric of the lives of the sent-down youth. Thus, this article aims to diversify the sources of historical evidence by adding private letters to the discussion. During the movement, letters were the main way for rusticated youths to communicate with their friends and families, and loved ones. Letter writing became a ritual-like routine that allowed spontaneous and intimate expression of emotions and thoughts, which were often not found in official documents and

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newspapers. Unlike memoirs and scar literature, it provides a perceptive that is undistorted by hindsight. This article carefully examines a collection of letters written by an individual male sent-down youth during 1968-75 as a case study. Through his account of the ups and downs in a farm, his laughter and tears, his hard labour in the field and his romantic encounters, this article produces a historical-analytical bottom-up narrative. With the lens of social and cultural history, I would trace the movements of the sent-down students and their change in emotions and beliefs throughout the period.

Upon in-depth analysis, one finds that it was possible for educated youth to spend their first flush of adulthood in farms living a life that solely depended on the Party ideology in their behavior and mentality. The letters are full of down-to-earth details in daily-life, that one perhaps find the educated youth not as distant to us as we thought. They remind us that another vast dislocation project with tragic consequences is not impossible and unacceptable under the regime of the CPC (Communist Party of China) with ordinary teenagers who can engage in state mobilizations without a thought on its shortcomings and dangers. It is important for us contemporaries to understand the sent-down generation as they were, so as to reflect on the nature, impact, and replicability of the massive rustication project.

Introduction

A typical day for an educated youth, Wang Shu, in China in the 1970s during the send-down movement consisted of mowing in the field, dragging political meetings and five hours of sleep. For us contemporaries, his days seem to be harsh and daunting. Many of his fellows, in later first-person narrations, voiced their boredom, sufferings, and traumas in the years in the rural area. But what did Wang think about it? The youth actually found it delightful and rewarding! To the perplexity of many, how did Wang, a member of the “lost generation” (*shiluo de yidai*) going through rustication,² act out the meaning of his life in the remote youth military farm with satisfaction and self-motivation?

The “lost generation” is also identified as the “educated youth” (*zhishi qingnian* or *zhiqing* in short), are students who were in or graduated from elementary, middle, or high school and were sent to the countryside under the campaign of *Up to Mountain Down to Countryside Movement* (*shangshan xiaxiang*, also translated as the sent-down campaign) in 1968, two years after the beginning of the Cultural Revolution. Before 1968, the targets of the sent-down program were mainly jobless city dwellers. In this period, approximately one million individuals were sent down.³ Amid the frenzy of the Cultural Revolution and the Red Guard movement in 1968, the Maoist leadership had to deal with the troubles caused by the Red Guards. As the radical and anarchical Red Guards stormed administrations and institutions, the Party leaders realized the necessity of restoring social order and production efficiency, through channelling their idealism and activism to elsewhere – the countryside. Subsequently, since 1968, relocation to the countryside was compulsory for urban youths who had finished schooling. The campaign soon

² For the terminology, see Michel Bonnin, “The “Lost Generation”: Its Definition and Its Role in Today's Chinese Elite Politics,” *China in Transition* 73 (Spring 2006): 249.

³ Thomas P. Bernstein, *Up to the Mountains and Down to the Villages: the Transfer of Youth from Urban to Rural China*, (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1977), 24.

became coercive, as there was resistance to it when the reality of rural lives was exposed in the cities. Between 1968 and 1980, about 17 million Chinese urban youth, accounting for about one-third of the population in the age group, were rusticated, and many stayed there for more than 10 years.⁴ It became a massive relocation project of youth from areas with a higher living standard to the areas with a lower one, from the industrialized to the nature-dominant environment. The CCP leaders aimed to, via population relocation, solve urban unemployment, restore social orders, reprogram the education system, and modernize the rural areas and frontiers.

The pivotal, lasting impact on the sent-down generation received both modern Chinese and international scholars' attention. Aside from the typical approach of analysing the Sent-down movement based on top-down politics, a careful look on at individuals' lives also helps to recast the meaning and lessons of the Cultural Revolution. In this essay, I am trying to write a history "from below" of the sent-down movement based on a collection of private letters the educated youth sent to his family. These letters by a young male, Wang Shu, reflect the inner world of the educated youth in first-person narrative with a combination of subjective expression and objective observation. The letters may provide insights into the rustication program from a micro-perspective and complement mainstream historical narratives.

In China, the Up to the Mountain and Down to the Countryside movement has been a sensitive topic. The state has been trying to avoid accusations about the coercive nature of the movement and their responsibility for the sufferings the youth faced thereat. Therefore, there has been

⁴ Liu Xiaomen, *Zhongguo zhiqingshi: Dachao* 中國知青史：大潮 (1953–1968) [History of *Zhiqing* in China: the spring tide (1966–1980)] (Beijing: China Social Sciences Press, 1998), 863.

limited discussion on the topic in Chinese academia, and researchers have heavily relied on official propaganda as evidence.⁵

Outside the country, foreign scholars have also expressed interest in the topic. Like many historical investigations in the initial stage, a top-down approach was first used, focusing on Mao's motivation for launching the rustication.⁶ Historians later turned more to the sufferings of the youth in the countryside with a bottom-up approach with the increasing availability of autobiographies and other sources in English and the growing community of Chinese diaspora.⁷ The so-called "scar literature" (*shanghen wenxu*) and educated youth literature (*zhiqing wenxue*) became a publishing phenomenon and the major sources of reference on the topic.⁸ They illustrate the cruelty of the sent down movement in the Cultural Revolution, and provide historians with an alternative source outside the party's statement.

However, reliance on "scar literature," autobiographies and memoirs as sources prompted other problems. For one, they have been often referenced in the main text without the specification of their fictional character.⁹ In many of the historians' work on the sent-down movement, their

⁵ Chen Yi, Fan Ziying, Gu Xiaomin, Zhou LiAn, "Arrival of Young Talent: The Send-Down Movement and Rural Education in China," *American Economic Review* 110.11 (2020): 3393-3430.

Gu H. ed., *Zhongguo Zhishi Qingnian Shangshan Xiaxiang Chimo* 中國知識青年上山下鄉始末 [The whole story of *Zhiqing* UMD in China], (Beijing: China Procuratorial Press, 1997).

⁶ For example, Stuart R Schram ed., *Authority, Participation and Cultural Change in China: Essays by a European Study Group*, (Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1973).

Gordon D. White, "The politics of hsia-hsiang youth," *China Quarter*, (1974): 491.

⁷ Michel Bonnin and Horko Krystyna, *The lost generation: The rustication of China's educated youth (1968–1980)*, (Shatin: The Chinese University of Hong Kong Press, 2013).

⁸ Ou Nianzhong and Liang Yongkang ed., Laura Maynard trans., *Mao's Lost Children: Stories of the Rusticated Youth of China's Cultural Revolution*, (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2015).

Pan Yihong, *Tempered in the Revolutionary Furnace: China's Youth in the Rustication Movement*, (Lanham, Md.: Lexington, 2002).

⁹ Judith Shapiro, *Mao's war against nature: Politics and the environment in revolutionary China*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001.)

analytical distinction of fictional sources from the non-fictional ones has been obscure. Since they provide plausible accounts and explanations, they seduce readers to take them as reliable history. As a result, the literary devices and imaginary scenes from those fictions have exaggerated or distorted the actual historical incident, and historians accordingly have constructed a narrative further away from historicity. Aside from fiction, memoirs are employed by many historians without being cautious of the bias of the source. Memoirs are flawed with human memories that are largely influenced by hindsight social collective construction and imposition, in addition to the natural memory lost.¹⁰ Especially in the People's Republic of China (PRC), where the government actively propagandized and pressed one prominent dominative official narrative on the public, recollection is even further from the historic truth. In these personal narratives, what happened on the ground is hard to distinguish from self-justification and victimization. The former educated youth often fit their accounts into two opposing frames –glorification and victimization.¹¹ On the one hand, they exhibited nostalgia for the freedom and achievements in the rural area, largely as a resistance against the rapid socio-economic shift in China since the 1990s. On the other hand, the narrators portrayed themselves as victims of the sent-down movement by emphasizing their sufferings and misfortunes, and labelling the days spent in the rural areas as “the lost years.” While many historians are aware of the limitations of relying on fiction and memoirs in reconstructing a more truthful rustication process, they cannot assemble their research in other ways due to the lack of diversity of sources. With the censorship of non-official publications, the sensitivity of

¹⁰ For more on the role of memoirs, and the memory in general, see: ”Xu Zidong, *Weile wangque de jiti jiyi: jiedu 50 pian wenge xiaoshuo* 為了忘卻的集體記憶：解讀五十篇文革小說 [For the forgotten collective memory: an analysis of 50 samples of Cultural Revolution fiction] (Beijing: Sanlian shudian, 2000).

Peter Zarrow, “Meanings of China’s Cultural Revolution: memoirs of exile,” *Positions* 7, 1(1999): 165-191.

¹¹ Michel Bonnin, “Restricted, distorted but alive: The memory of the “lost generation” of Chinese educated youth,” *The China Quarterly* 227 (2016): 752-772.

Jiang Yarong and David Ashley, *Mao's children in the new China: voices from the Red Guard generation* (London: Psychology Press, 2000).

the subject, and limited access to archives, historians on the Cultural Revolution are in a disadvantageous position in collecting sources compared to their colleagues on other topics.

To write a history less confined by hindsight, presentism, self-interest, and memory flaws, historians may consider using private letters as evidence. As primary sources, they expand our knowledge on a historical topic with its random, arbitrary and spontaneous expressions. It bears less burden of judgement as a non-retrospective narration and does not illustrate a planned story plot. As a first-hand non-anonymous source, it dates the events and narrates them when memories are fresh, emotions linger. It represents less of a collective consensus of a historical event, but a more personal take on and candid picture of the era.

Letters are a particularly helpful source for history research around the Cultural Revolution, as they are less infiltrated with official dogmas. In an era where the authorities stressed collectivism and the denial of self, these personal accounts show individuality amid the repression of personal life.¹² Under intense state surveillance and censorship, diaries were even written as showpieces. But letters were less subjected to official inspection, as processing a huge number of letters was troublesome and timely, and it was hard to seal the envelope after opening them.¹³ Thus, the letter-writers tend to express more private and socially or legally forbidden thoughts. In the countryside, letter writing and reading became a habit, a sacred ritual

¹² Bonnin, "Restricted, Distorted but Alive," 755-756.

¹³ This is not to say that letters from and to the sent-down youth were not subject to inspection. There was certainly no respect for individual privacy –the officials could open any letters or packages they found suspicious. But based on the multiple collections of letters I have read, either published or posted on online anonymously, those letters contained more or less some forbidden or politically incorrect messages, thus implying the letter-writers mostly did not expect their letters to be seen by third party. In a letter from a sent-down cadre, the letter-writer said he "doesn't need to think about what kind of words I should use" when he was writing to his wife. See bibliography for other collections of letters.

that many educated youth were committed to regularly. It was a moment to connect with their loved ones, as well as a medium for individual expression and reflection¹⁴

While letters do serve the personal interest of the writers, who undoubtedly conceal some facts while exaggerating others, it is the subjectivity that matters here. It does not always authentically reflect historical moments, but instead values, attitudes, beliefs, feelings of the participants of the historical moments, which will be more valuable when reinforced with other readings. A close reading of an individual case does not produce a comprehensive historical narrative, nor does it spill out all cause-and-effect of the historical event, but it provides valuable insights and emotional dimensions of individuals. This letter collection particularly has a wider importance in the research of educated youth, for it seems to be a rare survival of its kind, and likely the story of Wang and his parents' response are not unique. The value of Wang's letters lays in their richness in the information of his inner world and feelings.

Wang Shu: a “living Lei Feng”?

I acquired Wang Shu's letters on a Chinese second-hand books trading platform. Among the countless items of letters and writings of the educated youth of different qualities, I found Wang's collection to be the most comprehensive and legible. His letters, written between 1968 and 1975, address his parents.

¹⁴ Yang Guobin, *The Red Guard Generation and Political Activism in China*, (New York: Columbia University Press, 2016,) 120-124.

According to his letters,¹⁵ the young fellow was born on November 2, 1948, one year before the Communist Party took over the whole country and established its regime. Twenty years later, Wang became one of the millions of educated youths who were exiled to the countryside in 1968. His more-than-common given name, *Shu*, which means tree, also designated his character - lively and sturdily. From a family of six in Harbin, Heilongjiang, Wang was the opposite of a stereotypical buff and assertive North-eastern Chinese. The skinny young man with a self-disciplined, polite, and versatile personality, wore a pair of glasses and a watch. From his writings that have barely any literary errors, one can easily see that he was very well educated. Wang left his home city to the Greater Khingan Range (or Da Hinggan Range) in Inner Mongolia, the most northern part of China, while his elder sister and younger brother were also sent to different parts of the country for labour. Wang's father – a serious, stern man – was a cadre and was occasionally sent to different places to work, leaving his frail mother and younger sister at home. Wang wrote down his day-to-day life on those A4 single-lined, grid or plain white papers in neat handwriting with an ink pen, addressed to his beloved family. He always greeted his parents with enthusiasm in the beginning, and signed and dated the letters at the bottom of the papers.

Wang's experience in the rural area is not a particularly exciting one. Unlike many best-selling educated youth fictions or memoirs, Wang's writings recorded no rebellions, no killing, no sneaky underground activities. Of course, it does not mean that he did not witness any, nor those did not happen. It is in fact the opposite – historians now have more evidence of how realities of the rustication differed from the official portrayal – idyllic countryside where educated youth

¹⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu [Little Shu's family letters]. Acquired on January, 2020 through Kongfuzi jiushuwang, <https://www.kongfz.com/>. There are 64 letters in the collection, all in good condition. The letters were all written in simplified Chinese. They are two to three pages long. They are usually signed with the date, but some just with the month or the year. Two short letters come without any indication of date.

worked hand-in-hand with peasants and learned from each other.¹⁶ For one, the youth encountered immense difficulties, ranging from the lack of food, poor living conditions, sickness, unbearable labour, to isolation, conflicts with local peasants, and sexual assaults.¹⁷ Many memoirs recorded the lingering traumas. For another, underground literature, music, and art flourished when the youth first experienced freedom outside the tight supervision of state organizations in the cities.¹⁸ Some copied Russian literature by hand, while some assembled their own radios. It is beyond doubt that the experience of the sent-down youth varied greatly and mostly did not conform with official intentions and narratives.

It is under this historical context that Wang's experience became interesting – interestingly boring. He fits comfortably into the state narrative of an ideal educated youth – passionate about revolutions and political education, very hardworking, devoting the heart and soul to national modernization. Wang saw himself, just as Mao would have wanted, as a revolutionary successor.

Wang's generation grew up in the “New China,” in which they received political socialization and education that centred around the glorification of Mao, loyalty to the Party, and patriotism.¹⁹ A major education method was propagating “heroic models” (*yingmo*). The state constructed these model soldiers, model workers, model peasants and model youth to be celebrities, and their accomplishments and qualities served as the ideological and moral guidance for the

¹⁶ Bonnin and Horko, *The Lost Generation*, 453.

¹⁷ “Material Difficulties and Low Morale” in Bonnin and Horko, *The Lost Generation*, 235-326.

¹⁸ “The Second Society,” in Frank Dikötter, *The Cultural Revolution: A People's History, 1962–1976*, (Bloomsbury Publishing USA, 2016), 285-300.

¹⁹ Chen Yixin, “Lost in revolution and reform: The socioeconomic pains of China's red guards generation, 1966–1996,” *Journal of Contemporary China* 8.21 (1999): 222.

nation.²⁰ Articles in the *People's Daily*, movies, posters, exhibitions, songs, in addition to work-unit study sessions and school text tasks, were created around them. Among the heroic models, Lei Feng (1940-1962) has been the most widely known figure since the 1960s till the present day. His diary was published and became a must-have for every household.²¹ Most young people in the Red Guard generation accepted the Lei Feng spirit without question at an early age.²² Lei Feng, a PLA soldier who died protecting the public properties in 1962, was hugely publicized by the state since 1963 as a human embodiment of the ideal youth under Mao. He was selfless, loyal to Mao, modest, and dedicated. His aspiration, written in his diary, was to be “nothing more than a small but essential screw in the collective engine of the revolution.”²³ “Learning from Lei Feng” campaigns both before and during the Cultural Revolution produced a political mythology that preached practising basic good deeds and absolute devotion to Mao.²⁴ In localities, “living Lei Fengs” and “active elements of learning from Lei Feng” were selected to award those who were idealistic socialists, and some outstanding ones were publicized as local models through their speeches, publications, movies, and operas. Following Lei Feng, Ouyang Hai (1940-1963) and Wang Jie (1942-1965) were popular military models and subjects of many political education campaigns. They and many more local variations shared in a common loyalty to the Party and willingness to risk their lives for the public good but not for personal gains.

²⁰ Louise Edwards, “Military celebrity in China: the evolution of “heroic and model servicemen,” in Louise Edwards and Elaine Jeffreys ed., *Celebrity in China*, (Pokfulam: Hong Kong University Press, 2010): 21- 43.

²¹ Gay Garland Reed, *The Lei Feng phenomenon in the PRC*, (Virginia: University of Virginia, 1991), 16.

²² Reed, *The Lei Feng phenomenon in the PRC*, 16.

²³ Mary Sheridan, ‘The Emulation of Heroes,’ *The China Quarterly* 33 (1968): 15.

²⁴ Elaine Jeffreys, “Modern China’s Idols: Heroes, Role Models, Stars and Celebrities,” *Journal of Multidisciplinary International Studies* 9.1 (January 2012): 11.

It is evident in the letters that Wang Shu envisioned himself as a “living Lei Feng.” Wang explicitly swore to be “a screw that never rusts.” Wang understood the Lei Feng spirit comprehensively – it was not only about altruism and hard-working, but also obedience and anonymity. According to Lei Feng, “it is only by the many, many interconnected and fixed screws that the machine can move freely, increasing its enormous work power. Though a screw is small, its use is beyond estimation.”²⁵ Aspiring to be the screw in the machine for the Maoist revolution, Wang understood his “sent-down” life as an essential part of the formidable nation-building project.²⁶ Wang thought of the movement, not from his personal perspective and his gains and losses, but the nation’s and the Party’s perspectives. He was attempting to be selfless, and only thought about the “public matter” but not the “personal matter.” While many of his fellow educated youth found their repetitive labour meaningless and unbearably boring sooner or later, Wang had been fuelled with enthusiasm for physical labour and political activities for years. He took pride in his hard work, which was rewarded by his slow but steady promotions. For most of the time, Wang had no trouble abiding orders and went wherever his superiors sent him and did the tasks assigned to him. He did not question the effectiveness or the genuine impact of the tasks. Wang staged himself as a dedicated teenager, instead of a victim of coercive dislocation and harsh labour, contrasting with many memoirs, which painted miserable and wasted years. His letters allow us to imagine: How and why did adolescents like Wang Shu try to live like the national hero, Lei Feng?

²⁵ Lei Feng, *Lei Feng Riji Shiwenxuan* [Lei Feng’s selected daires and poems] (Beijing: Zhanshi Publishing House, 1982), 77.

²⁶ Wang, Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu.

The “sent-down” years

“Ever-lasting loyalty to Chairman Mao!” is how the first letter in the collection starts, on 25th October, 1968. Settling in Harbin Youth Farm did not seem to trouble or shock Wang. It is partly because a military farm had the best material conditions, compared to working in a village production team.²⁷ Wang got a cotton uniform and a military flurry hat, preparing for the freezing cold in the winter. He was soon occupied with the labour in the horse unit till 1969.

Time slipped by on the farm. The third letter was written on January 2, 1970, when he had just gotten back from visiting his family. By then Wang was hustling in the cooking unit, preparing for the new year celebrations. In the festive time, he learned how to make steam buns and enjoyed the special new year feast with beef dumplings. The son playfully signed his letter with a cute little icon of a tree.

When he was not cooking, Wang and his unit volunteered to dig tunnels for military usage. During the Cultural Revolution, China had split with the Soviet Union and a war between the two communist countries became more and more plausible. To defend against the communist giant equipped with nuclear weapons and missiles, the Chinese state mobilized the people to dig underground tunnels and burrows.²⁸ When students and workers alike finished their day-time duties, they spent night after night digging holes, removing dirt, and stacking bricks. In the border area, the anxiety for Sino-Soviet conflicts resulted in an ante-bellum state. Unfortunately, Wang’s enthusiasm was met with great difficulties posed by the breezing weather and frozen soil in the coldest part of China. Worse still, the cadres of his company were

²⁷ Yang, *The Red Guard Generation and Political Activism in China*, 104.

²⁸ Michael S. Gerson, *The Sino-Soviet Border Conflict Deterrence, Escalation, and the Threat of Nuclear War in 1969*, (USA: Centre for Naval Analyses, November 2010): 40-41.

not supportive towards their attempt. Yet, Wang and his comrades were prepared to move them with their relentless, overnight digging. “We are not afraid of the sky and the soil! Every dig we made is a bullet shooting at the Soviet revisionists!” The immense eagerness for fighting against the revisionists was still flowing in the blood of educated youth, at least in this company.

In the freezing March, Wang’s duty shifted to pasturing horses overnight, as he was sent back to the horse unit. In addition, his company was responsible for artistic performances in regiment meetings. Wang modestly mocked his own lack of artistic talent and experience, and thus he was content to act as a minor character.

The opera they performed was not the eight model operas, as ubiquitous as they were in the Cultural Revolution, but an opera that was written by their regiment. “Ode of Jin Xuehe” was a short opera celebrating Jin Xuehe, a male educated youth from Harbin also exiled to Wang’s regiment. On a rainy morning in May of 1969, some big wood trunks slipped from a car trunk accidentally.²⁹ In this critical moment, Jin used his body to block the trunks from falling onto the other six educated youths in front of the car. The heavy trunks hit his chest, and blood spilt from Jin’s mouth – he died immediately. Like other Chinese who self-sacrificed their life for their comrades, Jing was heroized, reported on local news and was promoted as a model soldier in the regiment. Jin was only one among many of the state-endorsed local variations of Lei Feng, who shared a similar ordinary background, did good deeds in their everyday lives, and

²⁹ Jia Hongtu, “Zhiqing gushi: Jin Xuehe sheji jui ren dao zai chun yu li” 知青故事：金學和捨己救人倒在春雨里 [The story of the educated youth: Jin Xuehe sacrificed himself to save others and died in the rain in the spring], (4 March, 2019) Accessed through <https://kknews.cc/zh-hk/story/mplpegg.html> (Please see Chicago Style manual on how you should cite digital works).

Jia Hongtu, *Qingchuan 1968* 青春1968 [Youth 1968], (Beijing: Zuo jia Chubanshe 2015), 22-27.

died heroically for the people and the Party. They were shaped by the state propaganda machines to be idols and role models for everyone in the country.³⁰

As an adolescent who grew up under the state-dominated socialization and education, it is no surprise that Wang internalized the official glorification of Jin's death. Wang did not grieve for Jin's death, nor felt angry about the man-made tragedy. Instead, he felt educated and inspired by the deceased. When he performed in the opera and praised Jin, Wang learned from and immortalized him. "Every time we act," Wang wrote, "it's like Jin Xuehe standing next to me like it used to, tapping my shoulder and leading me to progress!"³¹ In his words, the tragedy of Jin was an act of heroism, which he greatly admired.

The death of Jin perhaps fueled Wang's aspiration to be a "living Lei Feng". Ordinary youth in normal circumstances could not imagine emulating any god-like heroes. But when they were put in military production farms, got their soldier uniforms, and dug tunnels to defend against the Soviets, they were one step closer to becoming a military model. Additionally, the ones who had been chosen to be public heroes were once ordinary people, just like them, and what they did were achievable by these ordinary youth in the rural area as long as they were altruistic and not afraid to sacrifice themselves. The publicity machinery evaluated those "just-like-you-and-me" individuals into national models, and there was no reason for Wang Shu not wanting to become a local celebrity when he definitely had the chance to become one and saw his comrade – Jin Xuehe – already made to be one.

³⁰ Mary Sheridan, 'The Emulation of Heroes,' 47.

³¹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. March, 1970.

Looking up to all the heroic models, Wang also actively participated in all kinds of political activities and campaigns. He read and reread Mao's "The Three Classical Pieces" (*Laosanpian*) – and this was just one of his many rituals of worshipping Mao. He enthusiastically accepted the Party's indoctrination on having the correct "class stance" and stood firm to his class position. In May 1970, there was an education program against indecency in Wang's regiment, in which educated youth were evaluated by the local authorities. The program did not affect Wang personally, whose father was just pronounced as a "five-good cadre" (*wuhao ganbu*). But he was glad that the ones with "class issues" were banned from the construction project for national defence.

In the torrid heat of July of the same year, Wang for the first time complained about the food in the camp. As the rations of wheat were not sent to the regiment this year, all he could have were mix-grain steamed buns (*mantou*), which were so hard to swallow. However, Wang's complaint did not last for a few lines – he was quick in comforting himself and his parents passionately that the bitterness he was experiencing was nothing compared to that of the Red Army. "The Red Army climbed through snowy mountains and lived arduously, isn't our experience incomparable? We will do anything, and will put more effort in completing even harder tasks for the sake of revolution!"³²

Wang was as self-reassuring as before even when his tasks got tougher. In mid-summer, his assignment changed from feeding horses overnight to mowing in the field along with thirty youths in his company. Unfortunately, it did not start well – on the first day, as they were setting up the tents, there was a rainstorm. The rain lingered for days, hindering their labour progress.

³² Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. July, 1970.

Surprisingly, Wang thought that it was the most fruitful time by far in his life, and described the days of heavy labour as delightful. While his work was mostly monotonous, he never once complained about it. It is not because the labour wasn't high intensity enough, but it is because Wang believed that the nation needs his tasks for economic development and military defence, as the "revolutionary machine" cannot run without every "screw." His satisfaction and sense of validity were based on his perception of the contributions he made to the revolutionary progress of the nation. Thus, the tougher the working process was, the more self-fulfilling he was, regardless of the actual result of his tasks.

Wang's physical burden was heavier when there was a major transferal of educated youth in the camp. More than 400 people were transferred to another farm in the region due to an insufficient food supply. There were too many people, too few lands, and the transportation was inconvenient. There were only eight hundred people left in the camp with no newcomer in the year. Although his work became more intense than ever, Wang kept his optimistic tone and faith in the Party – "the future of the camp is promising!"³³

After the season of mowing, Wang devoted himself to the equally tiresome task of harvesting wheat. The workload was so heavy that no one was allowed to take leave to visit home. While time was tight for harvesting, Wang, unfortunately, got acute stomach flu. But Wang assured his parents, "My body is still very healthy! I recovered!" The youth always convinced himself that he is healthy, and disregarded any physical discomfort. This is a product of the state evocation: Mao's words and thoughts can transcend and overcome all weaknesses of physical bodies. Selfless socialist heroic characters whom Wang tried to live up to take no notice of the

³³ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. August 5, 1970.

feeling of pain. But perhaps more so than his words, Wang's torn tank top, pants and shoes were more accurate reflections of the harshness of labour.

Amid the strenuous production activities in August, Wang wrote an unusual letter to home. He mentioned his thoughts on romantic relationships for the first time. He led into the topic very indirectly:

Recently, I am thinking about how to contribute my life to the revolution, and I should not start thinking about personal matters too early. No matter how significant personal matters are, they are unimportant; no matter how minor the national and revolutionary matters are, they are important. There are some things that I have never told you about. There was a time when I was determined to never consider personal matters. But recently I got some new thoughts, though I am holding the same basic principles. Some topics are hard to talk about... Mom, please don't worry, I will not make mistake in this aspect."³⁴

The timid son circled around the topic, feeling anxious to disclose any details to his parents. This euphemism is even more evident when Wang spoke of a "minor incident" to his parents – some of his fellows joked about him and a girl. The female educated youth was working in the medical unit after she and Wang had worked together in the propaganda unit for a while. Wang nervously clarified that those rumours were untrue, and he did not think about the matter at all. "I did not take it seriously. I thought I was too young, and should not think about this. Please believe me!"³⁵ He was really trying to convince his parents, and perhaps himself, that he would not start a romantic relationship. But then, why would he mention the affair at all if he was not hinting something to them? At the age of 21, with no previous experience in romance, and no one to talk to around him who would not gossip about it, he seems to be testing out their attitude and subtly seeking their advice. His indirectness was understandable, not only due to his timid

³⁴ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. August, 1970.

³⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. August, 1970.

personality, but also the intrinsic risk of any romantic liaisons. Wang felt inappropriate to put any thoughts on romance – as his generation was educated to love the ‘public’ (*gong*, proletarian) and oppose the ‘private’ (*shi*, personal or capitalism) matters, and being selfish could be a crime. Wang was politically correct that romance was a “personal matter,” which one should prioritize after the “public good.”³⁶ On top of that, having any intimate relations with the opposite sex was considered indecent and a moral stain.³⁷ In his published diary, for example, Lei Feng likewise denied any romantic relations with females.³⁸ Wang tried to show his parents that he was not intimidated by the gossip, as “there is nothing of such sort (of romance), what should I be afraid of?”³⁹ His rhetorical question later got a genuine answer.

Oddly, in September of the same year, the usually energetic Wang was feeling miserable: “Today I am feeling terrible.”⁴⁰ He started his letter after the habitual heading of “Ever-lasting loyalty to the great leader Chairman Mao.” The day before, he fell on a harrow and had a very deep cut on his right hand. He rushed to the hospital and got three stitches. The next day, the doctor told the injured that his wound was infected and gave him an injection. The pain-stricken Wang used his right hand to write slowly and awkwardly, inking the papers with almost illegible Chinese characters. What upset him, even more, was the departure of his close friend, Feng Qingguang, from the farm. Feng’s parents were old cadres and recently retired, so Feng accompanied them to go back to their hometown. The Hubei-originated youth left in a hurry, leaving no time to say goodbye to Wang, who was still out in the grass field. Wang felt disconsolate: “There were fewer and fewer people on the farm, my comrades left one by one, I

³⁶ Yang, 107.

³⁷ Emily Honig, "Socialist sex: The cultural revolution revisited," *Modern China* 29.2 (2003): 143-175.

³⁸ Tian Xiaofei. "The Making of a Hero.: Lei Feng and Some Issues of Historiography." *The People's Republic of China at 60*, (Brill, 2011), 304.

Bonnin and Horko, *The Lost Generation*, 325.

³⁹ Wang Shu. *Xiaoshu jiashu*. August, 1970.

⁴⁰ Wang Shu. *Xiaoshu jiashu*. September 7, 1970.

am feeling very sad. Where will I be in the future? I have to think about these questions...”⁴¹

The gradual departing of Wang’s fellows reflected a wider phenomenon – many educated youths were attempting to return to their cities or get relocated. In fact, as soon as weeks and months after the urban youth were sent down, their parents tried to get them out of the impoverished countryside.⁴² The usual tactics were to claim illnesses or family issues, though both require certain proof and approval from local cadres, which were not easy to obtain in 1970.⁴³ Many colleagues of Wang were so desperate to return to their home city that they employed their personal connections, bribed the people in power, or even sickened themselves. Feng Qingguang, for instance, might well be mobilizing his parents’ (as cadres) social network to leave the farm, as parents’ relocation was usually not a sufficient reason. Even when the majority of the educated youth did not get the chance to return to their cities, there were still constant parting and social disconnections caused by frequent collective relocations. He told his parents in the letter, “Today another platoon was sent away. Watching our comrades leaving, many female comrades cried out loud, and some male comrades also teared up. I did not tear up at all. Since the year of (19)68... all four people in my class left, so did the twelfth in my school... I really want to cry out loud under my blanket in the house. But how is crying useful? I better think about the future!”⁴⁴ Despite trying to be tough, his words revealed his mixed feelings – his insecurity, vulnerability, and numbness.

⁴¹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. September 7, 1970.

⁴² Yang, *The Red Guard Generation and Political Activism in China*, 115.

⁴³ Thomas B Gold, "Back to the city: The return of Shanghai's educated youth," *China Quarterly* (1980): 755-770.

⁴⁴ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. September 11, 1970.

Three days later, the usual, cheerful Wang was back, and he wrote to his family about the omnipresent topic – work. A dozen days after his hand got stitches, Wang was assigned to watch over the wheatfields overnight. The nights in the north were shivering cold, but Wang powered through whenever he thought of “Chairman Mao’s teaching.” As always, Wang deeply believed that “Mao Zedong Thoughts” could help him conquer all difficulties, including physical fatigue, sleep deprivation, and all the issues in work.⁴⁵ As his hand recovered, his platoon participated in the concrete mixing and casting construction project for national defence. Wang casually mentioned that he “fainted once because of the smell of gasoline.” Again, the son tried to make his discomfort sound like nothing. Instead of complaining about the incident, Wang felt sorry for leaving the production battlefield in the key moment. In return for his hard work, on the eve of the National Day (October 1st), he was awarded the Commendation of the Battalion, to which he dedicated his family as a present. Was Wang an exception for always performing affectionate gestures to his beloved parents in the Red Guard generation, which has been characterized for their rebellion against and hostility towards their parents’ generation?⁴⁶

Wang believed that he could visit home in the near future. A new Circular announced that educated youth working for two years or more could request a leave. Along with other fifty sent-down youth of 1968, Wang was eligible for the opportunity. He wrote with deep sincerity, “Dad and Mom please don’t worry, we will see each other soon.”⁴⁷ Unfortunately, he was let down. In his next letter, Wang disappointingly told his parents that he could not visit home that year. The political commissar stated that sent-down youth could only visit home once every three years, and the poor son had to wait for at least half a year. Wang missed his family so

⁴⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. September 14, 1970.

⁴⁶ For example, Martin Singer marked “resentment to older generation” as a defining characteristic of the educated youth. See Martin Singer, *Educated youth and the cultural revolution in China*, (Michigan: University of Michigan Press, 1971), 80-81.

⁴⁷ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October 19, 1970.

much that he dreamt of seeing them many times, and the feeling was even stronger when his sister and brother both went back home. Wang begged, "Please send me a photo of the whole family, and I will stick my photo on it, so it looks like we are being together."⁴⁸ He did not envision that there would be a time when the whole family reunite again. His solicitude for his family was so sincere and heartfelt, that his self-reassurance of the need to contribute to the Party and the nation seems pale. Wang no longer voiced his disappointment a month later. The debates on political lines in his platoon took away all his energy. He engaged with the debates personally:

All comrades were not willing to speak. I did not dare to speak up too at first. But that was not the behaviour of a true revolutionary, one cannot just by-stand the erroneous line prevailed in the platoon. Some leaders in the platoon supported the erroneous line, and their fellows helped spread it. Therefore in the meeting, we who were the minority made up the courage to speak up. Perhaps we will be the targets of revenge of some leaders, but being revolutionary means being fearless of attacks and vengeance.⁴⁹

Seeing himself as Mao's revolutionary successor, the young man considered speaking against the bureaucrats as risky but necessary. Indeed, he was situated in the turmoil of the Cultural Revolution, when the state structure was dissolving, and one's political fate was more dependent on personal relations than ever.⁵⁰ Young students and power-holding cadres were both vulnerable to political accusations and drastic changes in status. Wang's speech posted risk to either himself or the leaders of the platoon. But were these young people being subversive? Probably not, as it is evident here: "Please don't worry, Dad. I am very calm... We

⁴⁸ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October 19, 1970.

⁴⁹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October, 1970.

⁵⁰ Thomas B Gold, "After comradeship: personal relations in China since the Cultural Revolution," *China Quarterly* (1985): 657-670.

must give our comments to the leaders, but our motive is to help them. One day, cadres who made mistakes will understand.”⁵¹

Unflappably, Wang also told his parent’s bad news – his blanket and coat were all burnt down in a big fire. He simply notified his parents and apologized in advance for using up more money to buy replacements, on which he later spent his monthly salary. It was surprising, even by the standard of his time, that he did not complain nor panic when he looked at the ashes of all his important belongings, but purely stated that it was a “misfortune.” This shows how Wang cared little about his personal, *private* possessions. In his subsequent letters, he repeatedly reaffirmed his parents, who had every reason to, not to worry and pleaded with them not to send him any additional things.⁵²

The undisturbed Wang told his family cordially that a “comrade” was going to visit home. On the eve of the Chinese New Year of 1971, Yip Cuihua was sent by Wang to visit his family on the way back to her home. Interestingly, this female educated youth was the one with whom he previously denied having a close relationship with. He wrote: “Let her tell you my situation. We knew each other well. But don’t let her bring anything for me.”⁵³ And that was his remarks on Yip – nothing explicit about their relationship, but enough disclosure for his parents to get a hunch. In Mao’s China, Confucius’s ideal of minimal heterosociality still triumphed over the Marxist ideal of eliminating gender differences.⁵⁴ Under this social norm, Wang’s parents would have sensed something when Wang mentioned a “she.”

⁵¹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October, 1970.

⁵² Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October, 1970.

⁵³ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. January 14, 1971.

⁵⁴ Zhang Dening and Yue Jianyi, *Zhongguo zhiqing qinglian baogao: qingchun jidi* 中國知青情戀報告：青春極地 [Report on love and sex among China’s sent-down youth: the pinnacle of youth], vol 2 (Beijing: Guangming ribao chubanshe, 1998): 2.

The timid son finally spoke more straightforwardly – though still far from direct – on the matter in his next letter.

But there is a matter laid upon me, it's hard to deal with and I'm inexperienced with it. At first, I didn't want to tell you about it, but in order not to make any mistakes, I have to tell you about this. It's my personal matter. Specifically, it's about her and me. We cared deeply about each other... In the beginning, none of us had put too much thought into it, but then gradually our relationship deepened. We were now in the stage where none expressed our feelings, but we both understood it in our hearts.⁵⁵

Wang described his romantic relationship shyly, and in brief, words pictured out a Platonic romance with a down-to-earth, upright girl. At the same time, Wang was confused about the relationship. And as always, he asked for his parents' advice when he was uncertain. "I did not know why I told you about this," Wang confessed, "but I thought I should not hide anything from my parents, and it helps to let you two learn about it."

Later, Wang regretted telling his parents about Yip. It was not out of shame or concealment, but he felt guilty for making his parents worried:

I should not have told you about this matter in the previous letter, as you had been thinking about it repeatedly overnight and it was holding you up... Now how should I put it? Maybe I am a bit embarrassed, but let me speak of it briefly... Now I am in the fifth company, and she is in the medical unit. I told her to learn the essay "Memory of Norman Bethune" (*Jinian Baiquien*) and write notes persistently. Although we do not meet very often now, we have the opportunity to see each other in battalion meetings.⁵⁶

While Wang's words portrayed a rather distant and aromantic relationship, he planned to marry the girl and form their own family at the age of thirty. In a page of grid paper, Wang illustrated

⁵⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. January 14, 1971.

⁵⁶ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. February, 1971.

a smooth flow of his romance with Yip, based on their comradeship, commitment, and shared political stance. Compared to his zeal for revolutionary labour and study, he was rather detached when describing his relationship. If there was passion and limerence in this romance, he hid it very well in the letters.

Meanwhile, Wang's life at work seems to be on track. He was still getting his hands on the hydraulic construction. The hardworking young man was climbing up the vocational ladder steadily – in February 1971, he was promoted to the deputy platoon leader, then later platoon leader, with an increase in wages.

After many repetitive days in April, Wang's work took a turn. He was sent to a construction site in the army in Bulisu, a town in Northern China. The transferral brought a major change in Wang's romantic life – he had stopped seeing Yip. He told his parents:

I've told her I will never find her again. In one way or another, it was to leave her quickly to avoid more pain in the future. So I was determined to come here to the new battalion for the construction project. And I was really sure, as the fifth battalion was overstaffed with 1500 people, I will definitely not be able to go back. We did not meet when I left. I wrote a letter to her on the last day as a comrade... I saw her outside the regiment the day I left, she smiled at me from afar, but I looked aside and stepped into the car.⁵⁷

Thus the young couple saw each other for the one last time in silence, and never going to meet again. Unlike the parting with his battalion in the train station, in which he admitted bluntly he broke down in tears, Wang did not show his sadness, though the breakup was a heavy blow on his perception of romance. "As for my personal matter, to be honest, before 25 years old I will not think about it again. I am prepared to devote all my energy to the revolutionary work."⁵⁸

⁵⁷ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1971.

⁵⁸ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1971.

He seemed to be living up to his vow in that period and did not mention the topic in the subsequent letters. In the new site, he and other all-male “monks companies” were prepared to toil around the clock for the construction with explosives and machines. Wang earned an improved diet as the working condition was harsher and sleeping time shortened. He got a ration of rice, white flour, and meat, which was considered very decent for the youth in the decade – most sent-down youth-only dreamt of getting away from starvation.⁵⁹ He did need the nutrition to support his hard labour. The ceaseless body could not stand up straight every day after work. Though with a tired physique, Wang still asked his parents to send him more books on politics, especially on heroic models, and engineering, so he could read in his free time. In this new place, the son did not have a lot of friends, thus he pleaded, “Dad and mom, please also send me more letters. Sister and little brother too, send some please.”⁶⁰

It soon came to his birthday on November 2, 1971. “I was lucky this year. The cooking unit sent us noodles with eggs. All comrades said I was blessed to have noodles on my birthday. At night, they accompanied me to the train station to buy candies. It’s a happy day.”⁶¹ Happiness was that simple to Wang at the age of 22.

Wang shifted his focus of “personal matter” from romance to his own prospects. Wang reminded himself not to equate a “promising future” with education qualifications. In the mind of the 22-year-old, introspection and self-reflection were processes of internalizing state propaganda and mobilizations. He often reminded himself to put the interest of the Party first, to base himself on the needs of the revolution. But for the first time, perhaps triggered by the

⁵⁹ Dikötter, *The Cultural Revolution*, 196.

⁶⁰ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. July 21, 1971.

⁶¹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. November 2, 1971.

letters sent from his friends who got into universities, Wang wrote about the possibility of going into the university in 1972. He listed out the preconditions of applying to a university in Harbin. “I seemed very far from the conditions, but I will fight for it!”⁶² Indeed, Wang was right about how hard it was to get recruited by universities, at the time when rumours about admissions and returning to the cities were flying around in the nation, and many educated youths could not wait to flock back to their urban homes. As resistance against rustication grew, cohorts of educated youth were allowed to return to their cities based on medical or family conditions in 1972.⁶³ Wang’s desire to go to a university did not make him slack off at work –Wang hustled around his labour, “I did not stop for even a minute in the battalion. I did not even have time to read the letters.” His half-a-page short letter was proof that he indeed was very busy.⁶⁴

Wang’s life is a mystery to us for the next two years, as there was no letter of the period in the collection. One thing we know is that he did not settle in his home city. Instead, in July 1974, he was a teacher of the ninth grade in the battalion. “It is a tiresome job to take care of the class, but I have a close relationship with my students, and most of them behaved and are considerate.”⁶⁵ Wang was a caring teacher – he spent his salary on his students and visited their families often. Being an always loving brother to his siblings, Wang bought a pair of boots for his younger sister and sent money to his younger brother.

Meanwhile, he began a heterosexual relationship for the first time since his romantic relationship with Yip died out. A male comrade in his regiment introduced Wang to his younger sister, another female educated youth. “She is three years younger than me, shorter than me,

⁶² Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1972.

⁶³ Gold, "Back to the city." Bonnin and Horko, 88-93.

⁶⁴ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1972.

⁶⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. July 3, 1974.

has a healthy body, her family lives in the Harbin mechanic factory, her father is a party member and a cadre, a photo is attached in this letter. We have been exchanging letters a few times, she has mailed me items like pants. I think that is the deal.”⁶⁶ Without mentioning the name of the girl, Wang introduced his partner to his parents in plain, even objective, wordings. However, in his next and also the last letter of the collection, dated February 25, 1975, Wang announced the death of the relationship:

I wrote a letter to Peng (the female educated youth), I was saying that since we were not a match in many aspects, let's call it off. But she wrote to me, saying that she would not find another person aside from me, which made me feel embarrassed. But I was being outright, putting the reasonings out. Our relationship will not last, so calling this off will not have any long-term effects and extra responsibilities. I am devoted to working.⁶⁷

That was how Wang's second attempt with a woman ended, so did his collection of letters. Every word in the letters shows how Wang Shu tried his best to emulate the heroic models in the years he spent in the most northeastern rural part of China. He largely lived out the Lei Feng spirit – love for the Party, for Mao, for labour, and for the people. Among the many faces of Lei Feng, he resembled the national idol the most in his aspiration to be a rustless screw in the collective – eagerly following superiors' commands and overachieving at the most ordinary or tedious positions. The sent-down movement provided a platform for Wang to actualize the ideals and channel his ceaseless energy into manual labour that socialist societies celebrate. He was obedient to the orders from the local government of frequently transferring to various farms and units, even though it meant tougher and unfamiliar tasks and parting from acquaintances – he believed that the Party would send him to wherever most needed. Being given arduous military and agricultural tasks in the border area, Wang could see himself to be another “living

⁶⁶ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1974.

⁶⁷ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. February 25, 1975.

Lei Feng” and sacrifice his life like Jin Xuehe. Although clothed with a modest tone, Wang Shu was actually proud of himself, of his hard work, and dedication to the country – the “sent-down years” was largely a rewarding journey to him.

However, unlike Lei Feng who was martyred and perfected through state-regulated propagation, Wang did not absolutely adhere to the state ideals. The rebellious spirit targeting authorities – against local leaders and one’s parents – was not found in Wang. He was a son filled with Confucius filial piety – constantly easing the worries of his parents, caring for his siblings, sending his salary back home, seeking consent from parents in romantic relationships, being humble before his parents... For his family, Wang tried to buy food from the “private markets.” As scholars pointed out, traditional Chinese ethics persisted through family education even under the anti-Confucianism culture during the Cultural Revolution, in which sons and daughters were still taught to obey.⁶⁸ Moreover, Wang’s letters display his shortcomings in acting and writing, emotions and moments of vulnerability, as well as failure in romantic attempts.

⁶⁸ Chen, "Lost in revolution and reform," 222.

Conclusion

The young Wang Shu was uncritically satisfied with devoting his youth to labouring and political activities. He found meaning in these meticulous tasks and exhausting days by internalizing and identifying with Mao's promulgation. For most of the time, the young man was passionate, motivated and delighted. He represents one of the successful cases of Chinese state inculcation – for Pan Yihong concludes quite precisely, “this was a complex generation. In its members, idealism, heroism, and self-sacrifice were combined with a lack of independent thinking.”⁶⁹

At the same time, the details sketched in his letters add a personal touch to the young ideological-driven man, who was boring, but real. These minor flaws and personal characteristics show that he was just one of the millions of ordinary nameless dislocated youth in China inspired by the Lei Feng spirit. And for that, his story was probably too boring for many editors, publishers, and readers. Dominating educated-youth literature, which focuses on life-changing, dramatic sufferings or achievements, seems to give too little space for us to imagine boring, non-captivating sent-down experiences. Daily routines and trivial matters, perhaps most susceptible to memory loss, in fact, made up the largest part of the educated youth's realities. Wang's letters humanized the educated youth. It bridges the gap between the two opposite popular images of educated youth – helpless victims or indoctrinated fanatics. He was constantly seeking self-improvement, but also single-minded; he adhered to Chinese traditional, but was also a believer of Mao; he toiled around the clock, but also calculated his salary; he was passionate about revolutionary projects, but also missed his family deeply; he celebrated heroic deaths, but also looked for opportunities to go into a university. Wang's letters

⁶⁹ Pan, *Tempered in the revolutionary furnace*, 216.

are gateways for readers to reimagine the fabric of daily life in the sent-down movement. His narrative was so down-to-earth with details in daily life, that one perhaps finds him not as distant to us as we thought. He is an authentic example of the successful state imposition of the Lei Feng model. He reminds us that another vast dislocation project with tragic consequences is not impossible and unacceptable under the regime of the CCP with ordinary teenagers like Wang who can engage in state mobilizations without a thought on its shortcomings and dangers. It is important for historians to look into the Down to the Countryside Movement carefully and closely without the benefits of hindsight, and understand the sent-down generation as they were, so as to reflect on the nature, impact, and replicability of the massive rustication project.

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Appendix

Below are three examples of letters written by Wang Shu in the collection.

All photos are taken by the author.

敬祝毛主席万寿无疆

16

关于姐姐毕业一事，以后安心等待分配。

董林给捐的东两金收到了，请放心。

林

1968年10月25日

20 × 19 = 380

Image 1: The first letter in the collection Wang, Shu, Xiaoshu jiashu. October 5, 1968.

永远忠于伟大领袖毛主席

爸、妈：

你们好！

两次来信均已收到。

此次冯中廉同志回哈去咱家，特捎信回去。

关于我回哈，本应此次一起回去，无奈工作脱身不得；估计我24-25号左右可以起身，26号左右就可以到家。希望文母千万不要着急。

要的东西基本已买好，肥皂、香皂、药皂我都买了，木耳也买了一斤（还没到手）不管怎样，木耳至少也可以带回家去几两。解放胶鞋我们这里没有，手中是可以解决的。至于我的冬季是不成问题的。希望文母不要挂念。

我一定守心工作

1969.5.

Image 2: The second letter in the collection Wang, Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. May, 1969.

敬祝毛主席万寿无疆！

亲爱的爸爸、妈妈、小妹：

你们好！节日快乐

今天是一月二日，已是70年代了！

从家回来已是好几天了，暂时在炊事班工作，爸爸妈妈都知道，赶到节日炊事班很忙，所以拖到今天才给家中写信。

也许这封信很短，现在已经十岁多了！

离开车马班是革命的需要，暂时调到炊事班是革命的需要，只要

有一颗为人民服务的红心，在哪里都一样干好！

节日的晚上总是忙到很晚，而且很想你们，你们想我吗？

又过了一天，今天是一月三日，小妹过生日好！

妈：我把如何过节说给你们好吗？

节日都不休息，全连战备，但过的很好，包了肉馅饺子，一顿饺子是牛肉，一顿饺子是猪肉是鄂伦春卖给我们的，此外鄂伦春还卖给我们不少狍子肉、野猪肉，总之野味很多，还有鲑鱼一斤、二斤大米

初中我学炒菜，会做馒头了，会做饺子了（这回是真会了，只是慢
点）会捏包子了，这都不是吹牛。

爸：我们现在报纸建议挖地道，可惜土冻的太厉害，但为了诺安
毛泽东同志，奋不顾身，为人民的伟大事业，天不怕，地不怕，每挖
一下就是射向苏联一粒子弹！

上封信中提到的秋秋秋梅已经头好，九十五公分的兰秋秋，100
公分的红秋梅，准备给各女一件、小森一件，我暂时保管，你们商量
一下吧！

在黑河和森处共蹲了四天，所带的钱全部用光了。回家后开资
又交了上个月的伙食费七元，扣下本月的伙食费，好不容易才凑齐了
买秋秋秋梅的十六元钱，所以下月可能不给家中寄钱了，希望妈
女原谅，据说不同仅给开十九元，这是有可能的！

小妹又长了一岁，快照张像花给大哥，要带相片的。

大哥向什么买的，希望你好好学习。

伊大娘的木耳暂时没买到，会的和木耳控制太紧，呆几天松
了就好了，现在是新年，春节前后买的较多！

20×16 保存好！ 千万努力！
照快给我寄来！

哈1969. 1. 3
儿村 一月三十

Image 3: The third letter in the collection Wang, Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. January 3, 1970.